

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP 2, Improving the collection, analysis and interpretation of pregnancy pharmacovigilance data

D2.5 Protocols of selected demonstration projects 1-5 uploaded on HMA-EMA Catalogues

(Previous EU PAS Register and ENCePP Resource
Database)

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Document History

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V0.1	3-12-2024	First Draft
V1.0	9-12-2024	Final version
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Abstract

Work Package 2 (WP2) of ConcePTION focusses on sources of primary data collection, such as spontaneous reports, data collected by TIS, literature, pregnancy registries, and enhanced PV studies. The primary goal of this WP was to optimize the collection of pharmacovigilance data on reported pregnancies and enhance the sharing of data and analytical methods to more quickly and effectively assess the risks associated with medication use during pregnancy and lactation. The sub-objectives were: 1) To identify and characterize existing data sources that track medication-exposed pregnancies; 2) To develop new methods and analyses for reported pregnancies; 3) To explore and compare the effectiveness of traditional and novel data collection systems, methodological approaches, and datasets through demonstration studies using diverse data sources; and 4) To create best practice guidelines for a more timely and efficient multifaceted approach to data collection, analysis, and interpretation of reported pregnancies, aiding healthcare providers and pregnant women in evaluating the risk-benefit of medication use during pregnancy.

To achieve these objectives, several demonstration studies were conducted in this WP, divided in five tasks:

1. Demonstration study 1 EU PAS 38841 Analysis and signal detection of pregnancy pharmacovigilance data in spontaneous reports, and literature, (Individual Case Safety Reports originating from published case series, non-interventional studies and patient support programmes)
2. Demonstration study 2 EU PAS 43370 Building a pregnancy pharmacovigilance model for the future: Can pregnancy data collected by ConcePTION partners be analysed using common standards developed by the ConcePTION project?
3. Demonstration study 3 EU PAS 43300-43376 Long-term investigation following exposure to individual medicines in utero: The LIFETIME system
4. Demonstration study 5 EU PAS 44505 Validation of primary source pregnancy pharmacovigilance data

Aim of this report is to provide an overview of the protocols of the various studies that are uploaded in the HMA-EMA Catalogues (Previous EU PAS Register and ENCePP Resource Database)

Protocols uploaded to the HMA-EMA website are shown as supplementary material to this report.

EUPAS 38841

Demonstration study 2.5.1

Analysis of pregnancy pharmacovigilance data in spontaneous reports, and literature, (Individual Case Safety Reports originating from published case series, non-interventional studies and patient support programmes)

PASS information

Title	Analysis of pregnancy pharmacovigilance data in spontaneous reports, and literature, (Individual Case Safety Reports originating from published case series, non-interventional studies and patient support programmes); demonstration study 2.5.1 of the ConcePTION project
Protocol version identifier	1.0
Date of last version of protocol	23-12-2020
EU PAS register number	Study not registered
Active substance	<p>For analysing spontaneous data of (national) pharmacovigilance (PV) centres, the following medicinal products (which are also part of the 2.5.2 protocol) will be covered: alemtuzumab (ATC index L04AA34), azathioprine (L04AX01), (oral) cladribine (L01AA40/L04AA40), cyclophosphamide (L01AA01), daclizumab (L04AC01), dalfampridine (N07XX07), dimethylfumarate (N07XX09), fingolimod (L04AA27), glatiramer (L04AA07), glatiramer acetate (L03AX13), interferon beta-1a (L03AB07), interferon beta-1b (L03AB08), intravenous immunoglobulin, laquinimod (N07XX10), leflunomide (L04AA13), methotrexate (L01BA01), mitoxantrone (L01DB07), mycophenolate mofetil/mycophenolic acid (L04AA06), natalizumab (L04AA23), ocrelizumab (L04AA36), ofatumumab (L01XC10), ozanimod (L04AA38), peginterferon beta-1a (L03AB13), rituximab (L01XC02), siponimod (L04AA42), sodium valproate (N03AG01) and teriflunomide (L04AA31).</p> <p>Other medicinal products (e.g. COVID-19 vaccines and treatments, pertussis vaccine (J07CA09)), might be identified later and added to the list where appropriate.</p>
Medicinal product	See active substance
Product reference	Not applicable
Procedure number	Not applicable
Joint PASS	Not applicable
Research question and objectives	<p>The main objective of demonstration study 2.5.1 is to gain insight into the nature of information on drug exposure during pregnancy from spontaneous reports and literature reports by</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describing the nature and content of spontaneous reporting systems (SRS) and literature data sources • Creating and validating a new optimized assessment tool for the quality of pregnancy data specifically • Describing the quality of reports in SRS, literature, teratology information services (TIS), registries and enhanced PV programme data • Assessing predictors of currently used teratogen signal detection techniques in international case safety reports (ICSR) databases • Exploration of cluster analysis as a possible new teratogen signal detection technique
EFPIA partners	Novartis Pharma AG Novo Nordisk
Academic partners/ENTIS centres	Kwazulu-Natal Research Innovation and Sequencing Platform (KRISP) Swiss Teratogen Information Service UK Teratogen Information Service Pharmacovigilance Centre Lareb
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2. List of abbreviations

ADR	Adverse Drug Reaction
AUC	Area Under the Curve
ATC	Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical classification system
CCSI	Company Core Safety Information
CDE	Core Data Elements
CDM	Common Data Model
EDD	Expected Date of Delivery
EFPIA	European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations
EMA	European Medicines Agency
ENTIS	European Network of Teratology Information Services
EOP	End Of Pregnancy
HCA	Hierarchical Cluster Analysis
HCP	Health Care Professional
ICSR	Individual Case Safety Report
IMI	Innovative Medicines Initiative
LMP	Last Menstrual Period
MAH	Marketing Authorisation Holder
MedDRA	Medical Dictionary for Regulatory Activities
MS	Multiple Sclerosis
OTIS	Organization of Teratogen Information Specialists
PAES	Post Authorisation Efficacy Studies
PASS	Post Authorisation Safety Studies
PRIM	PRegnancy outcomes Intensive Monitoring
PV	Pharmacovigilance
PV-report	Spontaneous reports database of Lareb
ROC	Receiver Operating Curve
SmPC	Summary of Product Characteristics
SQL	Structured Query Language
SRS	Spontaneous Reporting Systems
STIS	Swiss Teratogen Information Service
TIS	Teratology Information Services
UMC	Uppsala Monitoring Centre
WHO	World Health Organization
WMO	Wet Medisch-wetenschappelijk Onderzoek met mensen
WP	Work Package

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5. Abstract

Analysis of pregnancy pharmacovigilance data in spontaneous reports and literature; demonstration study 2.5.1 of the ConcePTION project.

Since limited data from studies performed pre-marketing are usually available before licensure of a medicinal product, we have to rely on post-marketing data from both primary as well as secondary data sources. The IMI funded ConcePTION project aims to enhance the way drug use during pregnancy is studied. This is in part achieved by improving the collection, analysis and interpretation of pharmacovigilance (PV) data, to allow for a more systematic analysis and exchange of data.

Work Package 2 (WP2) focusses on sources of primary data collection, such as spontaneous reports, data collected by Teratogen Information Services (TIS), literature, pregnancy registries, and enhanced PV studies. Tools developed for the analysis of spontaneous reports, however, were not specifically aimed at the analysis of safety information related to pregnancy. As a first step, this demonstration study will aim to gain insight into the nature of information on drug exposure during pregnancy from spontaneous reports and literature reports as filed in the ICSR databases of national PV centres and Marketing Authorisation Holders. The category literature reports therefore encompass Individual Case Safety Reports originating from published case series, non-interventional studies and Patient Support Programmes.

In order to achieve this general aim, 5 sub-studies have been designed. The first sub-study aims to describe the nature and content of spontaneous reports and literature data sources. The second sub-study aims to create and validate a dedicated assessment tool for measuring the clinical quality of pregnancy data specifically, and the third sub-study aims to use this newly developed tool in order to describe the quality of reports in spontaneous reports and literature. This substudy also takes the clinical quality of data from TIS, registries and enhanced PV programme data into account which -for all other aspects- will be studied in demonstration study 2.5.2. Finally, we will explore possibilities to improve the analysis of pregnancy related reports in spontaneous reports databases and literature by studying the characteristics of teratogen signal detection approaches currently in use and we will explore new possibilities for analysis of this data. In order to do that, sub-study 4 will assess predictors of currently used teratogen signal detection techniques in individual case safety reports databases, and sub-study 5 aims to explore cluster analysis as a possible new teratogen signal detection technique.

6. Amendments and updates

Number	Date	Section of study protocol	Amendment or update	Reason
1				
2				
3				

7. Milestones

Milestone	Planned date
Start of data collection	Not applicable
End of data collection	Not applicable
Registration in the EU PAS register	
Final report of study results	

8. Rationale and background

8.1. ConcePTION project

Effects of drug use during pregnancy are often unknown at the time of product licensure because the inclusion of pregnant women in clinical trials is considered unethical. (1) However, treatment during pregnancy is often needed for women with pre-existing chronic conditions such as asthma, epilepsy, cancer, multiple sclerosis (MS) and depression. In daily practice the majority of women take at least one type of medicinal product during pregnancy. (2-4) Knowledge about the safety of drug use during pregnancy is therefore warranted. Since limited data from studies performed pre-marketing are usually available before licensure of a medicinal product, we have to rely on post-marketing data from both primary as well as secondary data sources. With respect to the primary data, several established approaches are currently used to compile and analyse the data on the safety profile of drug use during pregnancy, including data collected by Teratology Information Services (TIS), spontaneous reports, information from literature, organised data collection programmes and registries.

The IMI funded ConcePTION project aims to enhance the way drug use during pregnancy is studied. (4) This is done in part by improving the collection, analysis and interpretation of pharmacovigilance (PV) data, to allow for a more systematic analysis and exchange of data. **WP2** (Work Package 2) focusses on sources of primary data collection, such as spontaneous reports, data collected by TIS, literature, pregnancy registries, and enhanced PV studies.

8.2. Individual Case Safety Reports databases

Post-marketing data are essential to evaluate the safety of drugs used during pregnancy. One way to collect data is via spontaneous reports, also known as Individual Case Safety Reports (ICSRs), which are recorded in databases of national PV centres and Marketing Authorisation Holders (MAHs). ICSRs from products licenced in the European Union are forwarded to the European EudraVigilance database. (5-7) The system is operated by the European Medicines Agency (EMA) and facilitates management and analysis of reported suspected adverse reactions to medicines. (7) The information in these reports is subsequently forwarded by the EMA to the WHO (World Health organization) collaborating centre for international drug monitoring (the Uppsala Monitoring Centre (UMC)), where data can be analysed on a global level. (8) Data collected in spontaneous report databases is retrospective in nature.

For medicinal products available on the European market, also cases described in literature are available as ICSRs in the EudraVigilance database and they can be identified as such. (9) MAHs are responsible for monitoring the medical literature on their licensed products, and reporting individual cases of suspected adverse reactions reported in literature into EudraVigilance and national safety databases - this is a regulatory requirement. (10) MAHs must perform a literature review of widely used reference databases. They must also monitor the scientific and medical publications in local journals in countries where medicinal products have a Marketing Authorisation. Reports of suspected adverse reactions from the scientific and medical literature, published abstracts from meetings and draft manuscripts, must be reviewed and assessed by MAHs to identify and record possible ICSRs. This category encompasses also data from published case series, non-interventional studies and Patient Support Programmes. All this safety information must be included in the safety databases of the MAHs and made available in EudraVigilance. Databases are checked regularly for potential duplicate reports.

Both spontaneous reports and literature data are filed in the ICH-E2B(R3) format. (11) In this demonstration study, cases described in literature are only considered when they have been filed as ICH-E2B(R3) reports in the databases of EFPIA (European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations) partners, EMA or national PV centres.

Other ways to collect information on drug use during pregnancy include TIS, pregnancy registries, and enhanced PV programmes. This type of information sources is mainly covered in the protocol of task **2.5.2** and will therefore not be discussed in detail in this protocol. Only in respect to the development of a tool for measuring and comparing the clinical quality of the data (sub-studies 2 and 3) these sources will be taken into account.

8.3. Relationship between demonstration studies 2.5.1 and 2.5.2

Part of the **WP2** objectives is to develop a common data model (CDM) with a distributed data approach, allowing for one centrally defined data analysis while the data access providers maintain control of their data and their use. Whereas information from spontaneous reports and literature can already be exchanged using the ICH-E2B(R3) standard (11), automated information exchange from other primary data collections for pregnancy (e.g. TIS, registries and enhanced PV programmes) usually is not yet possible.

Following discussion among the **WP2** members, it was decided to focus demonstration study **2.5.1** on spontaneous reporting systems (SRS) and literature data only. Demonstration study **2.5.2** will consider the description of the other data sources in its protocol. The exceptions are sub-study 2 and 3 (**S2** and **S3**) where a dedicated model for the measurement of clinical quality of pregnancy related data will be developed (**S2**) and where we will study possible differences between various sources (**S3**). In these studies we will not only focus on spontaneous reports and literature data, but also the data sources of demonstration study **2.5.2** (e.g. registry data, data from TIS centres and enhanced PV programmes).

In the demonstration studies described in this protocol (like the studies described in the protocol of demonstration study **2.5.2**) special attention is paid to medicinal products registered for MS. The rationale for this is that 1. several pregnancy registries are in place for MS, both drug-specific and disease specific and 2. enhanced PV programme approaches are in place for several MS drugs. Focus on these drugs with the same indication will enable a better alignment of the outcomes among all data sources and studies in **WP2** as well as **WP1**. Apart from medicinal products indicated for MS, the analyses proposed in these demonstration studies may be extended to other medicinal products and indications when considered relevant (e.g. in the case that the power of the studies is too limited or if the generalisability is at risk).

Out of scope of this demonstration study are studies from the general area of preclinical safety, even if reporting teratogenic or mutagenic effects. Subject areas within the scope of the demonstration projects being coordinated by **WP1** (secondary data collection and evaluation), for instance pharmacoepidemiological datasets like (non-)interventional clinical studies (including Post Authorisation Efficacy Studies (PAES) and Post Authorisation Safety Studies (PASS)). This also holds for studies in respect to breastfeeding and outcomes in the infant that will not be taken into account as well as studies focussing on paternal exposure. Finally, in respect to data from literature, only information from case reports as filed in databases from national PV centres and MAHs will be taken into account. Editorials, meta-analyses and review papers will therefore be excluded.

8.4. Rationale

Tools developed for the analysis of spontaneous reports (e.g. disproportionality or other quantitative and qualitative analyses) have not specifically been designed to analyse safety information related to pregnancy. In order to improve this process, as a first step the nature and content of the currently available data in SRS will be described. Additionally, the presence and absence of data that are relevant for the analysis of exposure during pregnancy will be described, as it could show the potential and need of additional pregnancy fields to the existing ICH-E2B(R3) format. (11) Likewise, the quality of the clinical information described in the available reports is unknown; despite a large number of fields available in the ICH-E2B(R3) model, it is not clear if the information is suitable and of sufficient clinical quality to understand the nature of the events that are described. Existing methods to assess the quality were not designed to specifically assess the quality of pregnancy data, and are therefore not suitable for the assessment of reports regarding pregnancy. (12, 13) A need exists to develop a new dedicated model for the measurement of clinical quality of not only ICSRs, but also the data sources of demonstration study **2.5.2** (e.g. registry data, data from TIS centres and enhanced PV programmes).

Apart from describing the content of the available data sources, a need exists for improvement of currently used signal detection techniques. Observations from daily practice are either published in the form of case reports or submitted as (spontaneous) reports to MAHs, national PV centres and international centres like the EMA and the WHO. These observations have been proven to be a useful tool in the detection of safety information in respect to the safety of registered medicinal products used during pregnancy, but they all have their shortcomings and are also not optimized for pregnancy data. (14-18) Knowledge of which aspects play a

role in the process of generating new signals may facilitate the signal detection process. Additionally, current methods are mostly focussed on associations between a medicinal product and a single adverse drug reaction (ADR) while many ICSRs report two or more ADRs. Therefore, we would like to explore the possibilities of cluster analysis as a possible approach for teratogen signal detection.

9. Research question and objectives

The main objective of demonstration study **2.5.1** is to gain insight into the nature of information on drug exposure during pregnancy from spontaneous reports and literature reports by

1. Describing the nature and content of SRS and literature data sources (**S1**)
2. Creating and validating a dedicated assessment tool for measuring the quality of pregnancy data specifically (**S2**)
3. Describing the quality of reports in SRS, literature, TIS, registries and enhanced PV programme data (**S3**)
4. Assessing predictors of currently used teratogen signal detection techniques in ICSR databases (**S4**)
5. Exploration of cluster analysis as a possible new teratogen signal detection technique (**S5**)

The sub-studies addressing these research questions are depicted in brackets.

10. Research methods

10.1. Sub-study 1: Characterization of pregnancy data in SRS and literature reports

Aims	To describe the nature and content of SRS and literature data sources. <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Describe the presence or absence of pregnancy related information in SRS and literature data sources for demonstration drugs- To describe the completeness of important pregnancy related variables in SRS and literature data sources- To describe the presence or absence of specific pregnancy related outcomes in SRS and literature data sources
Leads	Eugène van Puijenbroek, Lareb Yrea Weetink, Lareb
Collaborators	David Lewis, Novartis Other collaborators will be added during the execution of the study
Data sources	PV-report (Lareb), spontaneous and literature reports Argus Safety (Novartis), spontaneous-, literature and solicited (non-interventional studies and patient support programmes) reports

Various types of data sources contain information on the use of medicinal products during pregnancy. However, the way primary data are collected may differ, as well as the nature and content of spontaneous reports and information in literature. Knowledge of these characteristics is needed when data are going to be used and compared with other data sources in a later stage of this project.

Databases containing ICSRs of spontaneous reports and literature data are designed for the assessment and analysis of a wide spectrum of drug related issues (e.g. adverse events), but are not specifically designed to capture information on drug exposure during pregnancy. Consequently, they may lack dedicated fields for important pregnancy-related information. Apart from that, data may be incomplete or stored in the wrong fields.

Data on ICSRs are stored in a predefined format, following the ICH-E2B(R3) guidelines. Previously, a pilot study has been performed on spontaneous reports from Lareb, in which a first overview was made of the completeness of several important ICH-E2B(R3) variables for studying drug use during pregnancy. A comparison was made with the Core Data Elements (CDE), as defined as part of the deliverable of task 2.3. [unpublished data] We concluded that the availability of information varied widely (0.7% for mother's age at last menstrual period (LMP) to 100% for drug name). Non-derived CDE variables (those that could be used to populate the CDE fields directly) had higher availability compared to derived CDE variables (i.e. those variables requiring combining information from ICH-E2B(R3) data fields before they could be used to populate the CDE fields). The source of the report (e.g. health care professional or patient), receive date, origin of report (MAH or other) and several different categories of reported adverse drug reactions (ADRs) during or after pregnancy (i.e. pregnancy complications of the mother, perinatal pathology, major congenital anomalies, maternal ADRs not to pregnancy, and other/undetermined ADRs) were the most relevant predictors for the availability. No data are currently available on the validity of the reports and correctness of the pregnancy related information. This will be determined in task 2.5.5 of the ConCEPTION project.

The objective for this sub-study is to describe the nature and content of SRS and literature data sources as recorded in PV databases. This is achieved by describing the presence or absence of pregnancy related information in SRS and literature data sources for selected medicinal products; to describe the completeness of important pregnancy related variables in SRS and literature data sources, and to describe the presence or absence of *specific* pregnancy related outcomes in SRS and literature data sources. These are relevant questions as they can show differences between (e.g. Lareb vs. Novartis) and within (e.g. spontaneous reports vs. literature reports) the existing data sources. It is expected that these differences exist and by showing these

the found differences may point at the additional value of adding dedicated variables for future ICH-E2B versions.

10.1.1. Study design

This study will be a retrospective observational study using spontaneous and literature reports on pregnancies exposed to medicinal products of interest (see PASS information ‘active substances’, page 1). Spontaneous and literature reports will be collected from databases containing ICSRs, either spontaneous reports or literature cases.

In this sub study, several outcomes will be estimated:

1. The number of pregnancy reports in the total database, stratified per origin (either SRS or literature), per drug of interest (PASS information ‘active substances’, page 1), and per year.
2. The number of selected variables that are completed (irrespective of the quality or correctness of information actually being provided)
3. The number of selected pregnancy related complications and outcomes

An informal comparison will be made to the results of demonstration project **2.5.2** (registries, TIS, enhanced PV programmes).

10.1.2. Setting

This study will be performed on databases of The Netherlands Pharmacovigilance Centre Lareb (PV-report) and Novartis (Argus Safety). Both databases contain both spontaneous reports and literature reports. Argus Safety additionally contains solicited (non-interventional studies and patient support programmes) reports). Data will be analysed on both data sources separately and an informal comparison of the results will be performed.

All reports collected in the timeframe from inception to the 1st of January 2021 will be eligible for inclusion. From start to finish, the study is expected to take 6 months, consisting of 2 months data collection, 2 months data analysis, and 2 months of writing of the report.

Inclusion criteria

- ICSRs have to be related to drug use during, or within 6 weeks before pregnancy. Selection of ICSRs will be done using the pregnancy flag developed by EMA. [currently in the process of being published]
- ICSRs relate to the study drugs specified in PASS information ‘active substances’ (page 1 of this protocol) as ‘suspected’ or ‘interacting’ drug (not applicable for the outcome “total number of pregnancy reports in the database”).
- Coding and assessment of ICSRs has to be completed within the timeframe specified above.

Exclusion criteria

- In case of duplicates only the “master”-report will be taken into account, the underlying reports will be excluded.
- ICSRs regarding drug exposure during breast feeding.
- ICSRs regarding paternal drug exposure

10.1.3. Variables

Selected variables to be assessed for completeness

The variables for the analysis of pregnancy reports are based on the CDEs, defined as ‘essential’. [ConcePTION Deliverable 2.3] All essential CDEs will be assessed for whether these fields are completed. The essential CDEs are: individual case identifiers, linked mother/baby case identifier, primary reporter, primary reporter details, initial report date, mother’s date of birth, mother’s age at LMP, LMP, expected date of delivery (EDD), source of directly-reported EDD, date of end of pregnancy (EOP), prenatal tests, prospective or retrospective data collection (prospective status/true prospective status), drug names, drug start date, drug stop date, drug

indication(s), peri-LMP exposure, trimester 1,2,3 exposure, pregnancy/fetal/neo-natal outcome information (for categories see “pregnancy complications” below), gestational age at EOP, gestational timing of live birth, infant birth weight, infant sex, infant head circumference, death of live born infant, age at death, maternal death, maternal pre-pregnancy medical conditions, and maternal medical conditions arising in pregnancy. At this stage it is not clear if all essential CDE variables can be taken into account. This will be assessed in the early stages of the study. See also the remarks in the introduction section 9.1 of this sub-study on the pilot study that was previously carried out.

Pregnancy complications and outcomes

ICSRs code pregnancy complications (ICH-E2B(R3) field E.i.2.1b) using the Medical Dictionary for Regulatory Activities (MedDRA) version 23.1 (November 2020). (19) In this sub-study the codes assigned will be grouped and categorized by the researchers involved. The categories will be defined as:

- Pregnancy loss (if none of the subgroups is applicable the report will be categorized as live birth)
 - Stillbirth
 - Induced termination
 - Spontaneous abortion
 - Ectopic pregnancy
 - Molar pregnancy
 - Blighted ovum
- Congenital anomalies will be classified according to the EUROCAT classification. (20, 21)
 - Minor (e.g. accessory auricle, sacral pit)
 - Major (e.g. cardiac defects, neural tube defects)
 - Not otherwise specified
 - Other
- Chromosomal defects (e.g. trisomy 21, Turner syndrome)
- Fetal complications (e.g. intrauterine growth restriction)
- Neo-natal complications (e.g. asphyxia, neonatal infection, hypoglycaemia)
- Growth related complications
 - Small for gestational age at delivery
 - Large for gestational age at delivery
 - Fetal growth restriction
- Death of live born infant
- (Neuro)developmental delay (e.g. mental retardation)
- Maternal complications
 - Death
 - Medical conditions arising in pregnancy (e.g. preeclampsia)
 - Complications during/after delivery (e.g. post-partum bleeding, placenta previa)
 - Post-partum complications (e.g. post-partum haemorrhage)
- Maternal none-pregnancy related complication (e.g. injection site inflammation)
- Other
- No adverse pregnancy outcome reported

10.1.4. Data sources

Spontaneous reports, literature reports and solicited reports will be selected from the included data sources: PV-report from the Netherlands PV centre Lareb, and Argus Safety from Novartis.

Ideally, it would be preferable to perform this study on the EudraVigilance database, where all European ICSRs are included. For practical reasons, this is to date not possible. Over the course of this project we will keep studying the possibilities to include data from EudraVigilance in this study.

Pv-report (Lareb)

The Netherlands PV centre Lareb collects and analyses spontaneous reports of suspected adverse drug reactions reported by health care professionals or patients. These reports are recorded in PV-report, the database of Lareb. Spontaneous reports as reported to Lareb (ICSRs) are forwarded to the European EudraVigilance database and the UMC. Cases that have been published in literature are recorded by MAHs and EMA and are also made available in the form of ICSRs in PV-report. (9) PV-report was set up in 1991 (22), and contains over 296000 reports in total as of November 2020. However, this number also included reports not related to pregnancy. Reports regarding drug exposure during pregnancy can be selected using the pregnancy flag developed by the EMA. [to be published over the next months by EMA]

Argus Safety (Novartis)

Novartis Pharma AG is the marketing authorisation holder for a large portfolio of medicinal products, including pharmaceuticals, biological, advanced medicinal therapeutic products and gene therapies. In accordance with European legislation, Novartis is obliged to collect, manage, and submit individual reports of suspected adverse reactions to its authorized medicinal products. Individual case safety reports are recorded in Argus Safety (version 8.1.2.3). Argus Safety comprises Argus Core, Argus Affiliate and Argus J. It is a commercially available application used for data collection of adverse events and reporting of adverse event information. It is a web-based, validated database used for the tracking and processing of all safety cases received by Novartis. Argus Safety was first deployed in 2003, and contains over 8 million case reports as of November 2020. Reports of exposure to medicines during pregnancy can be selected using validated SQL scripts based on a pregnancy flag and additional ICH-E2B(R3) fields. Pregnancy information from Argus Safety has been published (e.g. Geissbühler et al., 2018). (23)

10.1.5. Study size

All cases fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria will be considered for this sub-study. Based on the pilot study previously performed in PV-report, it is estimated that in total (not limited to the demonstration drugs) approximately 4000 spontaneous reports about drug use during pregnancy are available. Upon limitation to the demonstration drugs specified in PASS information 'active substances' (page 1 of this protocol), this number will decrease considerably. It is not possible to have too low numbers in the first part of this study, as the aim is to describe what is available. If the conclusion of the first part is that the numbers are very low, all pregnancy cases (independent of demonstration drugs) could be included for the analysis of availability of variables, or multiple data sources could be combined.

For Argus Safety, 4,859 case reports for fingolimod, 331 for beta interferon, 679 for mycophenolate, and 757 for azathioprine are available. Overall, an estimated >30,000 reports of exposure to medicinal products during pregnancy in association with authorised medicinal products are included in the database (predominately exposures to the mother, but some reports of paternal exposure exist).

10.1.6. Data analysis

Data selection and analysis for the Lareb data will be performed using Microsoft SQL server 2017 and R studio version 2016. First, all pregnancy reports will be selected from the database using the pregnancy flag developed by EMA. [to be published] Descriptive statistics (absolute numbers, percentages) will be used to describe the total number of reports available, and the stratified numbers per origin (e.g. SRS, literature, MAH) and the stratified numbers per drug of interest. For the different drugs of interest, the numbers of reports reported will also be stratified per year, and time series will be used to show the trend of reporting over time (x-axis time, y-axis number of reports).

For all essential CDE variables (as described in section 9.1.3 'variables') it will be described whether the variables are available and if there is not specific variable, whether the information is described in other variables. Thereafter, the completeness of these variables as "IS NOT NULL" will be determined. Variables that have to be derived from other variables will be derived when possible, and thereafter availability of the information in the variables (how well they are filled) is depicted in percentages. In case a variable can be reported and derived, the availability is depicted for both methods separately and also combined. Results will be compared between different strata of drugs and between reports of different origins (e.g. national PV centre, MAH, literature). Reasons for missing values will be discussed.

The reported pregnancy complications will be categorized as described in section 9.1.3 'variables'. Descriptive statistics (absolute numbers, percentages) will be used to describe the number of reports per category, which will again be stratified for origin, demonstration drug and year. Assigned causality will not be taken into account in this study.

10.1.7. Limitations of the research methods

The criteria for determining whether a report is related to pregnancy or not will be based on the EMA pregnancy flag. [to be published] If, during the course of the study, an additional criterion is found to decrease misclassification, this criterion will be taken into account as well.

It is often unclear why variables are missing. It can therefore never be concluded (based on this study design) whether or not completeness of a variable is too low, it is only possible to objectively describe percentages of completeness.

10.1.8. Other aspects

Not applicable

10.2. Sub-study 2: Development and validation of a dedicated assessment tool for measuring the quality of pregnancy data

Aims	Creating, validating and testing a new optimized assessment tool for the quality of pregnancy data specifically
Leads	Eugène van Puijenbroek, Lareb Yrea Weetink, Lareb
Collaborators/tasks	Michael Stellfeld, Novo Nordisk Ursula Winterfeld, STIS Other collaborators will be added during the execution of the study
Data sources	PV-report (Lareb), spontaneous and literature reports STIS, TIS UKTIS, TIS pREGnant (Lareb), registry Gilenya Pregnancy Registry (Novartis), registry Argus Safety (Novartis), PRIM cohort enhanced PV programme

In order to assess the relationship between exposure to a drug and a reported adverse event in a reliable way, detailed clinical information of high quality is needed. Reports in which clinical information is well documented are more likely to contribute to a reliable assessment of drug safety signals since they can provide a more precise statement about the causal relationship between drug use and pregnancy outcome. However, the type and level of detail that is needed to assess the quality of a case may vary, depending on the nature of the reported event, the patient, her underlying conditions, and treatment. This information, that is clinical in nature, may vary between the reports. As an example, for a report concerning an early miscarriage in an otherwise healthy woman, other information will be needed compared to a report concerning a major congenital malformation in which the pregnant woman had been using various drugs and is known to have multiple underlying conditions.

To give an impression of the quality of information, some previous studies explored the completeness of reported information. An example is the VigiGrade completeness score that has been developed to measure the technical completeness of information provided in spontaneous reports of ADRs in general (so not only related to pregnancy), based on which specific fields are filled. (12) However, the presence or absence of information does not automatically reflect the level of clinical information, as required fields may be filled with inadequate, nonspecific, or ambiguous information. Relevant information from a clinical perspective may still be lacking, making it difficult to measure the actual clinical quality and to make a proper assessment.

Oosterhuis et al. (13) developed a tool for documenting the clinical quality taking into account whether information was indeed required for a proper assessment (ClinDoc). It includes four domains for which scores are assigned: the ADR, chronology of the ADR, the suspected drug(s) and finally patient characteristics. The final score categorizes reports into four categories: excellent, well, moderately or poorly documented. The outcome was compared with expert panel judgement. (13) Although a valuable tool for the assessment of the quality of ADRs in general, no existing quality assessment tools are available that are specifically designed for pregnancy data. Especially in these circumstances, different variables are of importance, compared to non-pregnancy data.

10.2.1. Study design

This study will create and validate a new tool (PregDoc) specifically optimized for assessment of the quality of pregnancy data. The tool should be useful for all sources of pregnancy data, i.e. spontaneous reports, literature reports, TIS data, registry data and enhanced PV programme data.

As a first step, a qualitative study will be performed based on interviews among a minimum of 5 experts from the fields of pharmacovigilance, teratology and clinical genetics. These interviews will be based on a set of

proactive and reactive ‘probes’ to guide the course of the interviews. They will be audio-recorded and afterwards transcribed and coded. Based on the collected data, a first model will be developed based on selected elements that play a role in defining the clinical quality. Examples of elements to be considered are the availability of information on the timing of exposure during pregnancy or sufficient information on the medical history to assess the case or outcomes of prenatal diagnostics. The way to assess and describe this information will be described as part of this first step and will be done in collaboration with the expert group that was interviewed.

This first version of the quality tool will be subject to cognitive interviewing (maximum of 10 experts) to gain insight into the way PV assessors understand the questions and how they interpret the answer options, highlighting any ambiguities. Interviews will be transcribed to identify issues where the interviewee had difficulties understanding and answering the quality items. The identified issues will be coded according to a dedicated system containing the following categories: comprehension, interpretation and logical/structural problems. When needed, amendments will be made.

As a next step, the quality tool will be validated with a selected number of 90 representative reports/cases from 6 different data sources (15 per source; spontaneous reports, literature reports, European Network of Teratology Information Services (ENTIS, Switzerland and UK), 2 registries, enhanced PV programme) that will be selected by the expert panel that is involved in the first version of the pregnancy quality assessment tool. This training dataset will be used for the weighing of the parameters of PregDoc. Assigned scores will be compared with the quality grading assigned by the expert group based on global introspection and sensitivity and specificity will be calculated. The performance of the model will be calculated using the Area Under the Curve (AUC) of the Receiver Operating Curve (ROC). (16, 24) When needed, the weighing factors of the selected elements will be adjusted to optimise the performance. The time in which the experts completed the clinical assessment tool, their ability to answer all questions and interrater variability will be evaluated.

As a final step we will test the performance of the revised version of the questionnaire. A minimum of 10 experts will use the tool to assess another 90 reports/cases (15 per data source). Each expert will assess a selection of the cases in order to reduce the workload. All cases will be assessed by 2 experts, and if the results are inconsistent a third expert will decide on the final grading. This test dataset is used to provide an unbiased evaluation of PregDoc fit on the training dataset. The performance of the quality tool will be expressed in terms of specificity and sensitivity.

Although measuring different characteristics, the score of the clinical quality as determined with the newly developed PregDoc tool will be compared to outcomes of the VigiGrade model. For those cases forwarded to the Uppsala Monitoring Centre (i.e. ICSRs and ICSR-literature cases), grading according to the VigiGrade system will take place automatically. The corresponding gradings will be retrieved at the UMC via the Vigilyze system. (12) For cases from non-ICSR data sources (TIS, registries, enhanced PV programmes) the VigiGrade score will not be compared in this study. Comparison of the assigned VigiGrade score and the PregDoc score will be performed informally.

10.2.2. Setting

All data collected in the timeframe from inception to the 1st of January 2021 will be eligible for inclusion. 180 representative reports/cases from 6 different data sources (2 times 15 per source; spontaneous reports, literature reports, ENTIS, 2 registries, enhanced PV programme) will be selected by the expert panel that is involved in the first version of the pregnancy quality assessment tool. These 180 reports will be equally divided in a validation and a test-set. The cases will be selected from PV data sources of the Netherlands PV centre Lareb, TIS centres (Switzerland, UK) and from EFPIA partners (Novartis). Selection criteria for these cases will be based on the first round of interviews with the expert panel. Sufficient variety in quality and clinical picture is important.

The experts that will take part in the interviews and final assessment will be recruited from ENTIS centres and EFPIA partners collaborating in the ConcePTION project. This study is expected to take 6 months, of which 2 months for the design of the new tool, 2 months for the validation, and 2 months of publishing the results.

For all included data sources the following in- and exclusion criteria apply, wherever not already applicable:

Inclusion criteria

- ICSRs/cases have to be related to drug use during, or within 6 weeks before pregnancy. Selection of ICSRs will be done using the pregnancy flag developed by EMA. [to be published]
- Coding and assessment of ICSRs/cases has to be completed within the timeframe specified above.

Exclusion criteria

- In case of duplicates only the “master”-report will be taken into account, the underlying reports will be excluded (applicable to ICSRs).
- ICSRs/cases regarding drug exposure during breast feeding.
- ICSRs/cases regarding paternal drug exposure

Because it is preferable to develop a tool that can be used on all pregnancy cases, this study will not be limited to exposures to the study drugs as specified in PASS information ‘active substances’ (page 1 of this protocol).

10.2.3. Variables

Assessment new tool

For the development and assessment of the new tool, the variables necessary will be determined in the first part of this study.

Assessment VigiGrade

VigiGrade has been developed for defining the quality of spontaneous reports; the measure mainly focussed on the administrative quality and is not designed for a specific clinical situation. Grading has been done automatically when ICSRs have been uploaded to VigiBase, the database of the Uppsala Monitoring Centre (WHO collaborating centre for international drug monitoring), and can be retrieved by national PV centres (among which Lareb). No additional variables are needed for assessment of the ICSRs. (12)

10.2.4. Data sources

PV-report (Lareb), spontaneous and literature reports

The Netherlands PV centre Lareb collects and analyses spontaneous reports of suspected adverse drug reactions reported by health care professionals or patients. These reports are recorded in PV-report, the database of Lareb. Spontaneous reports as reported to Lareb (ICSRs) are forwarded to the European EudraVigilance database and the UMC. Cases that have been published in literature are recorded by MAHs and EMA and are also made available in the form of ICSRs in PV-report. (9) PV-report was set up in 1991 (22), and contains over 296000 reports in total as of November 2020. However, this number also included reports not related to pregnancy. Reports regarding drug exposure during pregnancy can be selected using the pregnancy flag developed by the EMA. [to be published over the next months by EMA]

STIS, TIS

The Swiss Teratogen Information Service (STIS) is dedicated to providing healthcare professionals evidence-based information about medications and other exposures during pregnancy and breastfeeding in Switzerland. Furthermore, STIS staff collects patient data both during initial contact and after a follow-up period covering pregnancy and breastfeeding outcome. STIS is a member of ENTIS. The STIS database consists of pregnant and breastfeeding women that have been reported by a healthcare professional. Maternal characteristics (age, tobacco use, alcohol consumption, medical and obstetric history) and information on medication exposure (indication, timing in pregnancy, duration, dose and concomitant medication) are routinely collected at initial contact and updated through the follow-up process. Follow-up pregnancy and breastfeeding outcome information is collected via postal questionnaire, which is sent to the initial enquiring healthcare professional at first contact and shortly following the expected date of delivery. Information reported at first contact can be corrected when providing outcome information. For pregnancies, collected follow-up data includes delivery

mode, pregnancy outcome, gestational age at delivery, birth weight, length, head circumference and congenital anomalies. Data collection started in 1975 and is continuous with 10506 cases registered in the database (17-11-2020).

UKTIS, TIS

UKTIS are commissioned by Public Health England to be the sole dedicated UK provider of evidence-based information regarding the fetal risks associated with pharmacological and other potentially toxic exposures which arise during pregnancy or the peri-conceptual period. UKTIS are also funded to perform national surveillance of known and emerging human teratogens across the United Kingdom. The UKTIS (United Kingdom) prospective dataset consists of exposed pregnancies that have been reported to the service for counselling advice by a general practitioner (family doctor), general practice nurse or pharmacist, community midwife, hospital-based midwife, obstetrician or other secondary care medical specialist (physician or pharmacist), or a medicines information pharmacist. Follow-up pregnancy outcome information is collected via postal questionnaire, which is sent to the initial enquiring healthcare professional, shortly following the expected date of delivery that was reported at first contact. Outcomes not provided back to the service by 24 weeks after the estimated date of delivery are considered lost to follow-up. All clinical data, including environmental exposures (medicines, occupational chemicals, radiological, biological and social/recreational substances), obstetric history, relevant medical history, and pregnancy outcome information, are reported to UKTIS by healthcare professionals through a standardized data collection procedure. Information reported to UKTIS at first contact can be corrected by the enquirer when providing pregnancy outcome information. In house data consistency calculations are applied for the maternal age at initial reporting to UKTIS, and the expected date of delivery. Clinical advice provided to healthcare professionals is checked by a senior member of the service. A random sample of clinical enquiries are periodically selected and audited for accuracy and completeness of data recording by the Assistant Head of UKTIS. Pregnancy exposure and outcome information collected by UKTIS is recognised by the Caldicott Advisory Panel of Public Health England to be vital for the identification of novel human teratogens, in recognising trends and risks associated with teratogenic exposures, protecting public health from the impact of human teratogens, and monitoring adverse reactions to vaccine and medication exposures which arise during or around pregnancy. Accordingly, UKTIS data collection and processing is covered by section 251 of the National Health Service Act 2006 and Regulation 3 of The Health Service (Control of Patient Information) Regulations 2002 (Public Health England Approval Reference Number: 13091). Under UK law, the NHS Act 2006 and Regulation 3 of The Health Service Regulations 2002 enables the common law duty of confidentiality to be temporarily lifted. This enables healthcare professionals contacting UKTIS to disclose patient identifiable information (name, DoB, NS number) to UKTIS without being in breach of the common law duty of confidentiality. Under these regulations, UKTIS are obligated to remain compliant with all relevant legal data protection and information governance obligations. Data collection started in 1983 and is continuous with 13,840 prospective pregnancy outcomes registered in the database (04-12-2020). UKTIS are not obligated to report any suspected adverse events or reactions to the national regulatory agency (Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency).

pREGnant (Lareb), registry

The Dutch Pregnancy Register pREGnant has been set up to obtain insight into medication use among pregnant and breastfeeding women and into the potential effects on maternal and fetal health. It was launched on April 1st, 2014. Data is collected through six web-based questionnaires filled in by participating women. The data comprise current pregnancy, obstetric history, maternal lifestyle, health and medication use, delivery and infant health. The first questionnaire is sent as early in pregnancy as possible, followed by a second questionnaire in gestational week 17 (unless enrolment was after week 20, then the second questionnaire is skipped). Questionnaires 3 through 6 are respectively sent in gestational week 34, and 8, 26 and 52 weeks after the expected date of birth. All pregnant women of 18 years and older, who are proficient in the Dutch language and have access to internet are eligible for inclusion. All data is collected prospectively, although women can enrol at any time throughout the entire pregnancy. (6) As of 14 October 2020, 4856 women were enrolled.

Gilenya Pregnancy Registry (Novartis), registry

The Gilenya® Pregnancy Exposure Registry was launched in May 2011 to prospectively collect safety data on maternal, fetal and infant outcomes associated with fingolimod exposure during pregnancy and up to 8 weeks before the LMP. At time of enrollment the patient needs to be pregnant, have a diagnosis of MS, was exposed during pregnancy or up to 8 weeks before LMP and signed an informed consent form. No exclusion criteria are applied. Cases are considered prospective if at the time of enrollment, no prenatal testing had been done and pregnancy outcome was not known. Cases are considered retrospective if prenatal tests had been performed at enrollment, while the patient is still pregnant, regardless of their results. The primary outcome measure is the prevalence of major congenital malformations, defined as any structural defects with recognized surgical, medical, or cosmetic importance as per the European Surveillance of Congenital Anomalies (EUROCAT) guidelines, while anomalies were qualified as minor if they were of no serious medical or cosmetic consequence to the child. Other outcome measures included miscarriages, elective abortions, stillbirths, neonatal deaths (counted in live births), and term and preterm live births with or without congenital malformations. (23)

Congenital malformations are judged by external adjudicators (qualified pediatrician, clinical geneticist, teratologist, pediatric neurologist, nephrologist, toxicologist, or clinical pharmacologist), according to the EUROCAT or other guidelines. In cases of discrepancy, cases are classified as the more severe of the two adjudications.

As of 28 Feb 2020, 271 women were enrolled (9 were excluded from analysis due to protocol deviations). 262 women were analysed in the most recent interim report. 177 prospective and 85 retrospective reports.

Argus Safety (Novartis), PRIM cohort enhanced PV programme

The PRIM (PRenancy outcomes Intensive Monitoring) method uses the Argus Safety database (see section 9.1.4. Data Sources) to access prospective pregnancy cases. (25) This method was first developed for fingolimod, a treatment option for MS, due to slow enrolment in the company pregnancy registry. The aim of PRIM was to enhance the process of pregnancy data collection and improve data quality, and in particular to enable estimation of the proportion of major congenital malformation and other pregnancy outcomes. In order to do this, spontaneous reports of maternal exposure to fingolimod in pregnancy or in the eight weeks immediately before the last menstrual period of patients not enrolled in the pregnancy registry were identified. Follow up checklists were sent at four time points:

1. At the time of the initial pregnancy report;
2. At the end of pregnancy;
3. When the infant attained 3 months of age, and
4. When the infant was 12 months old

These questionnaires focused on core data required for derivation of programmed analyses. From 01 Mar 2014 to 28 Feb 2018, a total of 831 prospective maternal exposures with 843 infants were reported, with fetal outcomes reported in 459/843 (54.4%) of those infants. This enabled the calculation of proportions of pregnancy cases with the main pregnancy outcomes and of fetal cases with malformation. The number of reported pregnancies was significantly higher in PRIM than in the registry, showing that structured use of pharmacovigilance data enabled more rapid assessment of risks of maternal drug exposure. (25)

10.2.5. Study size

A minimum of 180 cases related to pregnancy and drug use will be studied (2 times 15 per data source), divided in a set of 90 cases for validation and a set of 90 cases for testing. These numbers should comply with the rule of thumb for prediction models: a minimum of 10 cases should be included per category in the model. Therefore, these numbers might increase after the first round of interviews in the case that more than 9 categories are included. A minimum of 5 experts will participate in the first interviews, a minimum of 10 in the validation, and a minimum of 10 for the testing phase. Experts may be involved in various phases, given the limited number of experts available and in order to reduce the workload for the individual experts.

10.2.6. Data analysis

The development and validation of the dedicated tool to measure the quality of pregnancy related reports/cases will be qualitative in nature. The various steps and calculations that will be conducted are described in section 9.2.1. Study design. Statistical analyses will be performed in R studio version 2016.

10.2.7. Limitations of the research methods

One limitation is that a relatively small number of PV assessors will be interviewed during the content validation. Although it is to be expected that a small group will reveal most critical problems, we cannot rule out the fact that a larger number will be able to reveal additional items. In addition, we will not use a development and test set, as underlying conditions will probably be different.

10.2.8. Other aspects

Not applicable

10.3. Sub-study 3: Quality of information

Aims	To study the quality of information present in SRS, literature reports, TIS data, registry data, and enhanced PV programme data on drug exposure during pregnancy. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To compare the quality of the different data sources - To study the influence of the data source itself and the nature of the pregnancy outcome on the final quality score
Leads	Eugène van Puijenbroek, Lareb Yrea Weetink, Lareb
Collaborators/tasks	David Lewis, Novartis Michael Stellfeld, Novo Nordisk Ursula Winterfeld, STIS Yvonne GeissBühler, Novartis Other collaborators will be added during the execution of the study
Data sources	PV-report (Lareb), spontaneous and literature reports STIS, TIS UKTIS, TIS pREGnant (Lareb), registry Gilenya Pregnancy Registry (Novartis), registry Argus Safety (Novartis), PRIM cohort enhanced PV programme

Sub-study 3 (**S3**) aims to build on **S1** by assessing the quality of information of spontaneous and literature reports by means of the new grading scale developed in **S2** (PregDoc). Additionally, information from TISs, registries and enhanced PV programmes will be included (although the majority of studies on the latter three sources are described as part of demonstration study **2.5.2**).

The assessment and analysis of information on the use of drugs during pregnancy in the post-marketing phase may influence the benefit/risk balance of registered products. Information about the safety of drugs can be based on various sources. As an example, spontaneous reports can be submitted both by consumers and healthcare professionals to national PV centres or MAHs. Information from literature or studies will be also be filed as ICSRs in these databases. (9) Also information from TIS centres, registries and other data collections play an important role in the evaluation of the safety of the use of medicines during pregnancy. It is obvious that the quality of information in these sources may vary, not only depending on the nature of the source, but also on the reporter, the drug that has been used, and the reported outcome. (12, 13, 16) For this reason, knowledge of the quality of the information present in the various data sources is important.

As described before in **S2**, in order to assess the relationship between exposure to a drug and a reported adverse event in a reliable way, clinical information is needed. (13, 16) Reports in which clinical information is well documented are more likely to contribute to a reliable assessment of drug safety signals since they can provide a more precise statement about the causal relationship. However, the type and level of detail that is needed to be able to perform assessment of a case may vary between reports, depending on the nature of the reported event, the patient and underlying conditions and treatment.

In this sub-study we will analyse potential differences in the quality of the information available in SRS, literature reports, TIS data, registry data, and enhanced PV programme data, that may contribute to the detection of new safety signals. In **S2** a new tool was designed to assess the quality of pregnancy data specifically (PregDoc) that will be used to assess the quality of several data sources containing pregnancy data.

The primary aim of this sub-study is to study the quality of information present in SRS, literature reports, TIS data, registry data, and enhanced PV programme data on drug exposure during pregnancy. The secondary aim is to informally compare the quality of the different data sources, and to study the influence of the data source itself and the nature of the pregnancy complication or outcome on the final quality assessment. No a priori

hypothesis has been included as no assumptions can be made about the quality of the information in the different data sources.

10.3.1. Study design

This study will be a retrospective observational study into the quality of information of ICSRs concerning spontaneous reports and information from literature (as ICSRs in PV database), and TIS data, registry data, and enhanced PV programme data. 6 data sources are selected: spontaneous reports, literature reports, ENTIS data (Switzerland, UK), 1 or 2 registries (Lareb and/or Novartis), and an enhanced PV programme. For all individual sources, forty cases will be selected randomly for quality assessment (240 in total). The two included TIS centres will each provide 20 cases to make a total of 40 cases for the included ENTIS data. These cases will be made available in a structured format that contains the information deemed necessary for the use of the tool for quality assessment. When applicable, cases will be anonymized and potential suggestions that may point at the origin of the cases will be removed, in order to blind the researchers for the reporting source of the case.

Assessment of the cases will be performed by two researchers who will be selected during the course of the study. They will appraise the quality of the reports independently using the PregDoc method designed in **S2**. Both researchers will provide a grading of the quality as described in this approach. Based on the results of **S2**, classes representing various levels of quality will be determined. For those cases in which the assigned quality classes of the researchers differ, both assessors will reconvene and discuss their grading, in order to come to an agreement. In case agreement cannot be reached, a third researcher will assess the case and decide which value (and thus quality class) will be appointed.

10.3.2. Setting

For all six sources (SRS, literature, ENTIS, 1 or 2 registries, enhanced PV programme) 40 cases (240 in total) will be selected randomly for quality assessment. All data collected in the timeframe between 1-1-2016 and 1-7-2021 will be eligible for inclusion.

From start to finish, the study is expected to take 9 months, consisting of 4 months selection and anonymization, 3 months of assessment, and 2 months of analysis and writing of the report.

In- and exclusion criteria

The same in- and exclusion criteria as described in **S2** (section 9.2.2. Setting) will be taken into account. Additionally, all ICSRs/cases have to relate to the study drugs specified in PASS information 'active substances' (page 1 of this protocol) as 'suspected' or 'interacting' drug.

10.3.3. Variables

For the assessment of the PregDoc score, variables as described in the deliverable of **S2** will be used.

10.3.4. Data sources

The same data sources as described in **S2** (section 9.2.4. Data sources) will be used.

10.3.5. Study size

For each of the six data sources 40 cases (40 in total) will be randomly selected. Since no data on the quality of these type of reports exist yet, it is not possible to make a formal power calculation.

10.3.6. Data analysis

Per data source 40 cases (240 in total) will be randomly selected by means of random number generators. Based on **S2** important categories will be selected as additional selection criteria to make sure an even selection is made between the data sources, if necessary.

After converting the cases to the right format based on the data fields needed for assessment with PregDoc, the selected cases will be anonymised and identifiers that may reveal the origin of the cases will be removed, in

order to blind the assessors for the reporting source of the case. After anonymisation the selected cases will be sent to one researcher, who will blind, combine and randomise the data of the different sources.

In order to reduce workload, cases will be randomly divided over researchers who are blinded for the source of the cases. They will appraise the quality of the reports independently using the PregDoc method developed and validated in **S2**. All cases will be assessed by two experts, who will both provide a grading of the quality as described in this approach. Based on the results of **S2**, classes representing various levels of quality will be determined.. For those cases in which the assigned quality classes of the researches differ, both assessors will reconvene and discuss their grading, in order to come to an agreement. In case agreement cannot be reached, a third researcher will assess the case and decide which value (and thus quality class) will be appointed.

Differences in quality between various data-access providers will be specified, stratified for spontaneous reports, literature reports, ENTIS data, the two registries (Lareb, Novartis), or enhanced PV data. Depending on the documentation tool developed in **S2** differences in partial aspects of the clinical quality can be specified. An informal comparison between the different data sources will be done, and the influence of the data source and the nature of the pregnancy complication/outcome on the final quality assessment will be analysed via linear regression modelling. Statistical analyses will be performed in R studio version 2016.

10.3.7. Limitations of the research methods

In this study a relatively small number of cases will be studied, given the heterogeneity of data. Since the analysis will mainly focus on drugs selected as demonstration drugs, generalisability of the outcomes will be limited.

10.3.8. Other aspects

Not applicable

10.4. Sub-study 4: What predicts a signal?

Aims	Assessing predictors of currently used teratogen signal detection techniques in ICSR databases
Leads	David Lewis, Novartis
Collaborators/tasks	Amalia Alexe, Novartis Bitia Rezaallah, Novartis Eugène van Puijenbroek, Lareb Michael Stellfeld, Novo Nordisk Yrea Weetink, Lareb Other collaborators will be added during the execution of the study
Data sources	PV-report (Lareb), spontaneous and literature reports Argus Safety (Novartis), spontaneous-, literature and solicited (non-interventional studies and patient support programmes) reports

The aim of the analysis of Individual Case Safety Reports (ICSRs) in pharmacovigilance is the early detection of previously unrecognized adverse reactions, and obtaining information on new aspects of previously known associations (those listed in the company core safety information, CCSI). Signal detection historically relied on the analysis, by trained PV assessors of the content of the ICSRs submitted by health care professionals (HCPs) and consumers. (26) Potential signals will undergo a detailed analysis in which other reports in the database and other sources of information are taken into account. Over the past decades, the number of ICSRs increased considerably, so additional approaches were developed to support the signal detection process. An example is disproportionality analysis, which enabled the screening of large amounts of data. Nevertheless, it is obvious that this approach has its shortcomings from an epidemiological point of view. (16-18) For this reason, the outcome of disproportionality analysis will be combined with other information such as the number of reports in the database, the source of the reports, if an association is labelled or not, or a possible pharmacological mechanism. This information will be used to select those associations that should be studied in more detail to assess if they represent a true safety signal. Although the contribution of various elements for the detection of safety signals in pharmacovigilance in general has been studied in detail (16), it is not clear which factors may contribute to the actual selection of safety signals in case of drug exposure during pregnancy. **S4** aims to improve the teratogen signal detection approach by studying which factors contribute to the selection of safety signals in cases related to teratogen signal detection.

10.4.1. Study design

This study will be a retrospective observational study determining predictors for medicinal product-ADR signal generation. The model will be based on ICSRs in the ICH-E2B(R3) format. (11) All included medicinal product-ADR associations expressed as MedDRA/ATC with a minimum of 3 reports will be assessed for whether they resulted in a signal or not. With all resulting medicinal product-ADR associations a prediction model will be made.

For this study, a reliable gold standard needs to be developed. An option is to use a reference list with associations with positive and negative controls that are based on the product information of the demonstration drugs (see PASS information 'active substances', page 1). Another option might be to take the moment on which association were highlighted as positive controls into account, since it cannot be ruled out that at this moment the number of reports were increased due to notoriety bias. It has to be checked if this information is only available to the MAHs of the product or also in the public domain. This may limit the amount of drugs that can be taken into account in this study. True signals could be based on company decision points (e.g. decision recorded by Medical Safety Review Committee) or on regulatory actions taken (e.g. CCSI or SmPC change).

10.4.2. Setting

This study will be performed on databases of The Netherlands Pharmacovigilance Centre Lareb (PV-report) and the Novartis PV database (Argus Safety). Both databases contain both spontaneous reports and literature reports; in addition the company database includes solicited reports (from non-interventional studies and patient support programmes). Data will be analysed on all data sources separately and an informal comparison of the results will be performed.

All reports collected in the timeframe from inception to the 1st of January 2022 will be eligible for inclusion. From start to finish, the study is expected to take 6 months, consisting of 2 months data collection, 2 months data analysis, and 2 months of writing of the report.

In- and exclusion criteria

The same in- and exclusion criteria as described in **S1** (section 9.1.2. Setting) will be taken into account.

10.4.3. Variables

The outcome variable of the prediction model will be whether the association between the medicinal product and the ADR led to a signal or not. Expected possible predictors are aspects that are usually involved in the process of signal detection. The possible predictors that will be included are: absolute number of ICSRs on the drug-ADR combination, lower limit of the 95% confidence interval (LL) of the reporting odds ratio (ROR) with the full database as the comparison group, the LL of the ROR with pregnancy reports as a comparison only, the percentage of the ICSRs on the drug-ADR association reported by HCPs, the percentage of ICSRs on the drug-ADR association derived from MAHs, whether the drug-ADR association is classified as serious, the time the drug has been on the market, the presence or absence of important variables as described in **S2**, the presence or absence of important variables as described in **S1**, the type of pregnancy complication/outcome (see classification in section 9.1.3. Variables). Additionally, it could be of interest to see how other variables could be taken into account in this study. An example are the Bradford Hill criteria, that play a role in the assessment of the causal relationship between the drug and the reported event. (26) It is possible that some of these criteria can also be used as predictors in this study. The feasibility of applying these predictor variables will be considered in more detail over the course of the project. The final choice for number and type of variables will after all depend on the number of associations that will be studied.

10.4.4. Data sources

Both spontaneous reports and literature reports will be selected from the included data sources: PV-report from the Netherlands PV centre Lareb, and Argus Safety from Novartis.

Ideally, it would be preferable to perform this study on the EudraVigilance database, where all European ICSRs are included. For practical reasons, this is to date not possible. Over the course of this project we will keep studying the possibilities to include data from EudraVigilance in this study.

Pv-report (Lareb)

The Netherlands PV centre Lareb collects and analyses spontaneous reports of suspected adverse drug reactions reported by health care professionals or patients. These reports are recorded in PV-report, the database of Lareb. Spontaneous reports as reported to Lareb (ICSRs) are forwarded to the European EudraVigilance database and the UMC. Cases that have been published in literature are recorded by MAHs and EMA and are also made available in the form of ICSRs in PV-report. (9) PV-report was set up in 1991 (22), and contains over 296000 reports in total as of November 2020. However, this number also included reports not related to pregnancy. Reports regarding drug exposure during pregnancy can be selected using the pregnancy flag developed by the EMA. [to be published over the next months by EMA]

Argus Safety (Novartis)

Novartis Pharma AG is the marketing authorisation holder for a large portfolio of medicinal products, including pharmaceuticals, biological, advanced medicinal therapeutic products and gene therapies. In accordance with

European legislation, Novartis is obliged to collect, manage, and submit individual reports of suspected adverse reactions to its authorized medicinal products. Individual case safety reports are recorded in Argus Safety (version 8.1.2.3). Argus Safety comprises Argus Core, Argus Affiliate and Argus J. It is a commercially available application used for data collection of adverse events and reporting of adverse event information. It is a web-based, validated database used for the tracking and processing of all safety cases received by Novartis. Argus Safety was first deployed in 2003, and contains over 8 million case reports as of November 2020. Reports of exposure to medicines during pregnancy can be selected using validated SQL scripts based on a pregnancy flag and additional ICH-E2B(R3) fields. Pregnancy information from Argus Safety has been published (e.g. Geissbühler et al., 2018). (23)

10.4.5. Study size

All cases fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria will be considered for this sub-study. Based on the pilot study previously performed in PV-report (described in S1), it is estimated that in total (not limited to the demonstration drugs) approximately 4000 spontaneous reports about drug use during pregnancy are available. Upon limitation to the demonstration drugs specified in PASS information 'active substances' (page 1 of this protocol), this number will decrease considerably.

For Argus Safety, 4,859 case reports for fingolimod, 331 for beta interferon, 679 for mycophenolate, and 757 for azathioprine are available. Overall, an estimated >30,000 reports of exposure to medicinal products during pregnancy in association with authorised medicinal products are included in the database (predominately exposures to the mother, but some reports of paternal exposure exist).

If the numbers are too low to perform this study, multiple data sources could be combined, the study could be expanded to inclusion of other drugs, and/or pre-signals could be included as an outcome.

10.4.6. Data analysis

Data will be collected using Microsoft SQL Server 17, and data analysis will be performed using R studio version 2016. All drug-ADR associations of the demonstration drugs mentioned in PASS information 'active substances' (page 1 of this protocol) consisting of at least 3 reports that are eligible for inclusion will form the basis for the development of the prediction model. A multivariable logistic regression based prediction model (outcome signal yes or no) will be developed and validated using the list with validated safety signals as the gold standard for the outcome.

First, contingency tables will be made in order to have a first look at the possible predictors of safety signals. This will be done for all predictors (as described in section 9.4.3. Variables). As a second step, univariable logistic regression models will be made with the same predictors. Results of the models will be reported in table format including the prediction values, p-values and 95% confidence intervals.

In the case that more of the tested predictors seem to be relevant from the contingency tables and univariable models, multivariable logistic regression models will be made. Backwards step-wise selection will be used with $P < 0.05$ (Wald test) as a selection criterion. For all possible predictors the variance inflation factor will be calculated to investigate collinearity, using 4 as a cut-off value. In case collinearity is found, this will be reported and only one variable will be included in the prediction model. Results of the models will be reported in table format including the prediction values, p-values and 95% confidence intervals.

Performance of the model will be calculated using the Area Under the Curve (AUC) of the Receiver Operating Curve (ROC). (16, 24) It should be noted that, although its' name may suggest differently, the prediction model that will be developed is not a substitute for the clinical, pharmacological and teratological analysis of the underlying cases. This approach only allows for an initial impression of the performance of the various candidate predictor variables in terms of sensitivity and specificity and their combined performance versus the gold standard that will be applied in this study.

If possible, the models will be validated on other (larger) datasets, such as EudraVigilance. (7)

10.4.7. Limitations of the research methods

A limitation of this study is the risk of bias due to selective reporting. Because PV databases contain well established associations, it is reasonable to assume that these associations are reported more frequently than unknown associations, which may influence the predictors in the model. Another limitation is that predictors will be assessed, but not tested in a separate dataset. Since a limited number of drugs is used, generalisability will be limited.

10.4.8. Other aspects

Not applicable

10.5. Sub-study 5: Cluster analysis as a possible new teratogen signal detection technique

Aims	Exploration of cluster analysis as a possible new teratogen signal detection technique
Leads	Eugène van Puijenbroek, Lareb Yrea Weetink, Lareb
Collaborators/tasks	David Lewis, Novartis Michael Stellfeld, Novo Nordisk Other collaborators will be added during the execution of the study
Data sources	PV-report (Lareb), spontaneous and literature reports Argus Safety (Novartis), spontaneous-, literature and solicited (non-interventional studies and patient support programmes) reports

As described in section 7.4. Rationale, we will explore new methods of teratogen signal detection techniques, specifically cluster analysis. The starting point in the detection of safety signals in spontaneous reporting usually is the association between a suspected medicinal product and a single reported term (product-event combination). This also holds for the analysis of ICSRs related to exposure to drugs during pregnancy. In reality however, the majority of reports are coded with multiple ADRs. As an example, over 60% of pregnancy related reports at Lareb have 2 or more reported terms. Often, there will be a reason for co-reporting these terms. For example, these terms express the same underlying phenomenon (e.g. nausea and vomiting, itching and rash, bruising and tendency to bleed), they represent an underlying syndrome (e.g shortness of breath, low blood pressure, urticaria), or have a similar common cause (diabetes and myocardial infarction), etc. Finally, coding one or multiple events in a single patient is impacted by coding standards and coding conventions. (27) although multiple factors may influence coding practices, focussing on drug-single ADR association in the analysis of ICSRs only, will ignore the link between the co-reported terms. This aspect is currently not routinely taken into account in the analysis of ICSRs.

In this sub-study we will examine if the use of cluster analysis will allow for a meaningful classification of reported adverse events in ICSRs related to pregnancy in order to support the signal detection. Cluster analysis seeks to identify natural subgroups in data with closer resemblance between items within a subgroup than between items in different subgroups. It represents a form of unsupervised learning, where the classes and their profiles are derived from data without additional guidance. (28) However, the approach requires dedicated knowledge to interpret the outcomes of the analysis based on for instance the clinical background and pathogenesis to determine if the results are indeed meaningful. For this reason, this study is exploratory in nature. As cluster analysis is an assumption free method no a priori hypothesis can be included.

The WHO collaborating centre UMC has previously used a new approach in cluster analysis, specifically designed for the purpose of signal detection of pharmacovigilance data (28), but the exact statistical approach remains unpublished, but is expected early 2021. In this study we will start exploring the possibilities of regular clustering methods such as Hierarchical Cluster Analysis (HCA) in data sources of Lareb and Novartis. (29) We will explore the possibility of performing cluster analysis in VigiBase (UMC) in this protocol. Additionally, as described in **S1** and **S4**, we will continue studying possibilities for collaboration with the EMA EudraVigilance database as well.

10.5.1. Study design

This study will be a retrospective observational cohort study of pregnancy related cases of products mentioned in PASS information 'active substances' (page 1 of this protocol). Cases will be analysed at the MedDRA Preferred Term (PT)-level and ATC code of the suspected drugs. Drugs will be taken into account individually and as classes, in order to find the most optimal method in this exploratory analysis.

Several approaches for cluster analysis are in use. In this study we will explore the possibilities of HCA as a teratogen signal detection technique. In the case that a collaboration with the UMC/WHO can be formalised, the possibility of consensus clustering [to be published] will be assessed as well.

Obtained clusters will be reviewed by clinicians to determine the backgrounds of the cluster (e.g. pharmacological profile, clinical scenario, etc.). For all clusters it will be assessed whether the association was known by means of comparison to the SmPC and consultation of teratology experts.

10.5.2. Setting

This study will be performed on databases of The Netherlands PV Centre Lareb (PV-report) and Novartis (Argus Safety). Both databases contain both spontaneous reports and literature reports; the Novartis system also includes solicited reports (from non-interventional studies and patient support programmes). Data will be analysed from both data sources separately and an informal comparison of the results will be performed.

All reports collected in the timeframe from inception to the 1st of January 2022 will be eligible for inclusion. From start to finish, the study is expected to take 6 months, consisting of 2 months data collection, 2 months data analysis, and 2 months of writing of the report.

In- and exclusion criteria

The same in- and exclusion criteria as described in **S1** (section 9.1.2. Setting) will be taken into account.

10.5.3. Variables

Spontaneous reports code pregnancy complications (ICH-E2B(R3) field E.i.2.1b) using the Medical Dictionary for Regulatory Activities (MedDRA) version 23.1 (November 2020). (19) The reported MedDRA PT fields will be taken into account as well as the ATC codes for the suspected drugs as mentioned in PASS information 'active substances' (page 1 of this protocol). Other variables that will be taken into account are: maternal age, duration of pregnancy, source of the reports, and trimester of exposure.

10.5.4. Data sources

Both spontaneous reports and literature reports will be selected from the included data sources: PV-report from the Netherlands PV centre Lareb, and Argus Safety from Novartis.

Pv-report (Lareb)

The Netherlands PV centre Lareb collects and analyses spontaneous reports of suspected adverse drug reactions reported by health care professionals or patients. These reports are recorded in PV-report, the database of Lareb. Spontaneous reports as reported to Lareb (ICSRs) are forwarded to the European EudraVigilance database and the UMC. Cases that have been published in literature are recorded by MAHs and EMA and are also made available in the form of ICSRs in PV-report. (9) PV-report was set up in 1991 (22), and contains over 296000 reports in total as of November 2020. However, this number also included reports not related to pregnancy. Reports regarding drug exposure during pregnancy can be selected using the pregnancy flag developed by the EMA. [to be published over the next months by EMA]

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Novartis Pharma AG is the marketing authorisation holder for a large portfolio of medicinal products, including pharmaceuticals, biological, advanced medicinal therapeutic products and gene therapies. In accordance with European legislation, Novartis is obliged to collect, manage, and submit individual reports of suspected adverse reactions to its authorized medicinal products. Individual case safety reports are recorded in Argus Safety (version 8.1.2.3). Argus Safety comprises Argus Core, Argus Affiliate and Argus J. It is a commercially available application used for data collection of adverse events and reporting of adverse event information. It is a web-based, validated database used for the tracking and processing of all safety cases received by Novartis. Argus Safety was first deployed in 2003, and contains over 8 million case reports as of November 2020. Reports of exposure to medicines during pregnancy can be selected using validated SQL scripts based on a pregnancy flag

and additional ICH-E2B(R3) fields. Pregnancy information from Argus Safety has been published (e.g. Geissbühler et al., 2018). (23)

10.5.5. Study size

All cases fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria will be considered for this sub-study. Based on the pilot study previously performed in PV-report (described in **S1**), it is estimated that in total (not limited to the demonstration drugs) approximately 4000 spontaneous reports about drug use during pregnancy are available. Upon limitation to the demonstration drugs specified in PASS information 'active substances' (page 1 of this protocol), this number will decrease considerably. If the numbers are too low to perform this study, multiple data sources could be combined.

For Argus Safety, 4,859 case reports for fingolimod, 331 for beta interferon, 679 for mycophenolate, and 757 for azathioprine are available. Overall, an estimated >30,000 reports of exposure to medicinal products during pregnancy in association with authorised medicinal products are included in the database (predominately exposures to the mother, but some reports of paternal exposure exist).

10.5.6. Data analysis

Data selection and analysis will be performed using Microsoft SQL server 17, R studio version 2016 and/or IBM SPSS statistics 22. All pregnancy reports eligible for inclusion will be selected from the database using the pregnancy flag developed by EMA. [to be published]

A cluster analysis method often used is HCA, which generates a series of models with cluster solutions from 1 (all cases in one cluster) to n (each case is an individual cluster). HCA also allows for working with specific variables as opposed to cases and can handle various types of data (e.g. nominal, ordinal etc.); however it is not recommended to mix different levels of measurement. The use of this method for teratogen signal detection will be explored in this study, by means of using various scenarios in order to find the most optimal one. (29) For example, stratification will be performed for known teratogens/medicinal products with a minimum of 10 years information available vs. more recent products.

All obtained clusters will be independently reviewed by two different clinicians to determine whether clusters are probably based on the pharmacological profile, clinical scenario or for other reasons. Differences will be discussed and in case of disagreement a third reviewer will make the final decision (Delphi method). (30) The outcomes will be informally compared with the available knowledge in the Summary of Product Characteristics (SmPC) of the various products under study, and will be discussed with teratology experts as it is expected that the SmPCs do not contain a lot of information on safety of drug use during pregnancy.

10.5.7. Limitations of the research methods

This study is exploratory in nature, which means that no definite conclusions can be made. Apart from that, the outcomes of cluster analysis will strongly depend on the interpretation of the experts involved. As this is part of the method, it will not limit this study, but it might limit the possibilities of cluster analysis as a teratogen signal detection technique.

10.5.8. Other aspects

Not applicable

11. Quality control and data management

11.1. Data recording and source data

Quality monitoring for completeness and correctness of data retrieved from the included data sources will be performed.

11.2. Confidentiality and coding

Project data are handled with utmost discretion and are only accessible to authorized personnel who require the data to fulfil their duties within the scope of the research project. Data will not include any patient identifier. For **S2** and **S3** clinical information will be needed for the comparison of the quality. Though data will be provided in an anonymised approach, confidentiality agreements will be signed by researchers involved with the data.

11.3. Data collection and transmission

Data collection of sub-studies can be combined in the studies where the same inclusion criteria apply. For **S2** and **S3** STIS and UKTIS will be combined as ENTIS data in RedCap. Data collection from the pREGnant registry is labour intensive as the analysis database is not yet ready. In the case that the research or the timelines are restricted because of this reason, pREGnant data may not be taken into account.

Data transmission is only applicable for **S2** and **S3**, where data of different sources will be combined. This will be done via a standard template or table that has to be filled for all data sources. Data will be anonymized and confidentiality agreements will be signed by researchers involved with the data.

11.4. Retention and destruction of study data

Data stay under the responsibility of each data access provider. Hence, study data will be handled according to local requirements.

Lareb

Processed data will be stored for preservation and further sharing, because it is the actual data that produces the research results. Data will be preserved for a period of 10 years after the project ends. Data will be archived in the Lareb archive.

Novartis

Processed data will be archived for reference and further sharing, because the research results are applicable to a specific dataset. Data will be managed and maintained for a period of 10 years after the completion of the IMI ConcePTION project. Data will be archived in a secure and private records management system which complies with GxP standards.

STIS

Data will be preserved for a period of 10 years after the project ends. Data will be archived in the STIS archive.

UKTIS

Data will be preserved for a minimum period of 10 years after the project ends, and will be securely stored in accordance with the local data protection agreements of the Newcastle upon Tyne Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust IT network.

11.5. Local quality control measures

PV-report (Lareb)

Data are collected and filed according to European Regulations following the Good Pharmacovigilance Guidelines (GVP) as published on the EMA website. (10) Data are stored in ICH-E2B(R3) format following data validation rules as specified in ICH. (11) Data are exchanged with the EudraVigilance database following the specifications as mentioned in the GVP guidelines. (10) Data cleaning and coding of the information is carried out by trained assessors of pharmacovigilance centre Lareb.

UKTIS

All clinical data, including environmental exposures (medicines, occupational chemicals, radiological, biological and social/recreational substances), obstetric history, relevant medical history, and pregnancy outcome information, are reported to UKTIS by healthcare professionals through a standardized data collection procedure. Information reported to UKTIS at first contact can be corrected by the enquirer when providing pregnancy outcome information. In house data consistency calculations are applied for the maternal age at initial reporting to UKTIS, and the expected date of delivery. Clinical advice provided to healthcare professionals is checked by a senior member of the service. A random sample of clinical enquiries are periodically selected and audited for accuracy and completeness of data recording by the Assistant Head of UKTIS.

STIS

The STIS database has been registered with the « Préposée à la protection des données et à l'information du canton de Vaud » (local authority for data protection) and the Swiss Health Observatory. Access to the database is limited to professionals in charge of the STIS activity (secure and limited computer access). The professionals involved in STIS activities are subject to the respect of legal confidentiality. Quality monitoring of data entry into the database is regularly performed.

pREGnant (Lareb)

All data is collected through web-based questionnaires, which allow for technical checks, validations and internal controls to minimize false entries of data. Completed questionnaires are checked by assessors in order to make sure all data is documented in the correct fields. Medication use is ATC coded, while maternal morbidities, pregnancy and partus related data and data on congenital anomalies is coded in ICD-10. Coding of anomalies is based on EUROCAT standards and a team of clinicians is available for consultation if necessary. In case of congenital anomalies additional clinical information, with permission of a participant, is requested from the paediatrician or family physician. If additional information is needed from other data sources (e.g. pharmacy, clinical records), participants can be contacted to obtain permission for these additional data requests.

Argus Safety (Novartis)

The Quality System for the Novartis Pharmacovigilance system operates in accordance with the guidance set-down in GVP Module 1 'Pharmacovigilance systems and their quality systems'. (31) This quality system is described in detail within the Novartis Pharmacovigilance System Master File (v27.0, 15 Oct 2020). Data are collected and filed according to European Regulations following the Good Pharmacovigilance Practice Modules (GVPs) as published on the EMA website. (10) Data are stored in an extended ICH-E2B(R3) format following data validation rules as specified in ICH (11) and in accordance with 21 CFR Part 11. (32) Data are submitted to the EudraVigilance database following the specifications within the GVP guidelines. (10) Data cleaning and coding of the information is carried out by trained pharmacovigilance specialists in accordance with GPVP and GCP guidelines. AUDITS INSPECTIONS

12. Protection of human subjects

The protection of human subjects is dependent on national regulations. As this project is performed in various settings, the applicable laws per location will be discussed, including data privacy.

The Netherlands

This study does not need approval by a medical ethical committee according to the Dutch regulations ('niet-WMO plichtig' Wet Medisch-wetenschappelijk Onderzoek met mensen).

United Kingdom

This study does not require review by Research Ethics Committees for sites in England, Scotland, Wales or Northern Ireland. This was verified by use of the tool @ <http://www.hra-decisiontools.org.uk/ethics/>.

Switzerland

In Switzerland this study using anonymized data does not require ethics committee approval.

13. Management and reporting of adverse events/adverse reactions

In case signals will be detected during the course of these demonstration studies signals will be handled according to the current and local rules and regulations. (33)

14. Plans for disseminating and communicating study results

Results of this study will be used in the ConcePTION project and published in a peer reviewed scientific journal if possible. Authorship in scientific publication will have to satisfy the conditions of the Uniform Requirements for Manuscripts Submitted to Biomedical Journals (www.icmje.org/icmje-recommendations.pdf.)

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Annex 1. List of stand-alone documents

Number	Document reference number	Date	Title
1			
2			

Annex 2. ENCePP checklist for study protocols

Doc.Ref. EMA/540136/2009

ENCePP Checklist for Study Protocols (Revision 4)

Adopted by the ENCePP Steering Group on 15/10/2018

The [European Network of Centres for Pharmacoepidemiology and Pharmacovigilance \(ENCePP\)](#) welcomes innovative designs and new methods of research. This Checklist has been developed by ENCePP to stimulate consideration of important principles when designing and writing a pharmacoepidemiological or pharmacovigilance study protocol. The Checklist is intended to promote the quality of such studies, not their uniformity. The user is also referred to the [ENCePP Guide on Methodological Standards in Pharmacoepidemiology](#), which reviews and gives direct electronic access to guidance for research in pharmacoepidemiology and pharmacovigilance.

For each question of the Checklist, the investigator should indicate whether or not it has been addressed in the study protocol. If the answer is "Yes", the section number of the protocol where this issue has been discussed should be specified. It is possible that some questions do not apply to a particular study (for example, in the case of an innovative study design). In this case, the answer 'N/A' (Not Applicable) can be checked and the "Comments" field included for each section should be used to explain why. The "Comments" field can also be used to elaborate on a "No" answer.

This Checklist should be included as an Annex by marketing authorisation holders when submitting the protocol of a non-interventional post-authorisation safety study (PASS) to a regulatory authority (see the [Guidance on the format and content of the protocol of non-interventional post-authorisation safety studies](#)). The Checklist is a supporting document and does not replace the format of the protocol for PASS presented in the Guidance and Module VIII of the Good pharmacovigilance practices (GVP).

Study title: Analysis of pregnancy pharmacovigilance data in spontaneous reports, and literature, (Individual Case Safety Reports originating from published case series, non-interventional studies and patient support programmes); demonstration study 2.5.1 of the ConcePTION project

EU PAS Register® number:
Study reference number (if applicable):

Section 1: Milestones	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
1.1 Does the protocol specify timelines for				
1.1.1 Start of data collection ¹	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.x.2
1.1.2 End of data collection ²	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.x.2
1.1.3 Progress report(s)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
1.1.4 Interim report(s)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
1.1.5 Registration in the EU PAS Register®	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
1.1.6 Final report of study results.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.x.2

¹ Date from which information on the first study is first recorded in the study dataset or, in the case of secondary use of data, the date from which data extraction starts.

² Date from which the analytical dataset is completely available.

Comments:

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<u>Section 2: Research question</u>	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
2.1 Does the formulation of the research question and objectives clearly explain:	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2.1.1 Why the study is conducted? (e.g. to address an important public health concern, a risk identified in the risk management plan, an emerging safety issue)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	8.4 and 10.x
2.1.2 The objective(s) of the study?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	9
2.1.3 The target population? (i.e. population or subgroup to whom the study results are intended to be generalised)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.x.2
2.1.4 Which hypothesis(-es) is (are) to be tested?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
2.1.5 If applicable, that there is no <i>a priori</i> hypothesis?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.x

Comments:

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<u>Section 3: Study design</u>	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
3.1 Is the study design described? (e.g. cohort, case-control, cross-sectional, other design)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.x.1
3.2 Does the protocol specify whether the study is based on primary, secondary or combined data collection?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	8
3.3 Does the protocol specify measures of occurrence? (e.g., rate, risk, prevalence)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
3.4 Does the protocol specify measure(s) of association? (e.g. risk, odds ratio, excess risk, rate ratio, hazard ratio, risk/rate difference, number needed to harm (NNH))	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
3.5 Does the protocol describe the approach for the collection and reporting of adverse events/adverse reactions? (e.g. adverse events that will not be collected in case of primary data collection)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

Comments:

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<u>Section 4: Source and study populations</u>	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
4.1 Is the source population described?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.x.4
4.2 Is the planned study population defined in terms of:				
4.2.1 Study time period	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.x.2

<u>Section 4: Source and study populations</u>	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
4.2.2 Age and sex	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.x.2
4.2.3 Country of origin	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.x.4
4.2.4 Disease/indication	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.x.2
4.2.5 Duration of follow-up	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
4.3 Does the protocol define how the study population will be sampled from the source population? (e.g. event or inclusion/exclusion criteria)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.x.2

Comments:

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<u>Section 5: Exposure definition and measurement</u>	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
5.1 Does the protocol describe how the study exposure is defined and measured? (e.g. operational details for defining and categorising exposure, measurement of dose and duration of drug exposure)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
5.2 Does the protocol address the validity of the exposure measurement? (e.g. precision, accuracy, use of validation sub-study)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
5.3 Is exposure categorised according to time windows?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
5.4 Is intensity of exposure addressed? (e.g. dose, duration)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
5.5 Is exposure categorised based on biological mechanism of action and taking into account the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of the drug?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
5.6 Is (are) (an) appropriate comparator(s) identified?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

Comments:

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<u>Section 6: Outcome definition and measurement</u>	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
6.1 Does the protocol specify the primary and secondary (if applicable) outcome(s) to be investigated?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.x.1 and 10.x.3
6.2 Does the protocol describe how the outcomes are defined and measured?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.x.3
6.3 Does the protocol address the validity of outcome measurement? (e.g. precision, accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, use of validation sub-study)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

Section 6: Outcome definition and measurement	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
6.4 Does the protocol describe specific outcomes relevant for Health Technology Assessment? (e.g. HRQoL, QALYs, DALYS, health care services utilisation, burden of disease or treatment, compliance, disease management)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

Comments:

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Section 7: Bias	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
7.1 Does the protocol address ways to measure confounding? (e.g. confounding by indication)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
7.2 Does the protocol address selection bias? (e.g. healthy user/adherer bias)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
7.3 Does the protocol address information bias? (e.g. misclassification of exposure and outcomes, time-related bias)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

Comments:

Wherever confounding of bias is a possibility it is considered and described, however, bias in the conventional sense is not included in this study as it is mainly descriptive and exploratory.
--

Section 8: Effect measure modification	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
8.1 Does the protocol address effect modifiers? (e.g. collection of data on known effect modifiers, subgroup analyses, anticipated direction of effect)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

Comments:

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Section 9: Data sources	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
9.1 Does the protocol describe the data source(s) used in the study for the ascertainment of:				
9.1.1 Exposure? (e.g. pharmacy dispensing, general practice prescribing, claims data, self-report, face-to-face interview)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.x.4
9.1.2 Outcomes? (e.g. clinical records, laboratory markers or values, claims data, self-report, patient interview including scales and questionnaires, vital statistics)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.x.4
9.1.3 Covariates and other characteristics?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.x.4
9.2 Does the protocol describe the information available from the data source(s) on:				

Section 9: Data sources	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
9.2.1 Exposure? (e.g. date of dispensing, drug quantity, dose, number of days of supply prescription, daily dosage, prescriber)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
9.2.2 Outcomes? (e.g. date of occurrence, multiple event, severity measures related to event)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
9.2.3 Covariates and other characteristics? (e.g. age, sex, clinical and drug use history, co-morbidity, co-medications, lifestyle)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
9.3 Is a coding system described for:				
9.3.1 Exposure? (e.g. WHO Drug Dictionary, Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) Classification System)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.x.3 and 10.x.4
9.3.2 Outcomes? (e.g. International Classification of Diseases (ICD), Medical Dictionary for Regulatory Activities (MedDRA))	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.x.3 and 10.x.4
9.3.3 Covariates and other characteristics?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.x.3 and 10.x.4
9.4 Is a linkage method between data sources described? (e.g. based on a unique identifier or other)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.x.1 and 10.x.6

Comments:

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Section 10: Analysis plan	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
10.1 Are the statistical methods and the reason for their choice described?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.x.6
10.2 Is study size and/or statistical precision estimated?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.x.5
10.3 Are descriptive analyses included?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.x.6
10.4 Are stratified analyses included?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.x.6
10.5 Does the plan describe methods for analytic control of confounding?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
10.6 Does the plan describe methods for analytic control of outcome misclassification?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
10.7 Does the plan describe methods for handling missing data?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
10.8 Are relevant sensitivity analyses described?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

Comments:

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<u>Section 11: Data management and quality control</u>	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
11.1 Does the protocol provide information on data storage? (e.g. software and IT environment, database maintenance and anti-fraud protection, archiving)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	11
11.2 Are methods of quality assurance described?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	11.5
11.3 Is there a system in place for independent review of study results?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Comments:

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<u>Section 12: Limitations</u>	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
12.1 Does the protocol discuss the impact on the study results of: 12.1.1 Selection bias? 12.1.2 Information bias? 12.1.3 Residual/unmeasured confounding? (e.g. anticipated direction and magnitude of such biases, validation sub-study, use of validation and external data, analytical methods).	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
12.2 Does the protocol discuss study feasibility? (e.g. study size, anticipated exposure uptake, duration of follow-up in a cohort study, patient recruitment, precision of the estimates)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	11

Comments:

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<u>Section 13: Ethical/data protection issues</u>	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
13.1 Have requirements of Ethics Committee/ Institutional Review Board been described?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	12
13.2 Has any outcome of an ethical review procedure been addressed?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
13.3 Have data protection requirements been described?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	11 and 12

Comments:

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<u>Section 14: Amendments and deviations</u>	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
14.1 Does the protocol include a section to document amendments and deviations?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	6

Comments:

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Section 15: Plans for communication of study results	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
15.1 Are plans described for communicating study results (e.g. to regulatory authorities)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	14
15.2 Are plans described for disseminating study results externally, including publication?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	14

Comments:

Name of the main author of the protocol:

Yrea Weetink, MSc (Lareb)

Date: 30/November/2020

Signature: _____

EUPAS 43370

Demonstration study 2.5.2

Building a pregnancy pharmacovigilance model for the future: Can pregnancy data collected by ConcePTION partners be analysed using common standards developed by the ConcePTION project?

PASS information

Title	Building a pregnancy pharmacovigilance model for the future: Can pregnancy data collected by ConcePTION partners be analysed using common standards developed by the ConcePTION project?
Protocol version identifier	1.0
Date of last version of protocol	30.09.2021
EU PAS register number	EUPAS43370
Active substance	<p>For ENTIS partners and pregnancy registries (Lareb) the following drugs (with the indication for multiple sclerosis) will be covered: alemtuzumab (ATC index L04AA34), azathioprine (L04AX01), cladribine (L04AA40), daclizumab (L04AC01), dimethylfumarate (N07XX09), fingolimod (L04AA27), glatiramer (L04AA07), glatiramer acetate (L03AX13), interferon beta-1a (L03AB07), interferon beta-1b (L03AB08), methotrexate (L01BA01), mitoxantrone (L01DB07), natalizumab (L04AA23), ocrelizumab (L04AA36), ofatumumab (L01XC10), ozanimod (L04AA38), peginterferon beta-1a (L03AB13), rituximab (L01XC02), siponimod (L04AA42) and teriflunomide (L04AA31)</p> <p>For EFPIA partners, pregnancy registries and enhanced pharmacovigilance (PRIM) programmes covering the following drugs will be in scope: fingolimod (L04AA27), teriflunomide (L04AA31), oral cladribine (L04AA40), ofatumumab (L01XC10), siponimod (L04AA42)</p> <p>Other drugs might be identified later and added to the list.</p>
Medicinal product	
Product reference	NA
Procedure number	NA
Marketing authorisation holder(s)	NA
Joint PASS	No
Research question and objectives	Objective: To determine whether pregnancy data collected by ConcePTION partners (ENTIS centres, enhanced pharmacovigilance programmes used by EFPIA partners, prospective pregnancy registries used by EFPIA partners, the Dutch Pregnancy Drug Register and other organisations) can be analysed using common data standards, clinical and technical definitions, and reporting algorithms developed by the ConcePTION project.
EFPIA partners	Novartis, Novo Nordisk, Merck KGaA, Sanofi; other EFPIA partners might be identified later and added to the list
ENTIS centres/countries	UK, Israel (Jerusalem, Zerifin), Switzerland, Lareb; other registries or countries might be identified later and added to the list.
Authors	Ursula Winterfeld, Guillaume Favre, Laura Yates, Svetlana Shechtman, Luke Richardson, Maya Berlin, Alan Moore, Yvonne Geissbuehler, Michael Stellfeld, Greg McBride, Alison Oliver

Marketing authorisation holder(s)

Marketing authorisation holder(s)	NA
MAH contact person	NA

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2. List of abbreviations

ATC	Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical classification system
CDE	Core Data Elements
CIOMS	Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences
DAP	Data access provider
EDD	Expected Date of Delivery
EFPIA	European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations
EMA	European Medicines Agency
ENTIS	European Network of Teratology Information Services
EOP	End Of Pregnancy
EUROCAT	European Surveillance of Congenital Anomalies
GVP	Good Pharmacovigilance Guidelines
IMI	Innovative Medicines Initiative
LMP	Last Menstrual Period
MACDP	Metropolitan Atlanta Congenital Defects Program
MAH	Marketing Authorisation Holder
MS	Multiple Sclerosis
NHS	National Health Service
OTIS	Organization of Teratology Information Specialists
PASS	Post Authorisation Safety Studies
PRIM	PRegnancy outcomes Intensive Monitoring
STIS	Swiss Teratogen Information Service
TIS	Teratology Information Services
UK	United Kingdom
WP	Work Package

3. Responsible parties

Swiss Teratogen Information Service, Service de Pharmacologie Clinique, CHUV, Rue du Bugnon 17, 1011 Lausanne, Switzerland

The Israeli Teratology Information Service, Israel Ministry of Health, Jerusalem, Israel

Clinical Pharmacology and Toxicology Unit, TIS Zerifin, Shamir Medical Center (Assaf Harofeh), Zerifin, Affiliated to Sackler School of Medicine, Tel-Aviv University, Tel Aviv, Israel

KRISP, University of KwaZulu-Natal, Durban, South Africa

Merck Healthcare KGaA, Darmstadt, Germany

Novartis Pharma AG, Basel, Switzerland

Novo Nordisk, Novo Alle, DK-2880 Bagsvaerd, Denmark

Sanofi, Paris, France

The Netherlands Pharmacovigilance Centre Lareb, Goudsbloemvallei 7, 5237 MH 's-Hertogenbosch, The Netherlands

This study is performed as a pilot study under demonstration project 2 of task 2.5 in the IMI funded ConcePTION project.

4. Abstract

Building a pregnancy PV model for the future: Can pregnancy data collected by ConcePTION partners be analysed using common standards developed by the ConcePTION project?

Rationale and background: Very little evidence-based information is currently available to optimise treatment with respect to the safe use of most medications during pregnancy. The ConcePTION project aims to change the way drug use during pregnancy is studied and reported to the scientific and regulatory community and to the public. As part of this project, common standards of data collection and reporting of pregnancy data have been established. This includes definition of Core Data Elements (CDEs) considered necessary for the prospective follow-up of exposed pregnancies. Implementation of aligned clinical definitions and coding standards for CDEs and implementation of aligned statistical methodology in future study protocols may greatly enhance the possibilities for conducting meta-analyses of data-sets collected by different stakeholders and/or comparative assessments of data from studies within the same disease area.

Objective: The objective of this pilot study is to determine whether pregnancy data collected by ConcePTION partners can be analysed using common data standards, common clinical and technical definitions, and common reporting algorithms developed by the ConcePTION project.

Study design: This study will test the degree to which data from various data access providers (DAPs) can conform to the definitions of the CDEs established in ConcePTION task 2.3 of Work Package 2. In particular, it will be evaluated whether conversion of the data structures of individual DAPs is possible in terms of clinical perspectives - do the clinical definitions being used in the individual DAPs align with those of the CDE; and technical processing perspectives - is it possible to convert the DAP data to the CDE fields either directly (requiring a technical conversion, for example, different date-formats) or is a more complex conversion needed? The feasibility of populating predefined table shells with existing pregnancy data from various data access providers will be tested.

Population: Prospective and retrospective cases from exposures in pregnancy and the peri-LMP period to drugs used for the indication of multiple sclerosis from the primary data collections participating in the ConcePTION project will be used in this pilot study. The main analysis will focus on prospectively reported pregnancy cases. Cases with exposures to teratogenic/fetotoxic drugs will be excluded.

Variables: Work Package 2 of the IMI ConcePTION project has defined (as Task 2.3) a set of CDEs. Clinical definitions and technical definitions were established for each CDE.

The variables to be included in this pilot study retrieved from each data source are based on the CDEs, defined as ‘essential’.

Data sources: Pregnancy exposure reports in scope for this study will be obtained from three types of data collection methods: pregnancy registries (Gilenya (Novartis), Aubagio (Sanofi), the Dutch Pregnancy Drug Register), EFPIA enhanced pharmacovigilance (PRIM) programmes (Gilenya, Siponimod and ofatumumab (Novartis), worldwide pregnancy surveillance program of oral cladribine (MAPLE-MS) (Merck Healthcare KGaA)), and data from selected European Network of Teratology Information Services (ENTIS) databases. Other data access providers might be identified later and added to the list.

Study size: This study will analyse data on pregnancies complying with the inclusion and exclusion criteria from each data access provider. Each DAP will summarise its ability to align its data to the CDE guidance, irrespective of sample size. The DAPs will be required to populate the pre-defined summary tables if they can provide data on ≥ 10 cases with known pregnancy outcomes.

Data analysis: The ability of each DAP to create an analysis dataset of elements conforming to the definitions of the CDEs established in ConcePTION task 2.3 of Work Package 2 will be described and discussed together with the processes used by them. Using this dataset each DAP will be asked to populate pre-defined summary tables according to the guidance in the Statistical Analysis Plan. Summary tables include information on pregnancy cases reported, pending, lost to follow up, and those with known maternal characteristics and risk factors, and known pregnancy outcomes (pregnancy and fetal outcome including congenital malformation) by timing of exposure. The populated tables will be discussed regarding informal comparisons and comparability between the analyses provided by each DAP.

Milestones: Protocol approval 09/2021, registration in the EU PAS register 09/2021, final report of study results 30.03.2023.

5. Amendments and updates

None

6. Milestones

Milestone	Planned date
Protocol approval	28.09.2021
Registration in the EU PAS register	30.09.2021
Final outputs received from each DAP	30.09.2022
Final report of study results	30.03.2023

7. Rationale and background

More than 5 million women become pregnant in the EU every year and the majority take at least one medication during pregnancy (1,2). Yet no or limited evidence-based information is currently available on most medications to optimize treatment according to reproductive safety, to reduce risks associated with drug use during pregnancy and to inform a woman's decision.

The ConcePTION project aims to change the way drug use during pregnancy is studied and reported to the scientific and regulatory community and to the public. As part of this project common standards of data collection and reporting of pregnancy data have been established. This includes definition of Core Data Elements (CDEs) considered necessary for the prospective follow-up of exposed pregnancies. Implementation of aligned clinical definitions and coding standards for CDEs and implementation of aligned statistical methodology in future study protocols may greatly enhance the possibilities for conducting meta-analyses of datasets collected by different stakeholders and/or comparative assessments of data from studies within the same disease area.

In the present pilot study, analysis of pregnancy data from a number of centres within the European Network of Teratology Information Services (ENTIS) as well as data from pregnancy exposure registries and enhanced pharmacovigilance programmes (PRenancy outcomes Intensive Monitoring (PRIM)) collected by Marketing Authorisation Holders (MAHs) are considered as well as other related primary data collections (e.g. the Dutch Pregnancy Drug register).

Pregnancy exposure registries are studies that collect health information on pregnancy and fetal outcomes exposed to medicinal products during pregnancy from patients who agree to participate and who give formal consent. Registries can be initiated by pharmaceutical companies, academic groups or research groups and can focus on a single drug, a drug class or a disease. There are well-documented challenges of patient enrolment into pregnancy registries (3, 4). However, registries provide important prospective data which may allow estimation of risk of a particular outcome.

A MAH receiving spontaneous reports of pregnancies exposed to its medicine is legally required to follow up those pregnancies and enter resulting data in the MAH's safety database (5). Although spontaneous reporting is particularly useful for detection of rare events and those with a long time to onset, reports tend to be biased towards negative outcomes and therefore may be less reliable from an epidemiological perspective. However, enhanced pharmacovigilance programmes with a structured end-to-end process approach for pregnancy surveillance with targeted checklists to obtain follow-up information and detailed data processing can enable analyses similar to those of a pregnancy registry (6). In both cases, selection of suitable comparators is often challenging, especially when the medical condition itself may be associated with the pregnancy outcome.

ENTIS is a network of centres across and beyond Europe that was established post-thalidomide. Although these centres are funded and operate independently to answer clinical enquiries regarding maternal use of medications in pregnancy and lactation, most collect information on the pregnancy outcome according to a similar protocol. For many years, ENTIS centres have undertaken multicentre studies (7-10) to assess the fetal risk of medications for which data are lacking, or in response to a possible concern regarding safety. Due to the lack of a central ENTIS database, this has involved a laborious multi-step process of manually extracting and combining anonymized data

from participating centres in an Excel sheet. The lack of a pre-approved 'ready to go' system and visibility of the number of cases of exposed pregnancies for which data are available further compromises the rate at which data are analysed and the ability to efficiently identify a potential teratogenic signal. Although developing a new central ENTIS database would be ideal, currently this would require information being manually entered from each centre's clinical service base, adding additional pressure to an already stretched and underfunded system. Use of common standards of data collection and reporting offers a possible solution that would enable a faster and more automated method of undertaking real-time surveillance of data collected by ENTIS centres. Moreover, it would enable the exchange with other data sources.

It is presently unknown whether existing data from ENTIS centres, from ongoing pregnancy registries, and from enhanced pharmacovigilance programmes collected by pharmaceutical companies are aligned with respect to clinical definitions and coding standards as defined by ConcePTION. In particular, it is useful to know if data from individual data access providers (DAPS) can be aligned in terms of:

- Clinical perspectives: do the clinical definitions being used in the individual DAPs align with those of the CDE
- Technical processing perspectives: is it possible for the DAP to create the CDE fields directly or is a more complex conversion needed?

This pilot study aims to evaluate whether selected variables considered essential for reporting of pregnancy outcomes are aligned with, or can be converted towards, such standards. This will be examined for four ENTIS centres, as well as for selected pregnancy exposure registries, and for selected enhanced pharmacovigilance programmes. If successful, it is envisaged to test whether data from these data sources can be analysed using standardized statistical methodology and be presented in table shells predefined by ConcePTION. Results of the tables from the three types of data collection methods will be informally compared. The aim is that the statistical analysis plan developed for this study can serve as a guidance document for future studies.

The study focuses on drugs used for Multiple Sclerosis (MS). The rationale for this is that

- various EFPIA partners are MAHs of MS drugs:
 - o several drug specific MS pregnancy registries and
 - o several PRIM programmes are in place for several MS drugs and can be used for this study.
- several disease specific pregnancy registries are in place for MS.

Focus on drugs with the same indication will facilitate relevant comparison of pregnancy outcomes from the various data sources.

8. Research question and objectives

Within the broader aim of building a pregnancy pharmacovigilance model for the future the objective of this study is to determine whether pregnancy data collected by ConcePTION partners (ENTIS centres, enhanced pharmacovigilance programmes used by EFPIA partners, prospective pregnancy registries used by EFPIA partners, the Dutch Pregnancy Drug Register and other organisations) can be analysed using common data

standards, common clinical and technical definitions, and common reporting algorithms developed by the ConcePTION project.

9. Research methods

9.1. Study design

This study will use data from different ENTIS databases, from prospective pregnancy registries, and from enhanced pharmacovigilance programmes. A descriptive comparison will be made of the various aspects of the different data sources. It is envisaged that the approach described above may facilitate comparisons of pregnancy data for different MS drugs collected by ENTIS and EFPIA partners and other related primary data collections.

9.2. Setting

All prospective and retrospective cases exposed during pregnancy and the peri-LMP period fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria from the following primary data collections (registry data, enhanced pharmacovigilance (PRIM) programme data, and data from several ENTIS centres) participating in the ConcePTION project will be used in this pilot study.

For each contributed medication each DAP will decide on a suitable initial and final data cut-off date for the summarised data series. The initial cut-off is likely to be the start of data collection at the time of approval of the medication. The final data cut-off point should be as late as possible but may be determined according to feasible timelines. The initial and final cut-off dates will be displayed in the summary table headers.

The main analysis will focus on prospectively reported pregnancy cases.

9.2.1 Prospective in retrospective case definition

Among retrospectively reported cases, abnormal outcome such as congenital malformations or pregnancy losses might be overrepresented due to reporting bias. Hence, the high risk of bias resulting from retrospective reporting of pregnancy cases is acknowledged. Therefore, the summary tables focus on prospectively reported cases there.

The preferred definition of a prospectively-reported case (and conversely that of a retrospectively-reported case) is that in the current version of the CDE document. This is referred to as “Simple prospective status”.

It is acknowledged that this classification might not be used by all DAPs. However, it might be possible to construct the preferred definition of pro-/retrospective from information collected on the initial pregnancy report date. If the data required for this transformation are not available and reclassification from the DAP’s definition to the “Simple prospective” definition is not possible, then the DAP should endeavour to use the “True prospective status” definition.

Lastly, if the “True prospective status” cannot be implemented, the DAP should use the “EMA prospective status” definition.

The following table indicates the preferred order of chosen definition.

Note that the prenatal screening tests referred to in these definitions are those which may be capable of identifying congenital anomalies (refer to the CDE document for details).

Regardless of which definition is possible, the same definition must be applied to every pregnancy case in the supplied dataset. If the status (prospective vs. retrospective) of an individual case is unknown, the case should be set to retrospective; this has the effect of excluding the case from most summary tables.

Table 1 Preferred definitions of prospective/retrospective pregnancy status

	Prospective	Retrospective
1. “Simple” Prospective status	Prospective - Report of any exposure which occurs during pregnancy/peri-LMP period whilst the patient is still pregnant.	Retrospective - Report of any exposure which occurs during pregnancy/peri-LMP period after the pregnancy has ended
2. True Prospective status (CDE definition)	True prospective: - Report of any exposure which occurs during pregnancy/peri-LMP period whilst the patient is still pregnant but before any prenatal screening capable of identifying congenital anomalies has been performed.	True retrospective: - Report of any exposure which occurs during pregnancy/peri-LMP period after the pregnancy has ended, or a report of any exposure which occurs during pregnancy/peri-LMP period whilst the patient is still pregnant but after any prenatal screening capable of identifying congenital anomalies has been performed
3. “EMA” Prospective status	EMA prospective: - Report of any exposure which occurs during pregnancy/peri-LMP period whilst the patient is still pregnant but before diagnosis of a foetal malformation via prenatal screening.	EMA retrospective: - Report of any exposure which occurs during pregnancy/peri-LMP period after the pregnancy has ended, or a report of any exposure which occurs during pregnancy/peri-LMP period whilst the patient is still pregnant but <u>after</u> detection of a foetal malformation via prenatal screening

9.2.2 The peri-LMP period

The peri-LMP period is the period immediately before the start of pregnancy during which the carry-over effect of the MS medication of the contributed data may potentially affect the fetus. Prospectively-reported pregnancies with exposure to the MS medication during this period (as well as those exposed during the pregnancy itself) contribute to the required summary tables.

The length of the peri-LMP period is product-specific and determined by the guidance in the following table taking into consideration aspects other than the half-life such as mechanism of action and the female reproductive system including time of ovum maturation and is intended to be conservative. For those MS disease modifying drugs (DMDs) which have information in the label, this time period is used as the peri-LMP period. For those MS DMDs with no information in the label, 5 times the half-life is used as the peri-LMP period. For those which provide a range of half-lives, the longer half-life is used.

The final column of the following table is the resultant length of the peri-LMP period to be used for this study.

Table 2 Length of the peri-LMP periods for contributed MS (DMD) medications

Traditional DMDs	ATC code	Administration technique	Half life	5 times half life	Defined peri-LMP period as per label (needed use of effective contraception since last dose)	Peri-LMP period (days) (Guidance to the DAP)
Alemtuzumab	L04AA34	Intravenous infusion	2 weeks	10 weeks	4 months	122
Cladribine	L01BB04	Oral	1 day	5 days	6 months	183
Daclizumab	L04AC01	Subcutaneous injection	21 days	105 days	No info in SmPC	105
Dimethyl fumarate	N07XX09	Oral	1 hour	5 hours	No info in SmPC	1 day
Fingolimod	L04AA27	Oral	6 – 9 days	30 – 45 days	2 months	61
Glatiramer acetate	L03AX13/ L04AA07	Subcutaneous injection/Self-injectable	1 hour	5 hours	No info in SmPC	1
Interferon beta-1a	L03AB07	Rebif: Subcutaneous injection	Rebif : 50 – 60 hours	Rebif : 250 – 300 hours (10,42 – 12.5 days)	Rebif / Avonex: None	13
Interferon beta-1a	L03AB07	Avonex: Intramuscular injection	Avonex : 10 hours	Avonex : 50 hours (2,08 days)	Rebif / Avonex: None	2
Interferon beta-1b	L03AB08	Subcutaneous injection	8 minutes to 4.3 hours	40 minutes – 21.5 hours	No info in SmPC	1
Mitoxantrone	L01DB07	Intravenous infusion	25 – 215 hours	125 – 1075 hours	No info in SmPC	45
Natalizumab	L04AA23	Intravenous infusion	27 days	135 days	No info in SmPC	135

Traditional DMDs	ATC code	Administration technique	Half life	5 times half life	Defined peri-LMP period as per label (needed use of effective contraception since last dose)	Peri-LMP period (days) (Guidance to the DAP)
Ocrelizumab	L04AA36	Intravenous infusion	26 days	130 days	12 months	365
Peginterferon beta-1a	L03AB13	Subcutaneous injection	78 hours	390 hours (16 days)	No info in SmPC	16
Teriflunomide	L04AA31	Oral	19 days	95 days	Between 8 months and 2 years (plasma conc below 0.02 mg/l)	730
Ofatumumab	L01XC10	Subcutaneous injection	17.6 days	88 days	6 months	183
Siponimod	L04AA42	Oral	30 hours	150 hours (6.25 days)	10 days	10
Methotrexate	L04AX03	Oral	7 hours	35 hours	6 months	183
Zeposia / Ozanimod	L04AA38	Oral	Ozanimod: 21 hours (active metabolite CC112273: 11 days)	105 hours (5 days) 55 days	3 months	92
Azathioprine	L04AX01	Oral	6 hours	30 hours	No info in SmPC	2
Rituximab	L01XC02	Intravenous infusion	22 days	110 days	12 months	365

9.2.3 Teratogenic drugs

Cases with exposures to teratogenic/fetotoxic drugs during the peri-LMP and during pregnancy will be excluded. Table 3 lists the teratogenic drugs and their peri-LMP period. The final column of the following table is the resultant length of the peri-LMP period to be used for this study. If the dates of exposure to a teratogenic drug of an individual case are missing, the case should be excluded.

Table 3. List of teratogens and their peri-LMP period: medications with an association with disruption of structural organ development or growth

Medication	ATC code	Administration technique	Half life	5 times half life	Define peri-LMP period as per label (needed use of effective contraception since last dose)	Peri-LMP period (days) (Guidance to the DAP)
Acitretin	D05BB02	Oral	50 hours (60 hours cis-acitretin) Etretinate 120 days	250 hours (300 hours cis-acitretin) Etretinate 600 days	3 years	1095
Alitretinoin	L01XF02/D11AH04	Oral	9 hours	45 hours	1 month	30
Bexarotene	L01XF03	Oral	1-3 hours	5-15 hours	1 month	30
Isotretinoin	D10AD04/D10BA01 / D10AD54	Oral	19 hours (29 hours 4-oxo-isotretinoin)	95 hours (145 hours 4-oxo-isotretinoin)	1 month	30
Tretinoin	D10AD01/L01XF01 / D10AD51	Oral	0.7 hours	3.5 hours	1 month	30
Carbamazepine	N03AF01	Oral	36 hours	180 hours	No info in SmPC	8
Phenytoin	N03AB02	Oral/intravenous injection	20-60 hours	100-300 hours	1 month	30
Fosphenytoin	N03AB05	Intravenous infusion/intramuscular injection	12 – 29 hours	60 – 145 hours	No info in SmPC	6
Primidone	N03AA03	Oral	15 hours	75 hours	No info in SmPC	3
Topiramate	N03AX11	Oral	21 hours	105 hours	No info in SmPC	4
Valproate	N03AG01	Oral	12-16 hours	60-80 hours	No info in SmPC	3
Phenobarbital	N03AA02	Oral/Intravenous injection	75-120 hours	375-600 hours	No info in SmPC	25
Carbimazole	H03BB01	Oral	3 hours	15 hours	No info in SmPC	1
Methimazole	H03BB02/H03BB52	Oral	2-8 hours	10-40 hours	No info in SmPC	2
Angiotensin Converting Enzyme inhibitors and	C09A/C09B/C09C/ C09D	Oral	NA	NA	NA 2nd and 3rd	

Angiotensin II Receptor Blockers						trimester exposure	
Dicoumarol	B01AA01	Oral	1-2 days	5-10 days	No info in SmPC	10	
Phenindione	B01AA02	Oral	5-6 hours	25-30 hours	No info in SmPC	1	
Warfarin	B01AA03	Oral	40 hours	200 hours	No info in SmPC	8	
Phenprocoumon	B01AA04	Oral	5-6 days	25-30 days	No info in SmPC	30	
Acenocoumarol	B01AA07	Oral	8-11 hours	40-55 hours	No info in SmPC	2	
Fluindione	B01AA12	Oral	69 hours	345 hours	No info in SmPC	14	
Misoprostol	A02BB01/G02AD06	Oral	20-40 minutes	100-200 minutes	No info in SmPC	1	
Diethylstilbestrol	G03CB02/G03CC05 /L02AA01	Oral	5-6 days	25-30 days	No info in SmPC	30	

9.3. Variables

Work Package 2 of the IMI ConcePTION project has defined (as Task 2.3) a set of CDEs. Clinical definitions and technical definitions were established for each CDE. The variables to be collected for each data source are those CDEs defined as ‘essential’ [ConcePTION Deliverable 2.3].

The essential CDEs are:

- individual case identifiers
- linked mother/baby case identifier
- primary reporter
- primary reporter details
- initial report date
- mother’s date of birth
- mother’s age at last menstrual period (LMP)
- date of LMP
- expected date of delivery (EDD)
- source of reported EDD
- date of end of pregnancy (EOP)
- prenatal tests
- prospective or retrospective data collection (prospective status/true prospective status)
- drug names
- drug start date
- drug stop date
- drug indication(s)
- peri-LMP exposure
- trimester 1,2,3 exposure

- total daily dose
- pregnancy outcome information
 - live-birth
 - stillbirth
 - induced termination
 - spontaneous abortion
 - ectopic pregnancy
 - molar pregnancy
 - blighted ovum
- gestational age at EOP
- gestational timing of live birth
- fetal outcome information
 - report of congenital anomaly/ies
 - classification and type of each reported congenital malformation
 - Genetic
 - Major
 - Minor
 - NOS (not otherwise specified)
 - fetal category
 - Genetic malformation case
 - Major malformation case
 - Minor malformation case
 - NOS (not otherwise specified) malformation case
 - other fetal problems
 - fetal growth restriction
 - neonatal complications
- infant birth weight
- infant sex
- infant head circumference
- small/large for gestational age at delivery
- post-natal death of live born infant
- age at death of neonate/infant / child
- maternal death
- maternal pre-pregnancy medical conditions
- maternal medical conditions arising in pregnancy
- plurality

9.4. Data sources

Data are provided by several DAPs. Pregnancy exposure reports in scope for this pilot study will be obtained from three types of data collection methods

- Pregnancy registries
- EFPIA enhanced pharmacovigilance (“PRIM”) programmes
- Data from selected ENTIS databases.

9.4.1 Pregnancy registries

Reports from selected prospective pregnancy exposure registries concerning MS drugs will provide data for this study:

- Gilenya pregnancy registry (Novartis)
- Siponimod pregnancy registry (Novartis)
- Teriflunomide pregnancy registries (Sanofi)
- The Dutch Pregnancy Drug Register (Lareb)
- Others might be added

9.4.1.1 Gilenya pregnancy registry (Novartis)

Gilenya pregnancy registry (Novartis): As of 28 Feb 2021, 297 women were enrolled (10 were excluded from analysis due to protocol deviations). 287 women were analysed in the most recent interim report. 196 prospective and 91 retrospective women.

The Gilenya Pregnancy Exposure Registry was launched in May 2011 to prospectively collect safety data on maternal, fetal and infant outcomes associated with fingolimod exposure during pregnancy and up to 8 weeks before the last menstrual period (LMP). At time of enrolment the patient needs to be pregnant, have a diagnosis of MS, was exposed during pregnancy or up to 8 weeks before LMP and signed an informed consent form. No exclusion criteria are applied. Cases are considered prospective if at the time of enrolment, no prenatal testing had been done and pregnancy outcome was not known. Cases are considered retrospective if prenatal tests had been performed at enrolment, while the patient is still pregnant, regardless of their results. The primary outcome measure is the prevalence of major congenital malformations, defined as any structural defects with recognized surgical, medical, or cosmetic importance as per the guidelines, while anomalies were qualified as minor if they were of no serious medical or cosmetic consequence to the child. Other outcome measures included miscarriages, elective abortions, stillbirths, neonatal deaths (counted in live births), and term and preterm live births with or without congenital malformations.

Congenital malformations are judged by external adjudicators (qualified paediatrician, clinical geneticist, teratologist, paediatric neurologist, nephrologist, toxicologist, or clinical pharmacologist), according to the EUROCAT or other guidelines. In cases of discrepancy, cases are classified as the more severe of the two adjudications.

9.4.1.2 Mayzent (siponimod) pregnancy registry (Novartis)

The Mayzent Pregnancy Registry will be conducted in collaboration with the Organization of Teratology Information Specialists (OTIS) in the US and Canada. This prospective pregnancy registry with three cohorts, namely siponimod exposed pregnant women versus 1) disease-matched pregnant women not exposed to siponimod, and 2) healthy pregnant women, will target to enrol 125 pregnancies in each of the three cohorts. The primary objective is to estimate and compare the prevalence of major structural defects in siponimod exposed pregnant women versus 1) disease-matched pregnant women not exposed to siponimod, and 2) healthy pregnant women.

Secondary objectives are to estimate and compare the prevalence of selected adverse pregnancy and infant outcomes in siponimod-exposed pregnant women versus 1) disease-matched pregnant women not exposed to siponimod, and 2) healthy pregnant women. The primary outcome of the study is major structural defects.

The secondary outcomes of the study are:

- Spontaneous abortion
- Stillbirth
- Elective termination

- Preterm delivery
- Preeclampsia / eclampsia
- Small for gestational age infants
- Small for age for postnatal growth to one year of age
- A pattern of minor structural defects
- Developmental performance at approximately one year of age
- Serious or opportunistic infections in the first year of life.

9.4.1.3 Teriflunomide pregnancy registries (Sanofi)

Teriflunomide Pregnancy Outcome Exposure Registry: An Organization of Teratology Information Specialists (OTIS) Autoimmune Diseases in Pregnancy Project.

This is a prospective, observational cohort study of pregnancy outcomes in women with MS who are exposed to teriflunomide during pregnancy. The objective is to evaluate any potential increase in the risk of major birth defects, in the first year of life, in teriflunomide-exposed pregnancies. The outcomes will be compared to those observed in two comparison groups: one in women with MS who have not been exposed to teriflunomide during pregnancy, and the other in women without MS. The secondary objective is to evaluate the potential effect of teriflunomide-exposure on other adverse pregnancy outcomes including any potential pattern of minor birth defects, spontaneous abortion, stillbirth, preterm delivery, small for gestational age at birth and at 1-year follow-up.

The treatment cohort (exposed group, Cohort I) includes pregnant women with a confirmed diagnosis of MS and teriflunomide exposure during pregnancy for any number of days, at any dose, and at any time from the 1st day of the last menstrual period (LMP) up to and including the 12th week after the first day of the LMP. The study excluded pregnant women with exposures commencing after the 12th week post-LMP; who had prenatal diagnosis of a major structural defect in the current pregnancy; who first come in contact with the project after 20 completed weeks' gestation; and who had previously enrolled in the study for a previous pregnancy (only 1 pregnancy per woman, may be registered).

One comparison cohort (Cohort II) will consist of pregnant women with MS not exposed to teriflunomide during the current pregnancy. Pregnant women who had previously been treated with teriflunomide if they had received any dose of the drug within 2 years prior to the index pregnancy and do not have documented blood levels below 0.02 mcg/mL prior to pregnancy were excluded. This group can be taking any other approved disease modifying therapy for MS.

The other comparison group (Cohort III) will consist of pregnant women who do not have a known diagnosis of MS and have no known exposure to a known human teratogen.

Retrospectively reported cases were excluded from all cohorts.

As of Jan 2021, the registry enrolled a total of 159 pregnant women (10 in cohort I, 101 in cohort II, and 48 in cohort III).

An International Pregnancy Exposure registry of Women with Multiple Sclerosis (MS) exposed to Teriflunomide

This is a voluntary, international, prospective, observational, non-interventional, exposure registry aiming to monitor pregnancies among women with MS who have been inadvertently exposed to teriflunomide during pregnancy to evaluate the risk of birth defects in their infants and fetuses. In addition, the registry will evaluate the potential impact of prenatal teriflunomide exposure on pregnancy and infant health, growth, and development. The objective of this registry is to compare the rate of birth defects with the birth defect rate of the European Surveillance of Congenital Anomalies (EUROCAT) network and with the birth defect rate of the Metropolitan Atlanta Congenital Defects Program (MACDP). The other objective of the study is to estimate the proportions of pregnancy outcomes including live born infants, recognized spontaneous abortions occurring at less than 20 gestation weeks, fetal deaths occurring at 20 gestation weeks or later, induced abortions without reported evidence of birth defects, TOPFA, ectopic pregnancy, molar pregnancy, pre-term live births (<37 gestation weeks), alterations in fetal/infant growth, indications of delayed development, and functional deficits observed during the first year of life in live born infants of women who received any dose of teriflunomide during pregnancy.

The registry will prospectively enrol pregnant women with MS who have been exposed to teriflunomide by taking any dose during pregnancy (defined as any time after the first day of the LMP) or prior to pregnancy start with documented plasma teriflunomide concentration greater than or equal to 0.02mg/L measured during pregnancy. Women who were participating in any clinical trial investigating teriflunomide at the time of pregnancy exposure are excluded. Data for study endpoint assessments will be recorded at four time points: 1) at the time of enrolment (i.e., registration), 2) approximately mid-pregnancy, 3) at the completion of pregnancy, and 4) at approximately one year of age for infants. The following countries are participating: Australia, Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Netherlands, Norway, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom.

As of Feb 2021, 37 pregnant women exposed to teriflunomide have been enrolled.

9.4.1.4 The Dutch Pregnancy Drug Register (Lareb)

The Dutch Pregnancy Drug Register (previously pREGnant register, in Dutch 'Moeders van Morgen') has been set up to obtain insight into medication use among pregnant and breastfeeding women and into the potential effects on maternal and fetal health. It was launched on April 1st, 2014. Data is collected through six web-based questionnaires filled in by participating women. The data comprise current pregnancy, obstetric history, maternal lifestyle, health and medication use, delivery and infant health. The first questionnaire is sent as early in pregnancy as possible, followed by a second questionnaire in gestational week 17 (unless enrolment was after week 20, then the second questionnaire is skipped). Questionnaires 3 through 6 are respectively sent in gestational week 34, and 8, 26 and 52 weeks after the expected date of birth. All pregnant women of 18 years and older, who are proficient in the Dutch language and have access to internet are eligible for inclusion. All data are collected prospectively, although women can enrol at any time throughout the entire pregnancy (8). As of 20

May 2021, 6563 women were enrolled. Data will be used to populate the predefined table shells only if a sufficient amount of MS cases exposed to the study drugs is available.

9.4.2 EFPIA enhanced pharmacovigilance (PRIM) programmes

Reports from EFPIA enhanced pharmacovigilance (PRIM) programmes concerning MS drugs will provide data for this study:

- Gilenya PRIM enhanced pharmacovigilance programme (Novartis)
- Siponimod and ofatumumab PRIM enhanced pharmacovigilance programme – if sufficient pregnancy cases are reported (Novartis).
- Worldwide pregnancy enhanced pharmacovigilance programme of oral cladribine (Merck)

9.4.2.1 Gilenya PRIM enhanced pharmacovigilance program (Novartis)

PRIM is defined as enhanced pharmacovigilance data collection and processing via sets of targeted checklists, structured follow-up, rigorous process of data entry and data quality control, and programmed aggregate analysis. This enhancement was initiated on 01 March 2014 for fingolimod to access data from pregnancies prospectively reported to the Argus safety database in patients who were not enrolled in the Gilenya Pregnancy Registry. To reduce bias in these estimates, the process focuses on prospectively-reported pregnancies. PRIM uses the EMA definition of prospective pregnancy cases: pregnancy outcome has not occurred and prenatal tests have not been performed at time of reporting or the result of the tests was not yet known or normal. PRIM was established as an end-to-end process including determining crucial outcomes of interest, definition of terms, data collection and follow-up, data processing and analysis. Data is being collected at Baseline (time of reporting), expected delivery date +1 month, expected delivery date+ 3months and expected delivery date + 12 months. The primary pregnancy outcome of interest is the occurrence of major congenital malformations in the offspring. In addition, pregnancy outcomes such as live birth, spontaneous abortion, stillbirth, elective termination, and ectopic pregnancy are being collected. Cases of minor malformation and data on infant adverse events (AE) such as infections and developmental milestones at three months and one year of age are being collected. As of end of February 2021 approximately 1350 fetus cases of maternal exposure during pregnancy have been prospectively reported to the Gilenya PRIM.

9.4.2.2 Siponimod and ofatumumab PRIM enhanced pharmacovigilance program (Novartis)

The PRIM studies for siponimod and ofatumumab are similar to the Gilenya PRIM program. The primary objective for both of these PRIM studies is to estimate the proportion of major congenital malformations associated with exposure to siponimod respectively ofatumumab immediately before and during pregnancy among live births and live births, stillbirths and termination of pregnancy for fetal anomaly (TOPFA). The secondary objectives include the estimation of the proportion of minor congenital malformations, pregnancy outcomes including live birth, stillbirths, spontaneous abortions and elective terminations and infant outcomes including infections up to 1

year of age. Pregnancy cases prospectively reported to Novartis (i.e. reported before pregnancy outcome has occurred) via spontaneous post-marketing report sources, post-marketing observational studies and patient-oriented programs, and reports from the Novartis clinical trials program are eligible for inclusion in PRIM analysis and results' summary. Retrospective cases, although followed up in a similar manner to the prospective cases, will be analysed and reported separately due to the associated reporting bias. Each study will run for a maximum of 10 years or achieve a sample size of 500 live births, whichever occurs first.

Data will be used only if sufficient pregnancy cases are reported.

9.4.2.3 Worldwide pregnancy surveillance program of oral cladribine (Merck Healthcare KGaA)

This surveillance program is based on analysis of worldwide data of exposure to oral cladribine during pregnancy or within 6 months before conception, captured in the Sponsor safety database GlobalLifeSphere MultiVigilance (LSSMV), for a 14-year period (2017-2031). Data is collected from individual case safety reports (ICSR) reported to safety data base LSSMV from: 1) spontaneous reports; 2) solicited reports, e.g., from patient support programs, clinical studies and observational studies.

All reports of exposed pregnancies are considered for inclusion, both in oral cladribine exposed pregnancies in women with MS, and in pregnancies fathered by men with MS exposed to oral cladribine. Pregnancies occurring during the following exposure window of susceptibility are included: 1) pregnancies of women with MS, occurring during oral cladribine treatment or within 6 months after last dose of oral cladribine; 2) pregnancies fathered by men with MS with exposure to oral cladribine within 6 months before conception. Data is collected on pregnancies and their outcomes. Pregnancies are followed until the outcome of the pregnancy is known i.e., spontaneous abortion, elective termination, stillbirth or live birth (with or without anomaly) or loss to follow-up, whichever occurs first. In cases of delivery of a baby with anomaly (such as congenital anomaly or other serious condition present in the baby at time of delivery), the case is followed up either to one year after birth or until loss to follow-up, whichever occurs first.

Adjudication of congenital anomalies is performed through medical review of narratives by an appropriate specialist.

A targeted questionnaire to obtain follow-up information on all pregnancies is used.

As of 30 June 2020, 61 reports of pregnancies in women with MS occurring during oral cladribine treatment or within 6 months after last dose of oral cladribine have been received into the LSSMV.

9.4.3 ENTIS data (pooled data held at STIS)

Four Teratology Information Services (TIS) from the UK, Switzerland, and Israel will provide data for this study with the following preliminary estimation of pregnancies exposed to MS medications:

- UK TIS: 45
- STIS: 35
- TIS Zerifin: 30
- Jerusalem TIS: 187

Data will be pooled from participating ENTIS centres to form one single ENTIS dataset for use in this pilot study. Pre-processing of ENTIS data will start at each ENTIS centre, which will create a dataset in a form as close as possible to that of the CDE.

It is assumed that ENTIS centres will be unable to perform a program-coded extraction of their data to a CDE structure. This extraction will have to be done manually for many data fields, issues being data cleaning. Also, although there are some CDE items which may be available directly in the ENTIS dataset, for many other CDE items information from several different ENTIS dataset variables need to be combined.

Each ENTIS centre will enter its resulting dataset into a pooled data repository based on the CDE and created using RedCap stream-lined process, a secure web application for building and managing online surveys and databases (<http://projectredcap.org/>). Identification of duplicates will be performed using a combination of details (such as country of report, exposure year, maternal age, medication, dosage, duration of exposure, duration of pregnancy, pregnancy outcome, details on abnormalities). Duplicates will be excluded. The pooled dataset will be held at STIS, which will be considered the DAP for the entire pooled ENTIS data.

Each ENTIS centre will summarise its ability to map its data to the CDE format in a similar way to that described at "Assessment of analysis datasets created by DAPs". This information will be summarised by STIS for the complete pooled ENTIS dataset.

The following ENTIS data are in scope of the study:

Prospective and retrospective cases of exposure to alemtuzumab (ATC index L04AA34), azathioprine (L04AX01), cladribine (L04AA40), daclizumab (L04AC01), dimethylfumarate (N07XX09), fingolimod (L04AA27), glatiramer (L04AA07), glatiramer acetate (L03AX13), interferon beta-1a (L03AB07), interferon beta-1b (L03AB08), methotrexate (L01BA01), mitoxantrone (L01DB07), natalizumab (L04AA23), ocrelizumab (L04AA36), ofatumumab (L01XC10), ozanimod (L04AA38), peginterferon beta-1a (L03AB13), rituximab (L01XC02), siponimod (L04AA42) and teriflunomide (L04AA31) used for the treatment of MS during the peri-LMP period (Table 2) or at any time during pregnancy.

The individual contributing ENTIS data sources are discussed further in the following sections.

9.4.3.1 UKTIS

The UKTIS (United Kingdom) prospective dataset consists of exposed pregnancies that have been reported by a general practitioner (family doctor), general practice nurse or pharmacist, community midwife, hospital-based midwife, obstetrician or other secondary care medical specialist (physician or pharmacist), or a medicines information pharmacist. Follow-up pregnancy outcome information is collected via postal

questionnaire, which is sent to the initial enquiring healthcare professional, shortly following the expected date of delivery that was reported at first contact. Outcomes not provided back to the service by 24 weeks after the estimated date of delivery are considered lost to follow-up.

9.4.3.2 STIS

The STIS (Switzerland) dataset consists of exposed pregnancies that have been reported by a healthcare professional. Follow-up pregnancy outcome information is collected via postal questionnaire, which is sent to the initial enquiring healthcare professional at first contact and shortly following the expected date of delivery. Information reported at first contact can be confirmed when providing pregnancy outcome information. In case of non-response, one reminder is sent systematically. Outcomes not provided back to the service 18 months after the estimated date of delivery are considered lost to follow-up.

9.4.3.3 TIS Zerifin

The TIS Zerifin (Israel) dataset consists of exposed pregnancies that have been reported by healthcare professionals and general public. Follow-up pregnancy outcome information is collected from general public via phone follow-up structured questionnaire. Information reported at first contact can be confirmed when providing pregnancy outcome information. Time of follow-up varies according to the aim of the study – there are periods when follow-ups were performed routinely, recently we perform follow-ups per study (depends on staff availability).

9.4.3.4 Jerusalem TIS

Jerusalem TIS dataset consists of exposed pregnancies that have been reported by pregnant women and health care professionals who spontaneously contact the service for consultation in pregnancy. After the expected date of delivery pregnancy outcome is actively sought. Follow-up is conducted by a telephone interview with the initial contact person. In most cases the follow-ups are carried out within the first 2-3 years of life.

9.5. Study size

This pilot study will analyse data on pregnancies complying with the inclusion and exclusion criteria from each data access provider.

Each DAP will summarise its ability to map its data to the CDE format using the methodology described at "Assessment of analysis datasets created by DAPs", irrespective of sample size.

Each DAP will be required to populate the pre-defined summary tables according to the guidance in the Statistical Analysis Plan if they can provide data on ≥ 10 cases with known pregnancy outcomes.

9.6. Data management

9.6.1 Construction of the analysis dataset by DAPs

To enable population of the pre-defined summary tables, each DAP will have to set up an analysis dataset, which (in terms of clinical definitions and technical definitions) contains elements adhering as closely as possible to the guidance in the document: “WP2 CDE”. To do this, each DAP will need to consider how best to process raw data from its safety database to construct its analysis dataset. For each CDE item, the following may need to be considered:

- Necessary adjustments to definitions usually used by the DAP
- Intermediate calculation steps
- Data cleaning/correction
- Recoding to CDE standards and harmonisation of variable / element structure
- Combination of raw data fields to construct certain CDE items
 - If, for a particular CDE item, there is no data field in the DAP’s database that corresponds directly to a required CDE item, then data reported in other raw data fields may have to be combined in order to construct that CDE item (e.g., date of LMP might have to be constructed from EDD minus 280 days).
 - Even if there is a data field in the DAP’s database that corresponds directly to a required CDE, data on that item might be missing for some pregnancy reports. In these cases, such combinations of raw data may differ from case to case (e.g., if LMP is routinely collected but missing for an individual case, then, only for that case would it be necessary to construct date of LMP from EDD minus 280 days).

DAPs are invited to contact the authors of this protocol to discuss any issues arising during this process.

9.6.2 Assessment of adherence of DAPs to the CDE guidance

Information provided by each DAP regarding unresolved gaps in alignment of data elements to CDE standards or other significant limitations is useful in the review of the analysis results and in making recommendations for future processes. Therefore, each DAP is requested to provide detailed information about their analysis dataset. The requested information is given in the Statistical Analysis Plan.

DAPs are invited to contact the authors of this protocol to discuss any issues arising during this process.

9.7. Data analysis

9.7.1 Data analysis by each DAP

Each DAP will be required to populate the pre-defined summary tables according to the guidance in the Statistical Analysis Plan developed. Summary tables include the following information:

- Tabulated summary (number and %) of pregnancy cases reported, pending, lost to follow up, and those with known pregnancy outcome
- Tabulated summary (number and %) of maternal characteristics and risk factors for those with known pregnancy outcomes
- Tabulated summary (number and %) of known pregnancy outcomes (pregnancy and fetal outcome including congenital malformation) by timing of exposure

Final, populated summary tables will be supplied by each participating DAP and included in a combined analysis report.

9.7.2 Comparison of analyses from each DAP and other sources

Drafts of the populated tables will be reviewed by the 2.5.2 project team. Requests for further refinement might be made to each DAP. For example, splitting the tables by sub-groups may be requested to allow results to be compared either with those from different DAPs or with corresponding data from population datasets.

Final versions of populated tables will be discussed and informal comparisons made between the analyses of datasets provided by each DAP. No formal meta-analysis will be attempted although recommendations for this may emerge.

9.7.3 Review of DAP's summary of its dataset construction

The ability of each DAP (and the processes used) to create a set of data elements aligned with the guidance in the CDE will be discussed based on the information supplied by each DAP.

9.8. Quality control

Adequate quality control measures are the responsibility of each DAP.

9.9. Limitations of the research methods

The aim of this demonstration project is to identify some of the current limitations of primary data collection programmes / studies / registries and propose improvements to such data collection systems.

This is a pilot study focusing on medications used for one indication only. Hence, the generalizability of the results may be limited.

For product specific pregnancy registries and PRIM programmes only those from participating EFPIA partners are available for this demonstration projects. Some of the

currently ongoing pregnancy registries and PRIM programmes will have a limited sample size at the time of analysis. To our knowledge the availability of disease pregnancy registries is limited.

The limitations for the ENTIS dataset include different information sources for outcome data (healthcare professionals and patients), the variations in timing of follow-up, missing data, the small sample size.

10. Protection of human subjects

The protection of human subjects is dependent on national regulations. Each participating DAP and each TIS contributing to the ENTIS DAP is individually responsible for ensuring that the provision of information to this study is undertaken in accordance with local data protection and ethical approval agreements.

11. Management and reporting of adverse events/adverse reactions

This study is non-interventional, based on secondary use of data. Therefore, the reporting of suspected adverse reactions in the form of individual case safety reports (ICSRs) is not required.

Aggregated results of adverse events/adverse reactions will be summarized in the study report, i.e. the overall association between an exposure and an outcome will be presented.

EFPIA partners contributing data to this study should include relevant findings from the study report in periodic aggregated regulatory reports (PSURs) submitted to Health Authorities.

12. Plans for disseminating and communicating study results

Results of this study will be used in the ConcePTION project and reported to IMI. Findings of general pharmacovigilance interest will be published in a peer reviewed scientific journal if possible. Authorship in scientific publication will have to satisfy the conditions of the Uniform Requirements for Manuscripts Submitted to Biomedical Journals (www.icmje.org/icmje-recommendations.pdf). Approval of submitted reports and scientific publications will be required by all collaborators.

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Demonstration study 2.5.3

Long-term investigation following exposure to individual medicines
in utero: The LIFETIME system

PASS information

Title	Long-term investigation following exposure to individual medicines in utero: The LIFETIME system
Protocol version identifier	Version 1
Date of last version of protocol	30.08.2021
EU PAS register number	
Active substance	ATC codes including, but not limited to N03.
Medicinal product	See Active Substances
Product reference	Not applicable
Procedure number	Not applicable
Joint PASS	Not applicable
Research question and objectives	Is routine surveillance for longer-term health and child neurodevelopment feasible, valid and accepted within already established pregnancy pharmacovigilance surveillance systems?
EFPIA partners	Novartis
Academic partners /ENTIS centres	UMAN, UZKN, UKTIS, UNEW, LAREB, UK and Ireland Epilepsy and Pregnancy Register, MHRA, UU.
Authors	<p>Rebecca Bromley, University of Manchester and Royal Manchester Children's Hospital</p> <p>Laura Yates, University of KwaZulu-Natal</p> <p>Victoria Simms, University of Ulster</p> <p>Matthew Bluett-Duncan, University of Manchester</p> <p>Dave Lewis, Novartis</p> <p>Amalia Alexe, Novartis</p> <p>Saskia Vorstenbosch, LAREB</p> <p>Luke Richardson, UKTIS</p> <p>Alison Oliver, UKTIS</p> <p>Sarah Mee, MHRA</p> <p>Phil Tregunno, MHRA</p> <p>Kendal Harrison, MHRA</p> <p>Krishna Bodapati Menon, Novartis</p>

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1. List of abbreviations and definitions

List of abbreviations

- ADHD Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder
- ASD Autistic Spectrum Disorders
- ASQ-3 Ages and Stages Questionnaire – 3rd Edition
- EFPIA European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations
- FVSD Fetal Valproate Spectrum Disorder
- IMI Innovative Medicines Initiative
- NaME Neurodevelopment of Babies Born to Mothers with Epilepsy
- MHRA Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency
- PASS Post Authorisation Safety Studies
- SPSS Statistical Package for the Social Sciences
- UMAN University of Manchester
- UK & I EPR UK and Ireland Epilepsy Pregnancy Register
- UKTIS UK Teratology Information Service
- UZKN University of KwaZulu-Natal
- WEB-RADR Web-Recognising Adverse Drug Reactions
- WP Work Package

List of definitions

- *Collaborating Group*: These are groups who undertake pregnancy pharmacovigilance studies pertaining to congenital anomaly data, who opt in to develop and pilot the LIFETIME System. Collaborating Groups may be disease or medication specific pregnancy registers or teratology information services.
- *Congenital anomaly*: Morphological, functional and/or biochemical developmental disturbance in the embryo or fetus whether detected at birth or not.
- *Fetus*: This term is used here with the broad definition of the term fetus, referring to the entire prenatal development from the conception until the birth.
- *Neurodevelopment*: The brain's development over time and its observable functions (e.g., milestone attainment, intellectual functioning, reading ability, social skills, memory, attention or focus skills).
- *Pharmacovigilance*: Science and activities relating to the detection, assessment, understanding and prevention of adverse effects or any other medicine-related problem.
- *Registry*: An organised system that uses observational methods to collect uniform data on specified outcomes in a population defined by a particular disease, condition or exposure.
- *Risk-benefit balance*: An evaluation of the positive therapeutic effects of the medicinal product in relation to the risks.
- *Signal*: Information arising from early investigations which suggests a potentially causal association between an exposure and an adverse event or set of outcomes.
- *Study Group*: The primary ConcePTION work package 2, demonstration 3 group.
- *Teratogens*: Environmental factors which can cause congenital abnormalities.

2. Responsible parties

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UK & Ireland Epilepsy Pregnancy Register

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3. Abstract

There is limited collection of data regarding longer-term child health and neurodevelopment following exposure in the womb to medications. This is despite the clear examples of deleterious impact of maternal medications on child health and development. The adaptation of already established pregnancy pharmacovigilance surveillance methods such as pregnancy registers or teratology information services, offers a route through which routine child health and neurodevelopmental screening could occur.

As part of the ConcePTION Study the LIFETIME System will be designed and piloted for feasibility, validity and acceptability. It will aim to be a cost-effective program, utilising parent reporting methods, which will allow for the standardised collection of longer-term child health and neurodevelopmental outcome data across different pregnancy pharmacovigilance surveillance sources (Collaborating Groups). Pregnancy and immediate birth outcomes recorded prospectively through the Collaborating Group's local procedures will be augmented with the LIFETIME follow up system, extending follow up from 6 months of age to 7 years of age. To be able to facilitate a more rapid accumulation of data, particularly for medications with a lower frequency of use, the feasibility of aligning and combining data from different Collaborating Groups using the LIFETIME System will be piloted.

If found to be feasible, valid and acceptable the LIFETIME System can be implemented into other pregnancy pharmacovigilance surveillance schemes throughout Europe to enable or enhance the collection of child health and neurodevelopmental screening data on a routine basis.

4. Amendments and updates

Number	Date	Section of study protocol	Amendment or update	Reason
1				
2				

5. Milestones

Milestone	Planned date
Application for required ethics Start of data collection	Study Month: 3 ConcePTION Month: 31
Start of data collection	Study Month: 5 ConcePTION Month: 33
Progress report(s)/ Interim report(s)	
Stage 1: Internal report of the requirements of the Collaborating Groups.	Study Month: 1 ConcePTION Month: 29
Stage 2: LIFETIME design and questionnaire selection complete	Study Month: 2 ConcePTION Month: 31
Stage 3: Completion of the questionnaire pilot	Study Month: 6 ConcePTION Month: 34
Stage 4: Pilot data collection using the primary age questionnaire set in an already established cohort results	Study Month: 17 ConcePTION Month: 44
Stage 5: Results from the pilot of the prospective data collection using Lifetime	Study Month: 7 ConcePTION Month: 35
Stage 6: Results from the feasibility study regarding the combining of LIFETIME data collected from different groups	Study Month: 27 ConcePTION Month: 55
Registration in the EU PAS Register®	Study Month: 1 ConcePTION Month: 31
Final report of study results (all stages)	Study Month: 28 ConcePTION Month: 56

6. Rationale and background

Certain medications are associated with increased risks of both congenital anomalies and impact on fetal brain development [1]. However, the use of medication during pregnancy is often necessary for women with both chronic and acute conditions [2, 3] and the time taken to gather adequate data on risk or safety is too long [4]. While there are several established approaches to routine data collection for congenital anomalies, including disease and medication pregnancy registers, teratology information service cohorts and others [5, 6], there is currently a lack of routine surveillance for the impact an exposure may have on the developing fetal brain and associated long-term outcomes.

The medications sodium valproate and isotretinoin are two examples whereby a medication exposure can be associated with a deleterious impact on the developing brain [7-9]. These two medications, one an antiseizure medication and the other an oral retinoid for severe dermatological indications, highlight the high risk to the developing fetal brain which can be conveyed by diverse medication classes. Both medications are associated with increased rates of poorer early infant development and later an increased risk of intellectual disability [9, 10], but each has a characteristic and distinct pattern of cognitive deficits. For both medications there is a dose dependent association, with higher doses leading to increased risks of impairment [9, 11] and an association with physical symptoms of the exposure such as characteristic congenital anomalies and facial dysmorphism [7, 9]. However, despite these clear detrimental effects, little is known regarding the risk (or lack thereof) posed to the developing brain by the majority of medications commonly prescribed to women of child-bearing potential, including some for which structural effects have been identified.

Both health outcomes and neurodevelopmental deficits present a substantial cost to the individual, their family and to society through increased requirements for health and educational interventions and support. Given the severity of the

associated impact on the development and functioning of the child's body and brain, an expedited system of routine surveillance for child health and neurodevelopmental outcomes is required. This system must enable rapid collection and evaluation of safety data across large populations, but with high sensitivity to identify moderate to severe child neurodevelopmental and health difficulties.

Neurodevelopment is a term which covers a diverse range of brain functions including intellectual abilities, language, attention, executive functions and other cognitive abilities, as well as motor development and social skills. The development of the brain is a protracted process which begins *in utero* but continues to unfold and be influenced through the postnatal years. A child's health status is also dynamic and given this extended period of development, the complex functioning of the organs are not be fully evident at birth. The breadth of diversity and the elongated developmental phase of child health and neurodevelopmental outcomes may make them appear more nebulous than their structural anomaly equivalents. However, if considered as a set of interrelated but independent outcomes, measured by a standardised assessment and within the correct age range, the individual areas of child health and neurodevelopment can be clearly defined, objectively measured and effectively reported on.

A recently convened expert consensus group regarding the investigation of child outcomes following exposure to medications in utero highlighted the importance of longitudinal follow up studies utilising direct assessment of the child by a blinded trained assessor[12]. However, such methodological approaches are costly both in terms of time and finance and therefore have not, and are unlikely to become, fully embedded into routine surveillance systems. An alternative approach is to model what is currently undertaken in many national child health and developmental services. Parent completed standardised and validated questionnaires are used to act as a way of identifying children at risk of poorer health and developmental outcomes and who require more comprehensive, specialist assessments. Thus, there is the opportunity to investigate whether parent completed questionnaire data is a feasible option to allow for an adequate

system of routine surveillance for child health and neurodevelopment following exposure in the womb to a medication. It is not proposed that such studies replace gold standard longitudinal studies with blinded assessments by trained personnel, but that such a system is used to screen for signals of altered child health and neurodevelopment following exposure to medicinal products. Such early warning signals should then lead to intensive gold-standard investigation from which conclusions can be drawn and regulatory decisions made.

The Innovative Medicine Initiative (IMI) funded ConcePTION project aims to enhance the way medication use during pregnancy is studied [13] in order to provide clearer, more comprehensive data to a more appropriate timescale. This demonstration project will contribute to this aim through the investigation of feasibility of a system which would allow for cost effective, routine screening level investigation into the health and neurodevelopmental outcomes of children exposed to medications in utero. This will form the basis of a wider system of routine screening and comprehensive assessment of longer-term child health and neurodevelopmental outcomes.

7. Research question and objectives

The primary research question: Is a routine surveillance system for longer-term health and child neurodevelopment feasible, valid and acceptable for implementation within already established pregnancy pharmacovigilance surveillance systems?

The secondary research question: Is it feasible to combine data from multiple Collaborating Groups for analysis?

This study has the following objectives:

1. To identify what adaptations are required within already established pregnancy pharmacovigilance systems to extend data collection to include child health and neurodevelopmental outcomes.
2. To design a standardised and sustainable system ('LIFETIME System'), including data collection tools and technology infrastructure, that is

capable of collecting longer-term child health and neurodevelopmental outcome data within already established pregnancy pharmacovigilance surveillance programs.

3. To investigate the validity of the chosen questionnaires for the LIFETIME System to detect the health and neurodevelopmental difficulties associated with in utero exposure to sodium valproate.
4. To test the feasibility and acceptability of the LIFETIME Questionnaire Set, in already established research cohorts.
5. To pilot prospectively the LIFETIME System in established pregnancy pharmacovigilance surveillance programs such as disease specific pregnancy registers and teratology information services.
6. To develop the agreements, data flows and infrastructure required to combine data from different Collaborating Groups and to test the feasibility of data combining.

9. Timelines

This demonstration project will run from September 2021 (month 31 of the IMI ConcePTION Study) until September 2023 (month 54 of the IMI ConcePTION Study). Figure 1 displays the timelines for each of the six stages of the project.

10. Research Design

This project is one of design and feasibility testing. Initially this project will focus on the development of the LIFETIME System: a set of questionnaires which will be the primary source of standardised data collection and the development of infrastructure to collect the data. Following this, three observational studies will be completed which will investigate validity and feasibility of the proposed system through the collection of primary data.

There are 6 stages to this investigation which will first develop and then feasibility test the new LIFETIME System. Table 1 provides a brief summary of each of the stage.

Figure 1. Demonstration project 3 timelines.

* Early work on this stage is required to establish procedures for recruitment during pregnancy with the collaborating groups.

Table 1. Summary of the objectives for each stage of the project

	Objective	Stage		
Stage 1.	To identify what adaptations are required within already established pregnancy pharmacovigilance systems to extend data collection to include child health and neurodevelopmental outcomes.	Development		
Stage 2.	To design a standardised and sustainable system (LIFETIME System) including data collection tools and technological infrastructure, that is capable of collecting longer-term child health and neurodevelopmental outcome data within already established pregnancy pharmacovigilance programs.			
Stage 3.	To investigate the validity of the chosen questionnaires for the LIFETIME System to detect the health and neurodevelopmental difficulties associated with <i>in utero</i> exposure to sodium valproate		Validity testing	
Stage 4.	To test the feasibility and acceptability of the LIFETIME Questionnaire Set <u>in an already</u> established research cohort.			
Stage 5.	To pilot prospectively the LIFETIME System in established pregnancy pharmacovigilance surveillance programs such as disease specific pregnancy registers and teratology information services.		Feasibility Testing	
Stage 6.	To develop the agreements, data flows and infrastructure required to combine data from different Collaborating Groups and to test the feasibility of data combining.			

10.1. Stage 1: Identification of adaptations required within pregnancy pharmacovigilance surveillance systems to extend to longer term follow up.

Objective: To identify what adaptations are required within already established pregnancy pharmacovigilance systems to extend data collection to include child health and neurodevelopmental outcomes.

Months: 1-2.

The needs of potential end users of the LIFETIME System will be identified through a series of meetings and feedback sessions with possible collaborating Groups who have indicated an interest in piloting the LIFETIME System.

Information will be sought from primary pregnancy pharmacovigilance data collection schemes such as teratology information services and pregnancy registers as to current practices, data collection methods and likely barriers to extending their follow up periods and scope. A mapping exercise to identify common areas of need or challenges will be undertaken with the required adaptations identified and solutions identified. For example, in the preparation for this demonstration project, preliminary discussions with potential Collaborating Groups have identified that alterations to research approvals would be required. As part of this stage standard documentation will be produced for Collaborating Groups which would require personalisation for their specific data collection method and translations (where required).

Output(s) for Stage 1: An internal demonstration project report will be drafted documenting the technical, expertise, legal and ethical requirements of the different pregnancy pharmacovigilance surveillance systems to be considered in the design of the system. Additionally, a series of user guidance documents and information sheets will be prepared following these consultations to enable the participating Collaborating Groups to apply integrate the LIFETIME System into their already running data collection schemes.

10.2. Stage 2: The development of a system of longer-term child health and neurodevelopmental surveillance.

Objective: To design a standardised and sustainable system (LIFETIME System), including data collection tools and technology infrastructure, that is capable of collecting longer-term child health and neurodevelopmental outcome data within already established pregnancy pharmacovigilance surveillance programs.

Months: 1-3.

Identified through work already conducted in ConcePTION Study Task 2.3 and through preparatory work for this protocol, Collaborating Groups will require a flexible system which relies on limited financial and staff time commitments. Therefore, an approach which utilises a Collaborating Group's already collected pregnancy, maternal health and medication data but extends the period of follow up using a standardised system of parental completed questionnaires to ascertain the child's health and neurodevelopmental information will be designed and tested. Once developed and validated the ConcePTION LIFETIME System will also be suitable for use as a complete data collection system for new users.

There is a clear rationale for starting surveillance early in the child's life and with high frequency into the preschool years[12]. A framework for the proposed LIFETIME System has been developed as part of ConcePTION Study WP2, Task 2.3 and includes repeated contact with the parent early in the child's development. For this ConcePTION Study demonstration project, we would look to extend child follow up to seven years of age. Ideally the LIFETIME System follow up would run beyond the primary school years and into the second decade of life, but this is beyond the scope of the current project and is an area identified for future development.

Infant Questionnaire Set Choice (6 months – 4 years)

In order to obtain data from parents a cost-effective set of questionnaires will be selected as part of the development of this system. A mixture of standardised and adapted screening measures will be chosen based on availability, feasibility and

evidence of sensitivity. As part of the preparatory work for this protocol, through literature searches, author experience and alignment with other data collectors (e.g. US Organisation of Teratology Information Services [14]) there was a clear rationale for the utilisation of the Ages and Stages (ASQ-3) [15] questionnaire to be used for infant to early childhood follow up. The ASQ-3 is a caregiver-report that helps determine whether a child's development is on track or identifies children at risk for developmental delay. The ASQ-3 has been translated into a wide range of languages and has been shown to be feasible, as well as being sensitive to delays in development induced by teratogens [16, 17]. The ASQ-3 would provide information on the child's development in the following critical areas: Communication, Gross Motor, Fine Motor, Problem Solving, Personal and Social development. The use of the ASQ-3 will be utilized for the first four data collection time points (6 months, 12 months, 24 months, 4 years) along with questions about the child's health. As part of the development of this protocol discussions with the ASQ-3 publishers have been held about a license which will allow for the delivery of the ASQ-3 in a variety of formats (e.g., electronic or paper based, smartphone app).

Primary Age Questionnaire Set Development

At older ages development is more complex and multi-faceted, a broader set of measures are required. Given the financial and time restraints indicated by Collaborating Groups, large and expensive questionnaire sets are not feasible, if the LIFETIME System is to be adopted in the longer term as part of routine surveillance methods. Therefore, a bespoke questionnaire set will be designed specifically for this the LIFETIME System from low cost but standardized and validated measures already available. The LIFETIME System development team will include experts in child development (psychologists and pediatricians) and those with longitudinal cohort expertise and the final LIFETIME Primary Questionnaire Set will include questionnaire tools covering both the child's health and their neurodevelopmental status. Early reviews of possible questionnaires for the Primary Age Questionnaire Set include: MacArthur Health and Behaviour Questionnaire[18], Paediatric Symptoms Checklist[19], Patient-Reported

Outcomes Measurement Information System- Pediatric Bank v1.0 - Cognitive Function[20]. The final decision on the questionnaires will be made in month four of the project to allow for validity assessment in Stage 3.

Figure 2. Graphical display of the screening element of the LIFETIME System

Developing administration procedures for the LIFETIME System

The ability to provide a flexible system delivery through different collection formats is required for the LIFETIME System. Typically, longitudinal parent-reported child health and neurodevelopmental data are collected via in person, paper or telephone-based questionnaires. Whilst these approaches may work in the context of certain services they may require too much resource for others (e.g., staff to complete telephone contacts with participants). To address these barriers, both web-based and App based delivery of the questionnaires will be trialed in the feasibility studies (stages 3 and 4) alongside more standardized completion, where needed.

As part of the ConcePTION Study, Work Package 2 partners including the Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency (MHRA) are repurposing

the WEB-RADR App (<https://web-radr.eu/>) to optimize it for pregnancy pharmacovigilance. WEB-RADR is an adverse event reporting App which will be extended as part of WP2 Demonstration Project 5 to create the ConcePTION App. This update will include an extension to include two key structured question sets: the ConcePTION Core Data Elements for pregnancy and immediate child outcomes, and the LIFETIME System questionnaires to provide the longer term follow up aspect of this initiative. The App will be utilized by some data collectors to deploy the questionnaires to participating women and send push notifications of relevant information and reminders.

Outputs Stage 2: The outputs from Stage 2 will be the developed questionnaire sets in electronic format and the delivery infrastructure (Web- based platform and App) for the feasibility and validity studies in Stages 3 and 4.

10.3. Stage 3: Assessment of the validity of the Primary Age Questionnaire Set.

Objective: To investigate the validity of the chosen questionnaire for the LIFETIME System to detect the health and neurodevelopmental difficulties associated with in utero exposure to sodium valproate.

Month: 3-6

Research Questions:

- Can the selected Primary Age Questionnaire Set detect the known neurodevelopmental difficulties associated with in utero exposure to sodium valproate?

The ASQ-3 has been trialed in the assessment of children exposed to certain medicines [21] and in infants born prematurely[22], as well as being used widely internationally as a general neurodevelopmental screening measure. However, because of the need for a more diverse set of measures as the child reaches 7 years of age a more bespoke set of measures will have to be selected and therefore

require trialing in a relevant population to determine that they are a sensitive and valid set of measurements to detect patterns of impairment associated with *in utero* exposure. Therefore, once assembled, the final LIFETIME Primary Questionnaire Set will be trialed by parents of children with Fetal Valproate Spectrum Disorder (FVSD) using a cross section observational cohort design. FVSD is a condition which can occur following prenatal exposure to the antiseizure medication sodium valproate and has a documented impact on child health and neurodevelopment[7]. Comparator data will be gathered from a set of non-exposed controls to ensure the Primary Questionnaire Set's ability to detect health and neurodevelopmental symptoms associated with a medication exposure.

Procedure

The finalized Primary Age Questionnaire Set will be re-created on an electronic platform hosted by the University of Manchester. Ethical approval will be obtained to promote this study through international charities which specialize in supporting families with children diagnosed with Fetal Valproate Spectrum Disorder [7], formally Fetal Valproate Syndrome. Parents of children and young people with Fetal Valproate Spectrum Disorder will be invited to take part in this study by the charities they are partnered with. Potential participants will respond to the invitation through an electronic link which will take the respondent to the Participant Information Sheet and the Consent Form. Following the provision of consent, participants will be asked to complete the Primary Questionnaire Set relevant to their child's age, through a Web-based platform. Using a standardized form at the end of the questionnaire, parents will also be asked to provide feedback regarding the acceptability of the questionnaire and its suitability to detect any difficulties their child experience.

Participating families will be asked at the end of the questionnaire if they or family members have children of a similar age to their young person who are unexposed to sodium valproate. They would be asked to complete the questionnaire for an unexposed sibling or to share a link to the study with their family member. Collection of data on siblings or family members where there is no history of exposure will allow for a comparator group to be established for this investigation.

Eligibility

Parents will be eligible for participation if:

- they are a parent of a child with Fetal Valproate Spectrum Disorder
 - o or for the comparator group, they are related to the parent of a child without exposure in the womb to sodium valproate.
- their child is aged between 6 years and 8 years 11 months.
- they can read and respond in written English.
- they are able to provide informed consent to participate

Variables

In this stage to validate the use of the chosen questionnaires the following will be measured:

- **Feasibility** – the number of families who consent to complete the questionnaires.
- **Completion rates**- the number of successfully completed questionnaires.
- **Acceptability** – women will be asked to provide their opinions on the usefulness and the suitability of the questionnaires to provide the information they view as important.
- **Validity** – the pattern of reporting and whether it has the validity to detect health and neurodevelopmental outcomes known to be influenced by exposure to valproate versus the comparator group. Additionally, the validity of the questionnaires will be investigated through the pattern of responding and whether it is concordant with the known pattern of health and neurodevelopmental difficulties in Fetal Valproate Spectrum Disorder.

Data and analysis

Responses to the bespoke Primary Age Questionnaire Set will be collated and analyzed to determine recruitment rates, completion rates and acceptability.

Appropriate statistical tests (e.g., t-test and Chi-square) will be used to examine differences between the group with Fetal Valproate Spectrum Disorder and the control group (friends and family no exposure group); should large enough numbers be obtained, analysis adjusting for confounder and mediating factors will

be undertaken (e.g. multiple linear and logistic regression analyses). The Primary Age Questionnaire Set would be considered sensitive if it identifies the difficulties known to occur at a higher rate in valproate exposed children (e.g., poorer ascertainment of language and motor milestones, language and social functioning and increased risk of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) and autistic spectrum disorders (ASD)).

Sample Size

The selected assessment measures from which the LIFETIME question set for assessment of age 4-7year olds are drawn will all have been previously validated. The current study will assess the validity and sensitivity of the LIFETIME derived Primary Age Questionnaire Set to detect differences between valproate-exposed and non-exposed individuals. Given that valproate is known to have a relatively large effect on development at 30-40% of exposed children[23], a sample size of 20-30 participants in each group will be sufficient to detect differences with 80% power and a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ [24].

Output(s) Stage 3: Following this validity pilot an internal Demonstration Study report will be drafted. Modifications to the LIFETIME Primary Age Questionnaire Set will be made where required, as indicated by feedback received from participants and any methodological issues that arise. The data collected from the parents of children and young people with Fetal Valproate Spectrum Disorder will be written up for publication demonstrating the suitability of the LIFETIME Primary Questionnaires Set to detect health and neurodevelopmental outcomes in the context of medication exposure.

10.4. Stage 4. To test the feasibility and acceptability of the LIFETIME Questionnaire Set, in already established research cohorts.

Objective: To test the feasibility and acceptability the LIFETIME Primary Age Questionnaire Set in an already established research cohort.

Months: 5-16

Research Questions:

- Is it feasible to collect data in middle childhood using the LIFETIME Primary Age Questionnaire Set?

- Are any developmental differences identifiable across the individual antiepileptic medication exposure groups?

This stage will investigate the feasibility and the acceptability of using the LIFETIME Primary Age Questionnaire set for cross sectional neurodevelopmental and child data collection in an already established research cohorts. A small number of participating Collaborating Groups will be invited to take part in this set of investigations as well as the prospective feasibility pilot in Stage 5.

Procedure

Groups who wish to collaborate on this Stage's investigations will be supported through the provision of standardised documents that can be adapted or included in local study protocols and applications. Once approvals are in place, women enrolled in the Group's Study (e.g., their pregnancy register, cohort study or other) will be invited to participate. If agreeable, a link to the participant information sheet and online consent form will be provided. Once consent has been obtained, the LIFETIME Primary Age Questionnaire Set will be completed.

Eligibility

Women and their children will be eligible for this study if:

- they were enrolled in the specific collaborating project during pregnancy
- their child is aged between 6 years and 8 years 11 months

Variables

This study will collect the following feasibility variables:

- Process: is it feasible to collect longer term health and neurodevelopmental data by retrospectively approaching and obtaining data from women previously enrolled prospectively in pregnancy surveillance systems which were primary for the collection of congenital anomaly outcomes?
 - Does the pilot methodology lead to recruitment rates of greater than 50% of eligible mother-child pairs?
 - Can missing data be kept below 10% for questionnaire completion?

- Resources: what are the resources required for the set-up of retrospectively contacting families who were previously enrolled?
 - Were there any common barriers to establishing retrospective contact with participants for collaborating groups?
 - What was the number of months this process took?
- Management: what were the data management issues associated with this study?
 - What adaptations were required to ethical and data governance approvals? Were there any common barriers here?
 - What adaptations to data management were required?
- Scientific: What were the outcomes on the questionnaires in this context?
 - Was the data distributed as expected in terms of means, standard deviations and rates of below cut off scores?

Data and analysis

Data will be collected directly from the women either through a secure web-based platform or through the ConcePTION App, developed in Stage 2. Once complete the data will be downloaded into SPSS 25 for analysis. Feasibility of this as a data collection method will be measured by the time taken to establish data collection using the LIFETIME Primary Questionnaire Set for the Neurodevelopment in Babies Born to Mothers with Epilepsy (NaME) Study cohort (aged between 6 and 8 years of age), from ethical submission through to a complete data set for analysis. Acceptability will be measured through the completion rate. Defining a precise acceptable response rate is difficult as this can be influenced by a variety of factors, but a response rate of ~65% has been suggested as a good general marker for self-completion questionnaires[25]. Analysis of outcomes across the different antiseizure medication groups will be undertaken using logistic regression for categorical scores and linear regression where the outcome is measured in a continuous manner.

Sample size

This is a feasibility pilot to test retrospectively contacting families previously enrolled in surveillance systems to obtain longer term health and

neurodevelopmental data. The feasibility sample has been set at a minimum of 100 mother-child pairs, which is 10% of a full study, which includes several different medications.

Output(s) Stage 4: An internal study report will be written reporting the feasibility of using the LIFETIME System with a cross sectional methodology in an already establishing research cohort. Data regarding the pattern of outcomes for each of the included medications will additionally be written up for publication.

10.5. Stage 5. To pilot the system in 'real world' disease specific pregnancy registers and teratology information services

Objective: To pilot prospectively the LIFETIME System in established pregnancy pharmacovigilance surveillance programs such as disease specific pregnancy registers and teratology information services.

Month: 1-24

Research Questions:

- Is it feasible to use the LIFETIME System for the prospective collection of data in different settings?

From the work undertaken in Stage 1, 2 and 3 of the demonstration project, the prospective element of the LIFETIME System (summarized in Figure 1) will be piloted for feasibility and acceptability of administering the infant ASQ-3 questionnaires at 6, 12 and 24 months of age.

Setting

The pilot will take place in different Collaborating Groups, but at a minimum will be piloted in one disease specific pregnancy register and one teratology information service. The UK and Ireland Epilepsy and Pregnancy Register and The Netherlands Pharmacovigilance Centre Lareb have agreed to be Collaborating Groups for the LIFETIME System. Further Collaborating Groups will be identified during the undertaking of this demonstration project. The LIFETIME Research

Team will work with Collaborating Groups to identify the individual adaptations they specifically require, and the optimal route of data collection for their network.

Eligibility

Given that the aim of this demonstration project is to develop and trial the feasibility and acceptability of integrating longer term follow up routinely within already running pregnancy pharmacovigilance surveillance systems a wide ranging inclusion criteria will be employed.

- Women who are enrolled or in the process of being enrolled in one of the Host Systems
 - o Women who are/were taking a medication at one or more times during their pregnancy
 - o Women who have enrolled where they were not taking a medication during the pregnancy (where applicable and available in the Collaborating Groups)
- Women who are willing to provide information regarding their child's development

Procedure

Women will be recruited during pregnancy through the Collaborating Group's standard procedures. Consent to follow up with women for the extended period will be obtained through modifications to the Collaborating Group's information consent process, as required. Women will be followed prospectively through the series of data collection points outlined in Figure 1.

Data collection

The collection of exposure information including the medication, its route of administration and its dose will be collected using the Collaborating Groups current methods. This may include data collection from the mother or from medical/ pharmacy records. Pregnancy information will also be collected in this way. Work will be undertaken to map this information to the ConcePTION Common Data Elements, to ensure key information is available regarding the exposure and required confounders. Although data collection using the LIFETIME System will be standardized across Collaborating Groups in terms of the measures

used, variations in the systems used by Collaborating Groups and potential differences in the preferences of participants require a flexible approach to administration. Data will be collected from the mother in her native language. This flexible approach will be ensured by utilizing three different methods of data collection, including:

- The ConcePTION Study App (LIFETIME section) designed in Stage 1 or it's web-based interface.
- On paper, via post, or a web-based questionnaire
- Via the telephone (certain collaborating centres only)

The exact deployment method chosen will depend on the Collaborating Group's capabilities and information governance limitations. Where the Collaborating Group is able, women will be offered a choice regarding the data collection method. Completed information, however collected, will be owned by the Collaborating Group.

Each Collaborating Group will be provided with either a standardized local database for the LIFETIME data or the standardized LIFETIME fields to add to their own existing database. It is expected that this will vary across Collaborating Groups depending on their current infrastructure. Data collected via the ConcePTION App or it's web-based interface will be held temporarily in the MHRA repository within the Amazon Cloud in a partitioned manner. Each Collaborating Group will be able to manually download their own participant data directly into their local database (e.g., questionnaire data completed over the phone for example) and will only access and view their own data. Further a shared workspace is being developed in collaboration with ConcePTION WP7 on the anDREa platform to allow for the processing, analysis and storage of data from different data collectors. Each Collaborating Group will download the data from the MHRA repository periodically and store within their own database during and after the period of this demonstration project, to ensure sustainability.

Variables

This study will assess the feasibility of the LIFETIME System. Questionnaires will be sent to the Collaborating Groups to understand their experiences. Feasibility will be measured through the following domains:

- Process: Do the piloted procedures amount to a system capable of widespread international recruitment and longer-term child follow up?
 - What percentage of eligible women at the participating sites consent to longer term follow up with the LIFETIME System?
 - Once recruited, what are the retention rates until 24 months?
 - What are the levels of missing data for those who participate?
- Resources: What are the resources required to execute this methodology in individual Collaborating Groups?
 - What are the general infrastructure costs of the system?
 - What are the per participant costs for data collection from pregnancy through to 12 months of age?
- Management: What are the data management considerations associated with this study?
 - What adaptations to the Collaborating Groups current data flows, databases and data management plans are needed?
 - Are the proposed procedures compliant with the applicable data protection laws?
- Scientific: Are the questionnaire data consistent with the normative sample data for the ASQ-3?
 - Are the score ranges and distributions as expected?
 - Are the published cut off's applicable in this context?
 - What are the rates of below average development for the children assessed as part of this?

Study Size

This study is a feasibility study investigating the establishment of the LIFETIME longer term child health and neurodevelopmental surveillance system. As many women will be recruited to this through the Collaborating Groups as possible within the 24-month period in order to test feasibility of recruitment. However, due to the per person screening cost associated with the ASQ-3 a limit of 500 families will included, providing ratings at 6 and 12 months of age, across all Collaborating Groups.

Data Analysis

Data will be analyzed investigating the feasibility and the acceptability of the LIFETIME System from the questionnaire completed by Collaborating Groups. Frequency information will be provided with regards to number of women recruited in specific time periods by specific Collaborating Groups and as a total by medication type. Rates of completion of the ASQ questionnaires at each age point, stratified by key demographic variables will be calculated. Rates of questionnaire completion and missing data will also be calculated.

Output(s) Stage 5: An internal study report and academic publication will be written reporting to results of these feasibility pilot.

10.6. Stage 6. To develop and test a secure data sharing platform where data from different collecting programs can combine data

Objective: To develop the agreements, data flows and infrastructure required to combine data from different Collaborating Groups and to test the feasibility of data combining.

Months: 17-24

Research Questions:

- Is it feasible to combine standardised data collected through the LIFETIME System from different collaborators?

Once LIFETIME System data collection is established in more than one Collaborating Group's System, the ability to combine data from multiple Collaborating Group's will be piloted. Combining data which has been collected in a standardized manner across different Collaborating Groups offers an opportunity to reduce the time taken to obtain adequate sample sizes and therefore will reduce the time taken for data to be available for women, regulators and prescribers. The infrastructure for the combining of data, collected to the LIFETIME System specification, will therefore be developed as part of this demonstration project in collaboration with ConcePTION Study colleagues within WP7. The feasibility of data transfer into this infrastructure will be piloted.

Section 1.01 Study Design

This will be a feasibility study which investigates the combining data from individual Collaborating Groups. This will be trialed focusing on data regarding the development of children exposed to the antiseizure medications, due to the UK and Ireland Epilepsy and Pregnancy Register early commitment to the project. The exact exposures included will be determined by the data available during the project.

Procedure

Collaborating groups will be asked to provide information on what data they have collected using the LIFETIME System on the selected antiseizure medications. Collaborating Groups who have not collected pregnancy and immediate child outcomes data to the ConcePTION Common Data Elements will be sent a questionnaire to determine comparability of their pregnancy, exposure and demographic data against the ConcePTION Common Data Elements.

Data combining

The pilot would test the feasibility of combining data on development at 6 months of age as measured by the ASQ-3. Preparatory work will be undertaken with Collaborating Groups to understand the data management requirements generally as well as local information governance rules. Depending on the outcome of these investigations data would either be analyzed as a pre-written script and then the aggregate data uploaded, or analysis will be conducted centrally on the anonymized individual participant level data. Part of this process is to understand the feasibility of dealing with aggregate or participant level data in this manner.

Supported by ConcePTION WP7, a secure and compliant system will be created to allow for a joint workspace in which to combine and analysis data from the different Collaborating Groups.

Variables

This is an investigation regarding the feasibility of combining data from multiple Collaborating Groups who have collected longer term child health and development data using the LIFETIME System (6-month data collection timepoint only). This information will be collected from the Collaborating Groups via a questionnaire with the following variables considered:

- Process: Are the proposed processes feasible?
 - Is data alignment (pregnancy and exposure information) and combining feasible?
 - What are the steps involved with alignment and combining and what are the challenges?
- Resources: What are the resources required?
 - In the Collaborating Groups and at the lead site?
 - What data infrastructure was needed and what were the costs of this?
- Management: What are the data management steps associated with combining data across multiple Collaborating Groups?
 - What adaptations to current processes are needed?
 - Are the proposed procedures fully compliant with relevant data protection rules? Are there any country specific limitations for consideration?
- Scientific: Is analysis possible on combined data?
 - Is aggregate level data or participant level data the most appropriate?
 - Does the combined data produce means, standard deviations and cut offs within the expected ranges?
 - What at the rates of below average performance on the ASQ-3 at 6 months?

Output(s) Stage 6. The primary output from Stage 6 will be a written report on the feasibility and success of aligning and combining data from the LIFETIME System's Collaborating Groups for central analysis. A collaboration will be undertaken with ConcePTION WP8, to identify opportunities for sustainability of the LIFETIME System, should it be a sensitive, valid and feasible way forward for the routine collection of child neurodevelopment and health outcomes.

11. Data sources

A variety of different data sources will be utilised across the stages of this study. These are displayed in the table below.

Table 2. Data sources expected to be utilised for each of the objectives.

	Objective	Data sources
Stage 1.	Development Stages	
Stage 2.		
Stage 3.	To investigate the validity of the chosen questionnaire set to determine the health and neurodevelopmental difficulties associated with in utero exposure to sodium valproate	Data will be obtained through collaboration with Charities who support families of children with Fetal Valproate Spectrum Disorder. This will include international Charities but limited to English speaking countries.
Stage 4.	To test the feasibility and acceptability of the LIFETIME Primary Age Questionnaire Set in an already established research cohort.	Collaborating Groups will be identified who are interested in testing retrospective recruitment. This will include disease specific pregnancy registers and teratology information services.
Stage 5.	To pilot integration of the LIFETIME System into established prospective pregnancy pharmacovigilance programs such as disease specific pregnancy registers and teratology information service derived cohorts.	Collaborating Groups will be identified as part of Stage 1 of this Demonstration Study. Currently, the UK and Ireland Epilepsy and Pregnancy Register and The Netherlands Pharmacovigilance Centre Lareb are interested in collaborating on feasibility testing.
Stage 6.	To develop and test a secure platform where data from different LIFETIME System Collaborating Groups can be combined.	Data sources will be dependent on those identified and by the type of data (e.g., medication exposures they collect).

12. Quality control

In order to ensure quality over the development of the LIFETIME System and the pilot, monthly core group meetings will be scheduled to occur every quarter. With each Collaborating Group collecting their own data, several audit principles will be drafted around the completion of data collection, recording and handling missing data.

13. Limitations of the research methods

The LIFETIME System is an ambitious plan to introduce routine child health and neurodevelopmental screening into teratology information services and prospective pregnancy registers in Europe. Given the novelty of this approach the aim is to test feasibility and acceptability rather than to collect data to investigate outcomes for specific medication exposures. However, if feasible and acceptable the system can continue to run following the pilot phase and will lead to the generation of adequately powered data sets to investigate child outcomes following specific exposures. The nature of this investigation also limits analysis of confounders and other potential biases. These will be investigated through future work.

Child development unfolds over a protracted period and therefore a complete prospective pilot stretching until the child is in the second decade of life cannot be ascertained in 24 months. In order to gain experiences with the types of data that will be collected at older ages, a retrospective cross-sectional data collection pilot in study 4 is being undertaken. Future work would test a prospective data system which starts in pregnancy and seamlessly follows the child up into the second decade of life.

Finally, signals of poorer outcomes must be followed up with more comprehensive investigations. The investigation of these additional follow ups are beyond the scope of this demonstration project but will be addressed in the ConcePTION Study Demonstration Projects 4 and 5.

14. Data management

Detailed data management plans will be drafted for Stages 1-6 of this project.

For example, Stages 3 and 4 will be conducted by the LIFETIME Research Group based at the University of Manchester. Specific ethical approval and data management applications will be made either through the University of Manchester (Stage 3) or the UK National Health Service (Stage 4) depending on the origin of the cohort to be utilised.

In Stage 5 and 6 Data will be collected by the Collaborating Groups who will be based in different European countries. Data management plans will need to be unique to Collaborating Groups, considering general principles determined by the Study Group in addition to local standard data management policies. Further, data management protocols may vary across individual participating centres depending on their current surveillance set up and how they choose to implement the LIFETIME System (e.g., App, electronic questionnaire etc). No identifiable information would be made available to the Lifetime Research Group, but analysis of data pertaining to recruitment, retention, completion and acceptability data will be made available to the LIFETIME Research Group as part of this Demonstration Project. Part of the approach into data combining will include consultancy on the required data management processes both internationally and at a local level for the Collaborating Groups. Currently, work is being undertaken to look at the anDREa platform.

The parties to this agreement and individuals acting on their behalf hereby commit to adhere to the rules of the ENCePP Code of Conduct in their entirety.

15. Protection of human subjects

Given that this pilot will be taking part across several different countries, local policies regarding the protection of human subjects will apply. Each Collaborating Group must meet their country specific obligations.

16. Management and reporting of adverse events/adverse reactions

Data will be collected, processed and held at the Collaborating Group (e.g., the specific pregnancy register or teratology information service provision). The reporting of adverse events in relation to child development will be undertaken by the Collaborating Group as part of their local, already established processes.

17. Plans for disseminating and communicating study results

The results of the Lifetime System design and pilots will be written up for publication in relevant journals as well as in the ConcePTION Demonstration Project 3 reports. The data will be submitted to relevant conferences such as the European Network of Teratology Information Services and other disease specific conferences where the use of pregnancy registers is high (e.g., Epilepsy and Neurology Conferences). In order to maximize the impact and likely uptake of the final system we would also seek to engage directly with prospective Collaborating Groups of the system to obtain feedback and user experience. We will also work with industry and regulatory partners to ensure that the sustainability and up take of this system is maximized.

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Annex 1. ENCePP checklist for study protocols

ENCePP Checklist for Study Protocols (Revision 4)

Adopted by the ENCePP Steering Group on 15/10/2018

The [European Network of Centres for Pharmacoepidemiology and Pharmacovigilance \(ENCePP\)](#) welcomes innovative designs and new methods of research. This Checklist has been developed by ENCePP to stimulate consideration of important principles when designing and writing a pharmacoepidemiological or pharmacovigilance study protocol. The Checklist is intended to promote the quality of such studies, not their uniformity. The user is also referred to the [ENCePP Guide on Methodological Standards in Pharmacoepidemiology](#), which reviews and gives direct electronic access to guidance for research in pharmacoepidemiology and pharmacovigilance.

For each question of the Checklist, the investigator should indicate whether or not it has been addressed in the study protocol. If the answer is "Yes", the section number of the protocol where this issue has been discussed should be specified. It is possible that some questions do not apply to a particular study (for example, in the case of an innovative study design). In this case, the answer 'N/A' (Not Applicable) can be checked and the "Comments" field included for each section should be used to explain why. The "Comments" field can also be used to elaborate on a "No" answer.

This Checklist should be included as an Annex by marketing authorisation holders when submitting the protocol of a non-interventional post-authorisation safety study (PASS) to a regulatory authority (see the [Guidance on the format and content of the protocol of non-interventional post-authorisation safety studies](#)). The Checklist is a supporting document and does not replace the format of the protocol for PASS presented in the Guidance and Module VIII of the Good pharmacovigilance practices (GVP).

Study title:

Long-term investigation following exposure to individual medicines in utero: The LIFETIME system

EU PAS Register® number:

Study reference number (if applicable):

<u>Section 1: Milestones</u>	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
1.1 Does the protocol specify timelines for				5
1.1.1 Start of data collection ¹	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
1.1.2 End of data collection ²	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
1.1.3 Progress report(s)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
1.1.4 Interim report(s)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
1.1.5 Registration in the EU PAS Register®	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
1.1.6 Final report of study results.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

¹ Date from which information on the first study is first recorded in the study dataset or, in the case of secondary use of data, the date from which data extraction starts.

² Date from which the analytical dataset is completely available.

Comments:

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Section 2: Research question	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
2.1 Does the formulation of the research question and objectives clearly explain:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	7
2.1.1 Why the study is conducted? (e.g. to address an important public health concern, a risk identified in the risk management plan, an emerging safety issue)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2.1.2 The objective(s) of the study?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2.1.3 The target population? (i.e. population or subgroup to whom the study results are intended to be generalised)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
2.1.4 Which hypothesis(-es) is (are) to be tested?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
2.1.5 If applicable, that there is no <i>a priori</i> hypothesis?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Comments:

This study is regarding the design and feasibility test of a novel methodological approach and therefore there is no <i>a priori</i> hypothesis.
--

Section 3: Study design	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
3.1 Is the study design described? (e.g. cohort, case-control, cross-sectional, other design)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10
3.2 Does the protocol specify whether the study is based on primary, secondary or combined data collection?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10
3.3 Does the protocol specify measures of occurrence? (e.g., rate, risk, prevalence)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.3, 10.4, 10.5 & 10.6
3.4 Does the protocol specify measure(s) of association? (e.g. risk, odds ratio, excess risk, rate ratio, hazard ratio, risk/rate difference, number needed to harm (NNH))	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
3.5 Does the protocol describe the approach for the collection and reporting of adverse events/adverse reactions? (e.g. adverse events that will not be collected in case of primary data collection)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	16

Comments:

There is no specification of measures of association as this is a design and feasibility study.

Section 4: Source and study populations	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
4.1 Is the source population described?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.3, 10.4, 10.5 & 10.6
4.2 Is the planned study population defined in terms of:				
4.2.1 Study time period	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
4.2.2 Age and sex	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
4.2.3 Country of origin	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
4.2.4 Disease/indication	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.3, 10.4, 10.5 & 10.6
4.2.5 Duration of follow-up	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
4.3 Does the protocol define how the study population will be sampled from the source population? (e.g. event or inclusion/exclusion criteria)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

Comments:

This study is a design and feasibility study and therefore there are certain source and study population elements which are not applicable.

Section 5: Exposure definition and measurement	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
5.1 Does the protocol describe how the study exposure is defined and measured? (e.g. operational details for defining and categorising exposure, measurement of dose and duration of drug exposure)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.5
5.2 Does the protocol address the validity of the exposure measurement? (e.g. precision, accuracy, use of validation sub-study)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
5.3 Is exposure categorised according to time windows?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
5.4 Is intensity of exposure addressed? (e.g. dose, duration)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
5.5 Is exposure categorised based on biological mechanism of action and taking into account the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of the drug?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
5.6 Is (are) (an) appropriate comparator(s) identified?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

Comments:

Exposure information is not relevant to all stages of the investigation.

Section 6: Outcome definition and measurement	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
6.1 Does the protocol specify the primary and secondary (if applicable) outcome(s) to be investigated?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.3, 10.2 , 10.4 & 10.5
6.2 Does the protocol describe how the outcomes are defined and measured?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.3, 10.2 , 10.4 & 10.5
6.3 Does the protocol address the validity of outcome measurement? (e.g. precision, accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, use of validation sub-study)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
6.4 Does the protocol describe specific outcomes relevant for Health Technology Assessment? (e.g. HRQoL, QALYs, DALYS, health care services utilisation, burden of disease or treatment, compliance, disease management)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

Comments:

This looks at feasibility in terms of process, resources, management and scientific methods; therefore there is no single primary outcome.

Section 7: Bias	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
7.1 Does the protocol address ways to measure confounding? (e.g. confounding by indication)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
7.2 Does the protocol address selection bias? (e.g. healthy user/adherer bias)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
7.3 Does the protocol address information bias? (e.g. misclassification of exposure and outcomes, time-related bias)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

Comments:

This is a design and feasibility study and therefore biases are not being addressed.

Section 8: Effect measure modification	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
8.1 Does the protocol address effect modifiers? (e.g. collection of data on known effect modifiers, sub-group analyses, anticipated direction of effect)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

Comments:

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Section 9: Data sources	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
9.1 Does the protocol describe the data source(s) used in the study for the ascertainment of:				
9.1.1 Exposure? (e.g. pharmacy dispensing, general practice prescribing, claims data, self-report, face-to-face interview)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.5
9.1.2 Outcomes? (e.g. clinical records, laboratory markers or values, claims data, self-report, patient interview including scales and questionnaires, vital statistics)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.4, 10.5, 10.6
9.1.3 Covariates and other characteristics?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
9.2 Does the protocol describe the information available from the data source(s) on:				
9.2.1 Exposure? (e.g. date of dispensing, drug quantity, dose, number of days of supply prescription, daily dosage, prescriber)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
9.2.2 Outcomes? (e.g. date of occurrence, multiple event, severity measures related to event)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.5
9.2.3 Covariates and other characteristics? (e.g. age, sex, clinical and drug use history, co-morbidity, co-medications, lifestyle)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.5
9.3 Is a coding system described for:				
9.3.1 Exposure? (e.g. WHO Drug Dictionary, Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) Classification System)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
9.3.2 Outcomes? (e.g. International Classification of Diseases (ICD), Medical Dictionary for Regulatory Activities (MedDRA))	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
9.3.3 Covariates and other characteristics?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.5
9.4 Is a linkage method between data sources described? (e.g. based on a unique identifier or other)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

Comments:

Not all of the points in section 9 are applicable due to the nature of this study being one of design and feasibility investigations.

Section 10: Analysis plan	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
10.1 Are the statistical methods and the reason for their choice described?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.3, 10.4 , 10.5
10.2 Is study size and/or statistical precision estimated?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
10.3 Are descriptive analyses included?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.3, 10.4 , 10.5

Section 10: Analysis plan	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
10.4 Are stratified analyses included?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.5
10.5 Does the plan describe methods for analytic control of confounding?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
10.6 Does the plan describe methods for analytic control of outcome misclassification?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
10.7 Does the plan describe methods for handling missing data?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
10.8 Are relevant sensitivity analyses described?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Comments:

Statistics are basic due to the type of investigations. There are no formal study size calculations as this study is investigating feasibility.

Section 11: Data management and quality control	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
11.1 Does the protocol provide information on data storage? (e.g. software and IT environment, database maintenance and anti-fraud protection, archiving)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.4, 10.5
11.2 Are methods of quality assurance described?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	11
11.3 Is there a system in place for independent review of study results?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Comments:

There is no system for independent review of the study results due to this being a design and feasibility study.

Section 12: Limitations	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
12.1 Does the protocol discuss the impact on the study results of:				
12.1.1 Selection bias?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
12.1.2 Information bias?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
12.1.3 Residual/unmeasured confounding? (e.g. anticipated direction and magnitude of such biases, validation sub-study, use of validation and external data, analytical methods).	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.5
12.2 Does the protocol discuss study feasibility? (e.g. study size, anticipated exposure uptake, duration of follow-up in a cohort study, patient recruitment, precision of the estimates)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.3, 10.4, 10.5, 10.6

Comments:

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<u>Section 13: Ethical/data protection issues</u>	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
13.1 Have requirements of Ethics Committee/ Institutional Review Board been described?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	10.5, 15
13.2 Has any outcome of an ethical review procedure been addressed?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
13.3 Have data protection requirements been described?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	14

Comments:

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<u>Section 14: Amendments and deviations</u>	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
14.1 Does the protocol include a section to document amendments and deviations?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	4

Comments:

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<u>Section 15: Plans for communication of study results</u>	Yes	No	N/A	Section Number
15.1 Are plans described for communicating study results (e.g. to regulatory authorities)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	15
15.2 Are plans described for disseminating study results externally, including publication?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	15

Comments:

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Name of the main author of the
protocol:

Dr Rebecca Bromley

Date: 30/08/2021

Signature

:

EUPAS 44505

Demonstration study 2.5.5

Validation of primary source pregnancy exposure and outcomes
(pharmacovigilance data)

PASS information

Title	Demonstration study 2.5.5 of the ConcePTION project; Validation of primary source pregnancy exposure and outcomes (pharmacovigilance data)
Protocol version identifier	Draft 0.5
Date of last version of protocol	Nov-21
EU PAS register number	In draft; not yet registered
Active substance	Various and unrestricted; Demonstration of validation testing of primary source pregnancy exposure and outcomes (pharmacovigilance data), including reports of medication exposures in pregnancy, concomitant risk factors for adverse pregnancy outcomes, pregnancy/fetal outcomes, and infant/childhood neurodevelopmental assessments
Medicinal product	Medicinal products authorized in the European Union and/or the United Kingdom
Product reference	NA
Procedure number	NA
Research question and objectives	The overarching aim of this demonstration project is to ascertain whether self-reporting methods of data collection in pregnancy exposure and outcomes can be considered reliable for pharmacovigilance purposes. The main objective of demonstration study 2.5.5 is to compare the completeness and accuracy of self-reported pregnancy pharmacovigilance data with corresponding data supplied by healthcare professionals (HCPs) in a variety of different contexts. The validation exercises undertaken in this demonstration project will be split into two main sub-studies.
Joint PASS	NA
EFPIA partners	Novartis Group
Academic partners/ENTIS centres	UK Teratology Information Service, Newcastle upon Tyne Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust The Netherlands Pharmacovigilance Centre Lareb The University of Manchester KRISP, University of KwaZulu-Natal, Durban, South Africa
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2. List of abbreviations

NA – Not applicable
MS – Multiple sclerosis
TIS – Teratology Information Service
PV – Pharmacovigilance
WP2 – Work Package 2 (ConcePTION Project)
HCPs – Healthcare professionals
ICSRs – Individual Case Safety Reports
SRS – Spontaneous Reporting Systems
MAHs – Marketing Authorisation Holders
AR(s) - Adverse Reaction(s)
SSRIs - Selective Serotonin Reuptake Inhibitors
CDE – Core Data Elements (as defined in WP2 Task 3)
SOC – System Organ Class (MedDRA term)
ASD – Autism Spectrum Disorder
LIFETIME - Long-term Investigation and Follow-up of health and neurodevelopment following Exposure To Individual MEDicinal products in utero
FVSD – Fetal Valproate Spectrum Disorder
NHS – National Health Service
UMAN – The University of Manchester
NUTH - Newcastle upon Tyne Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust
PII – Personally Identifiable Information

3. Responsible parties

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CH-4002 Basel
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The Netherlands Pharmacovigilance Centre Lareb
Goudsbloemvallei 7, 5237 MH 's-Hertogenbosch
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4. Abstract

Demonstration study 2.5.5 of the ConcePTION project will conduct research into the validation of primary source (self-reported) pregnancy exposure and outcomes (pharmacovigilance data).

The overarching aim of this research is to ascertain whether self-reporting (predominantly by consumers of medicines, i.e. patients) of pregnancy exposures and maternal/child outcomes provides sufficiently accurate evidence to be considered reliable for pharmacovigilance purposes. The main objective of demonstration study 2.5.5 is to compare the completeness and accuracy of self-reported pregnancy pharmacovigilance data with corresponding data supplied by healthcare professionals (HCPs) in a variety of different contexts. The validation exercises undertaken in this demonstration project will be split into two independent sub-studies.

Sub-study 1 will focus on validation testing of primary source pregnancy exposure and outcomes (pharmacovigilance data), including reports of medication exposures in pregnancy, concomitant risk factors for adverse pregnancy outcomes, pregnancy/fetal/child outcomes by sequential review of reports first submitted by patients or other non-healthcare professionals, and subsequently by HCPs. This research will be based on expert review of source documents in chronological order. Comparisons will be made between the original reports from non-HCPs, and the evidence reported by qualified HCPs. The review will enable the compilation of both qualitative and quantitative data in order to assess the validity of the non-HCP sourced reports.

Sub-study 2 will undertake child health and neurodevelopmental assessments conducted during clinical reviews to validate data provided by parents through remotely completed questionnaires. The reports from the non-HCPs (parents) will be compared with data from the formal clinical reviews conducted in person by trained experts. Detailed qualitative and quantitative comparisons will be made in order to assess the reliability and clinical validity of data from non-HCP (parental) sources.

Findings from sub-studies 1 and 2 will be evaluated and summarised to inform on the suitability of self-reporting methods of data collection in pregnancy pharmacovigilance research. We aim to publish a report in a peer-reviewed journal, which describes the findings of the two sub-studies. Recommendations will be provided for further developments and future research.

In conclusion, the ultimate objective of this research is to provide a measure of the level of confidence which can be applied to non-HCP sourced data concerning exposures to medicines during pregnancy and the associated outcomes of those exposures. This work will document the validity of collecting data directly from patients for pregnancy pharmacovigilance purposes, which could enhance data collection and future pregnancy

pharmacovigilance practices, thereby reducing the latency between medication licensing and evidence of fetal risk/safety, including longer term childhood health and development.

5. Amendments and updates

Number	Date	Section of study protocol	Amendment or update	Reason
1				
2				
3				

6. Milestones

Milestone	Planned date
Start of data collection	Sub-study 1: 01/03/2022 (utilising data that has been collected between 10 July 2012 – the effective date of Implementing Regulation 520/2012 – and 31/12/2021) Sub-study 2: Between 01/07/2022 and 30/09/2022 (Q2 2022)
End of data collection	30 June 2023
Registration in the EU PAS register	December 2021
Final report of study results	30 September 2023

7. Background and rationale

7.1. ConcePTION project

Effects of drug use during pregnancy are often unknown at the time of product authorisation because the inclusion of pregnant women in clinical trials is considered unethical ([Adam 2011](#)). However, treatment during pregnancy is often needed for women with pre-existing chronic conditions such as asthma, epilepsy, cancer, multiple sclerosis (MS) and depression. In daily practice the majority of women take at least one type of medicinal product during pregnancy ([Lupatelli 2014](#), [Mitchell 2011](#), [ConcePTION 2018](#)). Knowledge about the safety of drug use during pregnancy is therefore warranted. Since limited data from studies performed prior to marketing are usually available before licensure of a medicinal product, we have to rely on post-marketing data from both primary as well as secondary data sources. With respect to the primary data, several established approaches are currently used to compile and analyse the data on the safety profile of drug use during pregnancy, including data collected by Teratology Information Services (TIS), spontaneous reports, information from literature, organised data collection programmes and registries.

The IMI-funded ConcePTION project aims to enhance the way the use of prescription medicines during pregnancy is studied ([ConcePTION 2018](#)). This is done in part by improving the collection, analysis and interpretation of pharmacovigilance data, to allow for a more systematic analyses and

exchange of data. **WP2** (Work Package 2) focusses on sources of primary data collection, such as spontaneous reports, data collected by TIS, literature, pregnancy registries, and enhanced PV studies.

7.2. Demonstration project rationale

A variety of data collection techniques are utilised in pregnancy pharmacovigilance and pharmacoepidemiology studies, with self-reported information included in many; often for data collection efficiency reasons. However, data on the validity of self-reported pharmacovigilance information in relation to pregnancy exposures to medicines is often questioned.

A considerable amount of published literature exists in which core data elements required for pregnancy pharmacovigilance have been compared between self-reported and alternative data sources. These include reports of maternal medical history [[Alves 2011](#), [Hessol 2004](#), [van Gelder 2011](#)] certain obstetric outcomes [[Gresham 2015](#), [Hure 2015](#)] and/or gestational medication exposure data [[Stephansson 2011](#), [Espnes 2011](#), [Kallen 2003](#), [Nash 2015](#), [Nielsen 2008](#), [Olesen 2001](#), [Pisa 2015](#), [Sarangarm 2012](#), [van Gelder 2013](#)] compared with such data extracted from antenatal healthcare records, [[Alves 2011](#), [Stephansson 2011](#), [Hessol 2004](#), [van Gelder 2011](#), [Nash 2015](#), [Sarangarm 2012](#), [van Gelder 2013](#)] population-based administrative datasets (including prescription/medication dispensing databases), [[Espnes 2011](#), [Kallen 2003](#), [Olesen 2001](#), [Pisa 2015](#), [van Gelder 2013](#)] birth certificate repositories, [[Pisa 2015](#)] and perinatal healthcare databases. [[Gresham 2015](#), [Hure 2015](#)] The results of these studies have demonstrated conflicting findings regarding the concordance of self-reported maternal medical history data, with two studies demonstrating adequate agreement between maternal reports and antenatal healthcare records, [[Hessol 2004](#), [van Gelder 2013](#)] but one demonstrating poor agreement for some specific conditions. [[Alves 2011](#)] Other studies also suggested that overall obstetric outcomes appear to be reported to a relatively high standard. [[Gresham 2015](#), [Hure 2015](#)] However, only certain obstetric outcomes have been investigated, and no studies have been identified which have compared the validity of self-reported birth defect data. Many of the studies investigating medication exposure agreement between maternal self-report and alternative data sources have demonstrated that accuracy varied by therapeutic class [[Stephansson 2011](#), [Espnes 2011](#), [Nielsen 2008](#), [Pisa 2015](#), [Sarangarm 2012](#), [van Gelder 2013](#)] with good concordance for those medications which were used chronically, while poor agreement was observed for medications used intermittently. [[Stephansson 2011](#), [Sarangarm 2012](#), [van Gelder 2013](#)] However, several studies also demonstrated the probability of agreement to be influenced by maternal sociodemographic characteristics, health behaviours and maternal medical conditions. [[Hessol 2004](#), [van Gelder 2011](#), [Nash 2015](#)]

Validation of some of the key data sources being utilised in ConcePTION **WP2** demonstration projects is therefore essential to ensure reliability in the systems being proposed for the future of pharmacovigilance of exposures to medicines during pregnancy.

7.3. Relationship to other demonstration projects

Validation exercises undertaken in this demonstration project will relate to two other **WP2** demonstration projects (**2.5.1** and **2.5.3**).

Demonstration project **2.5.1** focusses on pregnancy pharmacovigilance data collected in individual case safety reports (ICSRs) via spontaneous reporting systems (SRS) operated by national pharmacovigilance centres and marketing authorisation holders (MAH). The 2.5.1 demonstration project encompasses several sub-studies which aim to:

(i) describe the nature and content of ICSRs;

(ii) create, validate and utilise a clinical quality assessment tool to assess the suitability of ICSR data for pregnancy pharmacovigilance research purposes; and

(iii) test existing methods of statistical signal detection for teratogen surveillance whilst exploring the feasibility for developing novel analytical techniques.

Validation of the data contained within ICSRs is also an important aspect which deserves careful review when considering the suitability of ICSR data for pregnancy pharmacovigilance research purposes, and this will be explored in demonstration project **2.5.5**.

Demonstration project **2.5.3** aims to develop novel investigatory systems which will allow researchers to investigate a wider spectrum of child outcomes across large populations. Although there can be considerable observational data available for such medications, the longitudinal endpoints of studies which have provided these data generally focus on malformation and other obstetric outcomes, generally described up to one year of infant age at most. As the longer-term developmental effects of *in utero* teratogenic/fetotoxic events are left undetermined, including any impacts medications may have on neurodevelopment and childhood health, safety assessments relating to the risk-benefit of medication use during pregnancy are often incomplete.

In demonstration project **2.5.5** data reported via the parent-completed questionnaires will be compared to the results of face-to-face clinical reviews which will include child health, dysmorphism and neuropsychological assessment. This comparison will validate the ability of the questionnaire to collect data for child health, dysmorphism and neurodevelopmental outcome screening for large-scale implementation into future pregnancy pharmacovigilance systems.

8. Research question and objectives

The overarching aim of this demonstration project is to ascertain whether self-reporting methods of data collection for pregnancy exposures and maternal/fetal/child outcomes in women taking prescription medicines can be considered reliable for pharmacovigilance purposes. The main objective of demonstration study **2.5.5** is to compare the completeness and accuracy of self-reported pregnancy pharmacovigilance data with corresponding data supplied by healthcare professionals (HCPs) in a variety of different contexts. The validation exercises undertaken in this demonstration project will be split into two main sub-studies:

8.1. Sub-study 1

Demonstration study **2.5.5 sub-study 1 (S1)** will compare the completeness and accuracy of ICSR data provided to a MAH where data relating to the same pregnancy exposure/outcome safety event has been collected from both a medication user (self-reporter) and a healthcare professional. There will be a focus on assessing the most important data content of ICSRs by comparing specified core data elements, as defined by **WP2 Task 2.3**, including but not limited to self-reported pregnancy exposures and obstetric outcomes.

The objective of this sub-study is to ascertain how completely and accurately self-reporters describe pregnancy exposure and outcome data to MAHs via ICSR reporting systems.

8.2. Sub-study 2

Demonstration study **2.5.5 sub-study 2 (S2)** will compare the results of parentally-completed child health and neurodevelopment screening questionnaires with findings from clinical face-to-face child health, dysmorphology and neuropsychological assessments undertaken by trained clinical experts. There will be a focus on assessing the most important data content of the childhood neurodevelopment screening questionnaires by comparing specified core data elements, as defined by **WP2 Task 3**, including but not limited to self-reported pregnancy exposures and questionnaire generated scores of neurodevelopmental attainments/deficits. In order to ensure that the sample is sufficiently heterogeneous to allow for the evaluation of the sensitivity of the parent-report measures, assessments will be conducted in a cohort of children (7-16 years of age) who will be at varying levels of risk for health and neurodevelopmental difficulties. To ensure that the sample includes children at high-risk of impairment, children and young people with a diagnosis of Fetal Valproate Spectrum Disorder (FVSD, ICD 11 LD2F.03) will be recruited. This condition is associated with *in utero* exposure to sodium valproate which carries a high risk of a wide range of physical, health and neurodevelopmental complications. Additionally, a group of children exposed to valproate who have not been diagnosed with FVSD, and a group of children exposed to topiramate *in utero* will also be recruited, as they represent a more moderate or lower risk of child health and neurodevelopmental difficulties respectively. Participants recruited at each level of risk will be considered as a single group for the purpose of psychometric evaluation, and for validation analysis.

The objectives of this sub-study are to:

- (i) Identify and recruit a cohort of children and young people (aged 7-16 years) who are either already diagnosed with FVSD, who were exposed to valproate *in utero* and do not currently have a diagnosis of FVSD, or were exposed to topiramate *in utero*.
- (ii) To undertake child health and neurodevelopmental screening through the parent questionnaire set developed in Demonstration project 2.5.3.
- (iii) To undertake validation analyses to understand the sensitivity of the parentally completed questionnaires to adequately detect the presence of child health conditions, dysmorphic facial features and neurodevelopmental deficits.

It is planned that this validation study will provide data of sufficient clinical quality to allow the formulation of classification thresholds, or cut-off values, which can be applied to the scores generated from the parent reporting questionnaires that relate to specific developmental outcomes. It is expected that such a validation will enhance the clinical utility of these questionnaires and increase confidence in their sensitivity as a tool for detecting complications of longer term child health/developmental outcomes following *in utero* teratogen exposure.

9. Research methods

In both **S1** and **S2** the basis for the validation of self-reported/parentally reported exposures and outcomes is the comparison of these data with HCP-reported/measured exposures and outcomes.

9.1. Sub-study 1: Validation of self-reported pregnancy pharmacovigilance data provided to a marketing authorisation holder

Databases containing ICSRs of spontaneous reports and literature data are designed for the assessment and analysis of a wide spectrum of issues related to medicinal products (e.g. adverse reactions), but are not specifically designed to capture information on exposure to medicines during pregnancy. Further to this, women who are motivated to self-report medicine use during pregnancy may be unfamiliar with SRS, and their rights as patients to report harms associated with medicines ([Herxheimer](#), [Matos 2016](#), [Banovac 2017](#), [MHRA](#)). Nevertheless, it has been clearly demonstrated that patient reporting has proven key in identifying certain signals of potential adverse reactions (ARs) that would not otherwise have been identified and in the causality analysis of others. Examples include a signal of electric shock-like sensations associated with the use of selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) and duloxetine, prolonged sexual dysfunction after discontinuation of SSRIs, vitamin B6 and polyneuropathy, amlodipine and interaction with grapefruit juice, donepezil and unusual dreams including nightmares, and medroxyprogesterone and infertility ([Harmark 2016](#)).

It should also be recognised that it is important to record exposures to medicines during pregnancy when the outcomes for both mother and offspring are normal. However, European regulatory reporting requirements for the onward submission of ICSRs by MAHs to regulatory bodies (e.g. EMA) are restricted to suspected adverse reactions associated with the use of medicines in pregnancy ([Good Vigilance Practice Module VI](#), [Guideline on the Exposure to Medicinal Products during Pregnancy: Need for Post-Authorisation Data](#), [GVP Annex III](#), and [Good Vigilance Practice Module P.III: Pregnant and breastfeeding women](#)). Consequently, medication exposures occurring in pregnancy which result in healthy outcomes are not centrally collated. As such, the single largest source of regulatory information on pregnancy exposures (Eudravigilance) is heavily biased towards the inclusion of reports of harmful effects following exposure to medicines. In our view it is important to provide a more balanced view based on the totality of the available evidence. Our research will, therefore, concentrate on validation the content of self-reported ICSRs held by MAHs that may contribute important pregnancy pharmacovigilance information concerning both positive and negative outcomes of the exposure of the mother and fetus to medicines.

The objective of this sub-study is to ascertain how completely and accurately self-reporters describe pregnancy exposure and outcome data to MAHs via ICSR reporting systems. This will be achieved by describing and comparing the presence or absence of pregnancy exposure and outcome-related information in self-reported SRS with HCP-sourced reports associated with a range of medicinal products, as described to a MAH (Novartis). Following evaluation the results of this study will describe the presence (or absence), precision (or lack of specificity) and completeness (or gaps) concerning exposure- and outcome-related variables in self-reported SRS. It is expected that this research will reveal differences in the information that is reported by medication users (self-reporters) and their HCPs, and by evaluating these differences we hope to highlight the additional value of self-reporting to augment data collection in pregnancy pharmacovigilance research.

9.1.1. Study design

This study will be a retrospective observational study using ICSR report data collected from women taking medicines during pregnancy and solicited data from HCPs for the same ICSRs, as submitted to a MAH (Novartis). In this sub-study, several exposure- and outcome-related elements will be

assessed (in line with specified core data elements, as defined by **WP2 Task 3**), in addition the PregDoc tool developed within **WP2 Demonstration Project 2.5.1**, or a modification thereof, may be trialled to assess the quality of each case report as provided from each reporter (self-reporter and HCP). Spontaneous reports will be assessed directly from the databases containing the ICSRs. The reports which will be included in the validation analysis will be identified using the following approach:

1. The number of reported pregnancy exposures in the total database with dual self- and HCP-reported data will be identified and stratified as per **Table 9.1** (below)
2. The required number of random sample self-reports (according to the ANSI quality sampling tables, see **Annex 1**) will be determined
3. The selected exposure and outcome variables will be assessed for completeness and accuracy as completed in self-reports versus the final reports, as verified by a HCP

Table 9.1: Overview of ICSRs from Marketing Authorisation Holders

Report primary source	Report type	Sub-type	Comment
a. Pregnant women	Spontaneous	ICSR	'Traditional' patient report
	Spontaneous	App	App-based report
	Spontaneous	PRIM	Enhanced pharmacovigilance
	Solicited	Patient support programme	Real-world data
b. Healthcare professionals reporting pregnant women	Solicited	Non-interventional study	'Traditional' NIS
	Solicited	Registry	Product-specific
	Spontaneous	ICSR	'Traditional' HCP report
	Spontaneous	PRIM	Enhanced pharmacovigilance
	Literature	ICSR	ICSRs or case series

9.1.2. Setting

This study will be performed in the Novartis global pharmacovigilance database (Argus Safety). In addition to spontaneous reports of ICSRs, Argus Safety contains solicited reports from non-interventional studies and patient support programmes (see **Table 9.1**). In case of duplicates the master ICSR and all related (linked) case reports will be taken into account, in order to aid validation of self-reported outcomes. Data will be analysed from each data source separately and formal comparison of the results will be performed. All reports collected in the timeframe from 10 July 2012 to 31 December 2021 will be eligible for inclusion. From start to finish, the study is expected to take 6 months, comprising 2 months' data extraction, 2 months' data analysis, and 2 months to prepare the report.

Inclusion criteria:

- All ICSRs documenting maternal use of medicines during pregnancy, regardless of pregnancy outcome (including those related to medicines classified as 'suspected' or 'interacting' and for reports of normal outcomes – i.e. no harm reported to mother, fetus or offspring). Although ICSRs are currently not specifically designed to optimally collect data on fetal effects of medications used in pregnancy, reports of exposure in pregnancy are received. Selection of such ICSRs from the Novartis dataset will be based upon a validated SQL query used to retrieve all pregnancy exposures for evaluation in accordance with the requirement for MAHs to evaluate periodically aggregated reports of exposures to medicines in pregnant or lactating women ([Good Vigilance Practice Module VII, Periodic safety update report](#)).

- Coding and assessment of ICSRs must be completed within the timeframe specified above
- In case of duplicates the Master Case (as defined within Section I.C.6.1.2 of [EU Individual Case Safety Report \(ICSR\) Implementation Guide](#)) and all related (linked) reports will be taken into account, in order to aid data validation and quality checking

Exclusion criteria:

- ICSRs reporting pregnancy following paternal medication exposure

9.1.3. Variables

Selected variables to be assessed for completeness:

The variables for the analysis of pregnancy reports are based on the **WP2 Task 3** core data elements defined as 'essential' within:

1. Table 4-2 Core data: Drug exposure
2. Table 4-3 Core data: Pregnancy outcome (Birth Type)
3. Table 4-4 Core data: Fetal outcome (birth – could also updated at follow-up visits)

These data will be assessed for completeness and accuracy (self-reported initial versus HCP-reported, where available). At this stage it is not clear if all essential CDE variables can be taken into account for all report types. This will be assessed in the early stages of this study, and modifications to the approach may be made based on the results of the assessment. These will be detailed and documented in the final study report.

Exposure to medicinal product(s):

Assessments will be made of exposure to medicines, according to the coding system used in each database. Both trade names and generic names (INN) will be accepted and coded according to the existing conventions for each database. Wherever possible source data should be retained for reference purposes. Where imprecise information is provided by the reporter of an ICSR, e.g. 'antibiotic' or 'anticonvulsant' this will be considered to have been provided (reported), but not precise, if confirmed with precision by a HCP e.g. antibiotic administered was amoxicillin, anticonvulsant prescribed was levetiracetam. Incomplete fields (e.g. partial dates, where the date is incomplete, but not wholly missing, that is the day or month or year or any combination of two of these are provided) will be managed according to the standard conventions applicable to the source database.

Pregnancy outcomes:

ICSRs code pregnancy complications (ICH-E2B(R3) field E.i.2.1b) using the Medical Dictionary for Regulatory Activities (MedDRA) according to the version which is applicable when the study is conducted ([Brown 1999](#)). In this sub-study the codes assigned will be grouped and categorized by the researchers involved. The categories will be defined, but not limited to, the below (taking into account the **WP2 Task 2.3** CDE):

- Pregnancy loss
 - Stillbirth
 - Induced termination
 - Spontaneous abortion
 - Ectopic pregnancy

- Molar pregnancy
- Blighted ovum
- Congenital anomalies will be classified according to the EUROCAT standard (EUROCAT [A](#) & [B](#))
 - Minor (e.g. accessory auricle, sacral pit)
 - Major (e.g. cardiac defects, neural tube defects)
 - Not otherwise specified
 - Other
- Chromosomal defects (e.g. trisomy 21, Turner syndrome)
- Other term mapped to the congenital anomalies system organ class (SOC)
- Fetal complications (e.g. intrauterine growth restriction)
- Neonatal complications (e.g. asphyxia, neonatal infection, hypoglycaemia)
- Growth related complications
 - Small for gestational age at delivery
 - Large for gestational age at delivery
 - Fetal growth restriction
- Death of live born infant
- (Neuro)developmental delay (e.g. delayed developmental milestones, cognitive, motor and social deficits)
- Maternal complications
 - Death
 - Medical conditions arising in pregnancy (e.g. preeclampsia)
 - Complications during/after delivery (e.g. post-partum bleeding, placenta praevia)
 - Post-partum complications (e.g. post-partum haemorrhage)
- Maternal none-pregnancy related adverse event (e.g. injection site inflammation)
- No adverse outcome reported either affecting the mother or the offspring (e.g. normal birth, normal newborn, no adverse events in mother or child)

9.1.4. Study size

All ICSRs fulfilling the inclusion criteria will be considered for this sub-study. As the aim is to assess a random sample of the available self-reported data all pregnancy ICSRs will be considered for inclusion in the first part of this study. If the conclusion of the first research is that the number of reports is too high for the timescale and resource allocated to this study, limitations will be applied, for example to focus on selected products or therapeutic areas to focus the analysis of upon validation of medically important variables for known teratogens.

For Argus Safety (Novartis) >30,000 reports of exposure to medicinal products during pregnancy in association with authorised medicinal products are estimated to be included in the database. It has been assumed that the time period selected and requirement for paired HCP and self-reports will limit the selection to a more manageable number.

9.1.5. Data analysis

Descriptive statistics (absolute numbers, percentages) will be used to describe the total number of reports available, the stratified numbers per report source (e.g. SRS, literature), and the stratified numbers for self-reported and HCP-validated ICSRs. For the essential CDE variables (as described in section **9.1.3**) the availability of the data will be assessed, as well as the specificity of each variable, whether or not the information is described in other variables. Thereafter, the completeness of these

variables as “IS NOT NULL” will be determined. Variables that have to be derived from other variables will be derived where possible, and thereafter availability of the information in the variables (how accurately and reliably they are filled) will be assessed. Reports will be compared between different sources (i.e. self-reported versus HCP). Comparative statistics such as Cohen’s Kappa can be calculated to show agreement between the reports. Potential reasons for missing values or discrepancies will be evaluated and reported. The reported pregnancy complications will be categorized as described in **section 9.1.3**. Descriptive statistics (absolute numbers, percentages) will be used to describe the number of accurately validated reports from women, according to report source origin.

9.1.6. Limitations of the research methods

The criteria for determining whether a report is related to pregnancy or not will be based on the EMA pregnancy flag ([EMA 2018](#)) or a validated SQL query based on the requirements set down in the relevant EMA Good Vigilance Practice guidelines. If, during the course of the study, an additional criterion is found to decrease misclassification, this criterion will be taken into account as well. It is often unclear why variables are missing, particularly from spontaneous reports. It cannot be concluded (based on this study design) whether or not completeness of a variable is too low, it is only possible to describe the report as medically valid or not (e.g. for those reports with critical errors – see **Annex 1**). Additionally, ICSRs will include descriptions of both healthy and adverse outcomes. This raises an interesting challenge, it is expected that there will be a high degree of correlation/agreement for the healthy outcome reports, but a greater disparity concerning adverse outcomes. Analyses stratified by the outcome of the pregnancy will be conducted to test this hypothesis.

9.2. Sub-study 2: Validation of parentally completed childhood health and neurodevelopment screening questionnaire; a clinical study into the phenotype associated with fetal valproate spectrum disorder

Due to a combination of important ethical restrictions and statistical/methodological complexities, performing research to assess the safety of maternal medication use in human pregnancy is particularly challenging. [\[Grzeskowiak 2012\]](#) As such, adequate information concerning the impact of prenatal medication exposure on the developing fetus takes many decades to collect. [\[Adam 2011a\]](#) Furthermore, most of the research performed in this field has limited the follow-up of exposed infants to the end of the pregnancy, or up to a maximum of one year after live birth. However, it is known that some adverse health impacts which may arise following prenatal medication exposure may only be detected at a later stage of life (i.e. physical health/neurodevelopmental impairments). [\[Adam 2011a, Hoover 2011\]](#) As such, teratogen/reproductive toxicity surveillance systems which do not perform longer term follow-up of exposed infants are potentially limited in their ability to detect clinically relevant risks which may be associated with *in utero* medication exposures. [\[Thomas 2017\]](#) Also, in contrast with prenatal exposures which result in fetal loss, or even some non-visible malformations that can be surgically corrected to eliminate or reduce physical impairment, prenatal exposures which sufficiently impact offspring health and development can result in the requirement for lifelong healthcare and social support. A high economic impact of developmental disorders has been estimated for some specific conditions. For example, in the United

Kingdom the lifetime cost of supporting an individual with an Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) has been estimated to be between £0.9 and £1.5 million. [[Buescher 2014](#)]

Given the lack of adequate evidence concerning the long-term impacts of prenatal medication exposure, the pregnancy pharmacovigilance data that are available for most medications are currently considered incomplete. This results in an inadequate evidence-base for both medication prescribers and pregnant women alike, and has contributed towards both ambiguous safety recommendations from the manufacturers of medicines [[Arguello 2015](#)] and inaccurate risk perceptions by both healthcare professionals [[Csajka 2014](#), [Damase-Michel 2008](#)] and pregnant women. [[Widnes 2013](#)] Pregnant women therefore often locate and/or receive conflicting guidance on the risks and benefits of gestational medication use, [[Hameen-Anttila 2014](#)] which in turn can result in maternal anxiety over the potential adverse fetal/developmental effects and even poor medication adherence. [[Widnes 2013](#), [Hameen-Anttila 2014](#), [Lupattelli 2014](#)] Considering the potential health impacts which can arise following poor gestational medication adherence, [[Matsui 2012](#)] there is a clear need for an improved pregnancy pharmacovigilance evidence-base to promote the optimised use of medicines in pregnancy.

The development of routine long-term surveillance systems and research tools for use in pregnancy pharmacovigilance is paramount for decreasing the data gaps which exist around the childhood health and development impacts of *in utero* medication exposure. Due to high costs and participant time requirements, wide-scale implementation of routine clinical assessments of childhood health and development for all medications where there may be developmental concerns are generally considered infeasible. However, the development and implementation of a set of routine childhood health and development screening questionnaires, for routine completion by parents of children with prenatal medication exposure, could provide a valuable data source for long-term pregnancy pharmacovigilance. Signals identified by such routine screening would lead to more intensive clinical level investigations.

As described above in **section 7.3**, a set of routine childhood health and neurodevelopment screening questionnaires will be developed in demonstration project **2.5.3**. The objective of this sub-study (**S2**) is to validate the ability of this set of questionnaires (compiled within ConcePTION as the 'LIFETIME' system) to screen for child health and neurodevelopmental impairments. This validation study will attempt to establish clinical thresholds, or cut-off values for the scores generated from the parent reporting questionnaires that can identify risk for minor and major impairment.

Sodium valproate is a known human teratogen, with *in utero* exposure having pronounced impacts on childhood health and neurodevelopment. Prenatal sodium valproate exposure has been associated with an estimated risk of neurodevelopmental impairment in up to 40% of exposed infants, [[Baker 2015](#)] with a 3-15% risk of autism spectrum disorder (ASD) specifically. [[Adab 2004](#), [Bromley 2008](#), [Christensen 2013](#), [Eriksson 2005](#), [Rasalam 2005](#)] As such, families where children have been diagnosed FVSD [[Clayton-Smith 2019](#)] provide an opportunity to validate the ability of the LIFETIME screening questionnaires to detect a wide range of child health and neurodevelopmental symptoms which are found on standard clinical reviews. Additionally, children exposed to valproate but who have not been diagnosed with FVSD and children exposed to topiramate in utero will be recruited as a group expected to be at moderate to lower risk for child health and neurodevelopmental difficulties. These three groups of children will be aged 7 -16 years and will form a single study group to ensure a broad spectrum of childhood health and neurodevelopmental outcomes are included in the validation analysis.

Should the parentally completed questionnaires are able to detect the spectrum of difficulties documented on clinical review, the LIFETIME screening questionnaires could be used for the detection of child health and neurodevelopmental deficits follow exposure *in utero* to medications for which there is limited or no information available .

9.2.1. Study design

This will be an observational data validation study which will compare the results of parentally completed childhood neurodevelopment screening questionnaires with results obtained via clinical face-to-face neuropsychological assessments.

9.2.2. Setting

This study will involve the recruitment of three participant groups, including families living in the UK where children have been: (i) diagnosed with FVSD; (ii) exposed to valproate *in utero* but do not have a diagnosis of FVSD; (iii) unexposed to valproate, but exposed to topiramate *in utero*. These study participants will be recruited from demonstration project **2.5.3** and other sources, including but not limited to, UK National Health Service (NHS) clinics and epilepsy patient support groups/FVSD support charities. After study enrolment, the parent(s) or guardian(s) of the child/children will be asked to self-complete the LIFETIME screening questionnaires online. This will collect parental views on a range of child health and neurodevelopmental outcomes, including reasoning, language, memory, attention, motor, social and executive functioning. These elements were identified to be essential for assessing childhood health and neurodevelopmental attainment in a previous ConcePTION work package task (**WP2 Task 2.3**).

The children will subsequently be assessed in face-to-face clinical sessions where a battery of standardised neuropsychological assessments will be performed, and standard child health and dysmorphology reviews will be completed. These assessments will be performed by trained childhood neuropsychologists at the University of Manchester (UMAN) and the clinical interviews will be conducted by a Clinical Geneticist and Clinical Psychologist with experience of identifying medications effects. The neuropsychological clinical assessments will be undertaken with exposure history masked.

The child's performance on the clinical review in each of the areas listed in **9.2.3** will be reviewed and determined to be 'of concern' or 'within normal limits' based on clinical psychometric scale cut-off values and ICD-11/DSM-5 criteria for conditions (e.g. Social Communication Disorder). The submitted questionnaire data will be reviewed and compared to the clinical assessments. Where standardised cut-off values for determining developmental status (i.e. "within normal limits", "of concern") have been previously established for questionnaires, the psychometric properties of these values will be formally investigated (e.g. AUC, sensitivity, specificity) and different cut-off values will be explored to determine the optimal cut-off value in each context. For questionnaires that do not have previously established standardised cut-off values, formal analysis will be carried out to establish the optimal cut-off value for indicating developmental status. In doing this, the ability of the LIFETIME screening questionnaires to identify poorer health and neurodevelopmental outcomes will be compared against the clinical ratings.

Overall, the results of the face-to-face clinical assessment will be used to validate the ability of parental reporters and the LIFETIME screening questionnaires to identify (using standardised score/ psychometric scale cut-off values) children who have health or neurodevelopmental difficulties.

9.2.3. Variables

There will be a focus on assessing the most important data content of the childhood neurodevelopment screening questionnaires by comparing specified core data elements, as defined by **WP2 Task 2.3**, including but not limited to self-reported pregnancy exposures and questionnaire/clinically generated scores of neurodevelopmental attainments/deficits. The LIFETIME Screening Questionnaires will be assessed on their ability to detect difficulties or poorer outcomes in the following domains:

- Cognitive; reasoning, memory, language, attention, executive functioning
- Academic functioning
- Social functioning
- Motor functioning
- Emotion and behaviour: Internalising (depression, anxiety), externalising, attention problems
- Health conditions
- Dysmorphic facial presentation

9.2.4. Study size

Owing to the time required to perform clinical review of study participants, and to process clinical data post-assessment, it is estimated that a maximum of 60 study participants could be included in this validation study. This sample size will allow for sufficient conclusions to be drawn regarding the ability of the screening questionnaires to collect the data required to perform assessments of childhood neurodevelopment and physical health due to the in-depth nature of the data being collected.

9.2.5. Data analysis

In this validation sub-study, exposure- and outcome-related data (in line with specified core data elements, as defined by **WP2 Task 2.3**) collected from the parentally-completed childhood neurodevelopment screening questionnaires will be compared for completeness and accuracy with the results obtained from the clinical face-to-face neuropsychological assessments. Agreement between parental reports and clinical assessment results will be quantified using a range of statistical approaches, including (where appropriate) Cohen's Kappa statistic, correlation coefficients, receiver operating characteristic (ROC) and area under the curve (AUC) plots, and calculations of sensitivity/specificity. Descriptive statistics and qualitative methods may also be utilised where required.

9.2.6. Limitations of the research methods

The aim of this study is to validate the ability of an electronic questionnaire to collect the core data elements required to assess childhood neurodevelopment and physical health following *in utero* medication exposure. This study will utilise assessment data from a group of children aged 7-16 years who have varying degree of risk for health and neurodevelopmental difficulties. Parentally completed questionnaires have previously been criticised for use in neuroteratogen surveillance

([Damkier 2017](#)), in part, due to concerns that these questionnaires have not been validated for use in this field. This group recognises that the LIFETIME screening system, even if validated for detecting child health and neurodevelopmental difficulties, is there to generate signals which would then require clinical level investigation to either confirm or refute the signal.

The main limitations of this study surround the sample size of the validation study. Whilst the study methods detailed above attempt to ensure a range of participants at high, moderate and low risk for health or neurodevelopmental difficulties, it may only be possible to conclude that the LIFETIME screening system is only sufficient to detect substantial difficulties (which is anticipated to require fewer study participants).

10. Quality control and data management

10.1. Data recording and retention

Quality monitoring for completeness and correctness of data retrieved from the included data sources will be performed. In **S2**, all self-reported and clinically collected data will be recorded electronically, and stored at UMAN in accordance with the applicable data protection legislation (UK). Backups of the original electronic records will be maintained for at least the duration of the study, and for a period thereafter in accordance with local requirements/procedures (**S1** – Novartis and **S2** – UMAN).

10.2. Confidentiality and coding

Project data will be managed with the discretion expected of healthcare professionals, and will only be made accessible to authorized personnel who require access to the data in order to fulfil their duties within the scope of the research project. Data will not include any personally identifiable information (PII), and wherever appropriate the 'privacy' feature in Argus Safety will be invoked to ensure that PII is masked before any data are output. Though data will be provided in an anonymised approach, non-disclosure (confidentiality) agreements will be signed by researchers involved in processing or assessing the data.

10.3. Data collection and transmission

As the data are already held and maintained by the MAH (Novartis), no additional data collections will be performed in **S1**. Protected PII data utilised in the performance of **S1** will not be transmitted outside of the MAH (Novartis) pharmacovigilance system.

Two data collection processes exist in **S2**. The first will involve the parental completion of the childhood neurodevelopment screening questionnaires. These data will be collected via the Qualitrics platform, with the data stored at UMAN. The second data collection will be obtained via clinical face-to-face neuropsychological assessments. Clinical assessment data will be also be stored at UMAN. De-identified copies of the parentally completed childhood neurodevelopment screening questionnaires coupled with the corresponding results of the face-to-face neuropsychological assessments will be securely transferred to Newcastle upon Tyne Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust (NUTH) for validation analysis. Study participants will be informed of this data transfer during study participation consent, and will have opportunities to discuss the process with the study team. Participant agreement to this data transfer will be a pre-requisite for participation in the study. Data

transferred to NUTH will be securely stored on the NHS information technology network, and shall only be accessible to those directly involved with the data analysis.

Aggregate data produced through the validation analysis will be shared between all study partners. No individual patients will be identified or identifiable within this dataset.

11. Protection of human subjects

The protection of human subjects is dependent on national regulations. As this project is performed in various settings, the applicable laws per location will be discussed, including data privacy. **S1** will be performed using existing data which exist in the MAH (Novartis) global safety database (Argus Safety). No new data will be collected for this sub-study, and no additional ethical approvals are required to analyse the data already held within the ICSR database. **S2** will involve the use of data collected from a sub-study of demonstration study **2.5.4**. This sub-study will involve the recruitment of study participants in the UK, and will therefore require research ethics approval, which will be independently assessed by the NHS Health Research Authority. To attain research ethics approval to perform this study in the UK, a participant information sheet will be developed that will explain the study and the expectations of study participants in detail. An informed consent form to guide study participant's understanding of the research, including the aims, objectives, methods and planned results will also be developed. These two materials will clearly explain how the data generated in the 2.5.4 sub-study will be utilised in the **S2** validation study of demonstration project **2.5.5**.

12. Management and reporting of adverse events/adverse reactions

The two sub-studies (**S1** and **S2**) within demonstration study 5 of ConcePTION task 2.5 are non-interventional, observational studies which are not testing investigational medicinal products. Neither **S1** nor **S2** will analyse data in a manner that would be likely to yield evidence of a new adverse event or previously unreported adverse reaction. In the unlikely event that a potential safety signal is detected during the course of these demonstration studies, signals will be handled according to the current and national legislation (regulations) and guidelines ([EMA 2017](#)).

13. Plans for disseminating and communicating study results

Results of this study will be published as a report on the ConcePTION website and in submitted to a peer reviewed scientific journal. Authorship in scientific publication will have to satisfy the conditions of the Uniform Requirements for Manuscripts Submitted to Biomedical Journals (www.icmje.org/icmje-recommendations.pdf.)

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Annex 1. ANSI standard tables for quality sampling ('AQL tables')

One hundred percent inspection and validation of ICSRs is not considered feasible for this research. As a result the required number of self-reports for random sampling will be calculated according to the ANSI quality sampling tables (35 Sources: Mil-Std 105E, replaced by commercial standards: ISO2859, ANSI/ASQ Z1.4-2003, NF06-022, BS 6001, DIN 40080). The method of calculation of the required number of cases for validation was the Acceptable Quality Limit (AQL) Sampling Simulator (36). This random sampling method applies statistics, rather than a fixed percentage, based on the total sample size available for assessment. Strictly this method is applicable to fixed batches of consumer goods, but it has been adopted for quality assessment within pharmacovigilance systems. Proposed settings for the AQL applicable to pregnancy and breastfeeding exposures and outcomes are:

- 0% for critical defects (defined as totally unacceptable: data content is unreliable such as an incorrectly coded medicinal product, or regulations are not respected deviation from ICHE2B(R3) structure leading to a rejection under the EudraVigilance business rules);
- 2.5% for major defects (these ICSRs would usually not be considered unacceptable by the assessor, but there is at least one important inconsistency, such as a partial date which does not permit the accurate calculation of the trimester of exposure for a late 1st/early 2nd trimester case report);
- 4.0% for minor defects (there may be some minor departure from ICSR specifications, but there is no medical importance as a consequence e.g. use of synonymous but not identical medical terms, such as hives vs. urticaria, typographical errors, poor use of English in the narrative text).

AQL Sampling Simulator

Quantity: Inspection Level:

CRITICAL defects		
Select AQL: <input type="text" value="Not Allowed"/>	Accept Point: 0	Reject Point: 0
Sample Size: 80 ICSRs		

MAJOR defects		
Select AQL: <input type="text" value="1.0"/>	Accept Point: 2	Reject Point: 3
Sample Size: 80 ICSRs		

MINOR defects		
Select AQL: <input type="text" value="1.0"/> <input type="text" value="n.b. 10%"/>	Accept Point: 14	Reject Point: 15
Sample Size: 80 ICSRs		

Example: For a validation of 1,000 ICSRs, I selected level II 'normal inspection' and AQL of 0 for critical defects, 2.5% for major defects, and 10% for minor defects.

In the upper below, I referred to the intersection of the respective ICSR sample size and General Inspection Level indicates sample size code letter J. Then, I referred to the lower table, located row J, which indicates the required sample size of 80. To comply with AQL of:

- 0% critical errors, no ICSRs from the sample size may fail the inspection with a critical error;
- 4% major errors, 7 ICSRs from the sample size may fail the inspection with a major error;
- 6.5% minor errors, 10 ICSRs from the sample size may fail the inspection with a minor error;

SAMPLE SIZE CODE LETTERS							
Lot Size	General Inspection Levels			Special Inspection Levels			
	I	II	III	S1	S2	S3	S4
2 to 8	A	A	B	A	A	A	A
9 to 15	A	B	C	A	A	A	A
16 to 25	B	C	D	A	A	B	B
26 to 50	C	D	E	A	B	B	C
51 to 90	C	E	F	B	B	C	C
91 to 150	D	F	G	B	B	C	D
151 to 280	E	G	H	B	C	D	E
281 to 500	F	H	J	B	C	D	E
501 to 1200	G	J	K	C	C	E	F
1201 to 3200	H	K	L	C	D	E	G
3201 to 10000	J	L	M	C	D	F	G
10001 to 35000	K	M	N	C	D	F	H
35001 to 150000	L	N	P	D	E	G	J
150001 to 500000	M	P	Q	D	E	G	J
500001 and over	N	Q	R	D	E	H	K

ANSI/ASQ Standard Z1.4 - 2008

SINGLE SAMPLING PLANS FOR NORMAL INSPECTION												
Sample Size Code Letter	Sample Size	Acceptable Quality Levels (Normal Inspection)										
		0.065	0.10	0.15	0.25	0.40	0.65	1.0	1.5	2.5	4.0	6.5
		Ac Re	Ac Re	Ac Re	Ac Re	Ac Re	Ac Re	Ac Re	Ac Re	Ac Re	Ac Re	Ac Re
A	2											0 1
B	3											0 1
C	5											0 1
D	8											0 1
E	13											0 1
F	20											0 1
G	32											0 1
H	50											0 1
J	80											0 1
K	125											0 1
L	200											0 1
M	315											0 1
N	500											0 1
P	800											0 1
Q	1250											0 1
R	2000											0 1

↑ Use first sampling plan above arrow, if sample size equals or exceeds lot or batch size, do 100 percent inspection.
 ↓ Use first sampling plan below arrow AC : Acceptance number Re : Rejection number